

Clock genes and Photoperiodism in the Aphid *Acyrtosiphon pisum*

Miquel Barberà Solà

Tesi dirigida pel Dr. David Martínez Torres

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En David Martínez Torres, Professor Titular del Departament de Genètica i membre de l'Institut Cavanilles de Biodiversitat i Biologia Evolutiva de la Universitat de València

INFORME que Miquel Barberà Solà, Llicenciat en Bioquímica per la Universitat de València, ha realitzat baix la meua direcció el treball que porta per títol: "Clock genes and photoperiodism in the aphid *Acyrtosiphon pisum*.", per a optar al Grau de doctor per la Universitat de València.

I per a que conste, en compliment de la legislació vigent, signe el present informe a València, a 6 de desembre de 2016.

Sign.: Dr. David Martínez Torres

Les següents paraules són un xicotet agraïment a totes les persones que, d'alguna o altra manera, m'han donat suport per a fer possible aquesta tesi doctoral.

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I. Introduction

1. Aphid General Biology

Aphids are soft-bodied hemimetabolous insects that feed on plant phloem sap and are mainly distributed in temperate regions of the northern hemisphere (Blackman and Eastop, 2000). Of the approximately 5000 species of aphids, 250 are classified as agricultural pests that cause important losses on crop production by direct damage or as vectors of plant viruses (Oerke, 1994). Aphid body size varies from 1 to 10 mm (Dixon, 1985). Their characteristic stylet is comprised of modified mouthparts which are used to pierce through plant tissue and reach the vascular system to feed on plant sap (Emden, 1989). Most characteristic of aphids is the confluence of several polyphenisms, the most studied of which are wing dimorphism and polymorphisms associated with cyclic parthenogenesis that define their characteristic complex life cycles. Aphid development is characterised by the succession of four larval stages named L1 to L4 with the corresponding three larval moults and a final moulting process from which the adult emerges.

The publication of the sequence of the pea aphid genome in 2010 (The International Aphid Genomics Consortium, 2010) strongly contributed to advance in the study of aphids in general, and the pea aphid *Acyrtosiphon pisum* (Harris) in particular. The pea aphid genome is particularly large (ca. 540 Mbp), arranged in four holocentric chromosomes (Blackman, 1987) containing ca. 37000 predicted transcripts (Brisson et al., 2016) and ca. 28000 predicted proteins¹. The genome of *A. pisum* has one of the lowest G/C content among insects (The International Aphid Genomics Consortium,

1 https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome/448?genome_assembly_id=29162

2010). The large number of genes found in *A. pisum* when compared with other insects is a consequence of gene expansion of genes families related to chromatin remodelling, miRNA synthesis and sugar transport, as well as the presence of aphid specific genes (Huerta-Cepas et al., 2010).

1.1. Phylogenetic issues

Insects are considered the most diverse animal group in the history of life (Rota-Stabelli et al., 2013). Although there are significant extinct groups, most extant lineages appeared approximately 250 Mya, and many living insect families originated in the Cretaceous approximately 120 Mya (Grimaldi and Engel, 2005). As other arthropods, insects have a chitinous exoskeleton known as cuticle that provides protection against external environment. Most studies include aphids in the order Hemiptera (Figure I.1), the most diverse non-holometabolous insect group (Grimaldi and Engel, 2005; Song et al., 2012). Hemipteran diversity is related to angiosperms radiation (Grimaldi and Engel, 2005) and all hemipterans are characterised by the loss of maxillary and labial palps and by the presence of a sucking beak (also known as *rostrum*). Hemipterans include four monophyletic suborders: Sternorrhyncha, Auchenorrhyncha, Coleorrhyncha and Heteroptera (Figure I.2 A), although the monophyly of Auchenorrhyncha is questioned and some authors propose that it should be divided into two groups, Cicadomorpha and Fulgoromorpha (Song et al., 2016a, 2016b). Aphids are included within Sternorrhyncha, which recent phylogenetic analysis place in a basal position within Hemiptera (Misof et al., 2014; Song et al., 2016a, 2016b). Sternorrhyncha mouthparts are ventral and opisthognathous (i.e. oriented backwards), with long fine stylets that are coiled inside the *rostrum* when not being used. Stylets consist of

Figure I.1. Simplified insect phylogeny modified from Kjer et al. (2016). Phylogenetic position of Hemiptera, the order where aphids are included, is highlighted in red.

modified maxillae and mandibles that are used to penetrate the plant tissue in order to reach the sieve tubes. The sedentary way of life caused by the feeding habits of some sternorrhynchans have stimulated the appearance of defence adaptations against desiccation and predators such as wax secretion, gall formation and symbiotic relationships with ants. Sternorrhyncha encompasses superfamilies Psylloidea, Aleyroidea,

Coccoidea and Aphidomorpha (see Figure I.2 A). The superfamily Aphidomorpha originated in the Triassic (220-210 Mya) and includes 5000 insect species classified in the families Adelgidae, Phylloxeridae and Aphididae (Grimaldi and Engel, 2005; Heie and Wegierek, 2009). Adelgidae and Phylloxeridae are considered basal groups (Sorensen, 2009). Although the term aphid has been used for all the members of Aphidomorpha, in this thesis it will refer only to members of the family Aphididae, also known as true aphids (Figure I.2 B). Members of the superfamily Aphidomorpha share cyclical parthenogenesis, being the asexual phase originally oviparous, as it is the case for extant adelgids and phylloxerans, while viviparity was acquired only in true-aphids (i.e. Aphididae) (Sorensen, 2009). Adelgids feed mainly on conifers, as thought to have been the case of ancestral aphids, while members of Phylloxeridae feed on plant families such as Fagaceae, Juglandaceae, Rosaceae, Ulmaceae, and Vitaceae (Heie, 1987). There are more than 4700 aphid species (family Aphididae) distributed around the globe, although aphid diversity is mostly concentrated in northern temperate regions (Heie, 1994; Remaudière and Remaudière, 1997). Most aphid species are included in the subfamilies Eriosomatinae (301 species), Calaphidinae (358 species), Lachninae (346 species) and, specially, Aphidinae (2483 species) (see Figure I.2 B) (www.aphidsonworldsplants.info, accessed 29th October of 2015). The species object of study in this thesis, *Acyrtosiphon pisum*, is included in the latter subfamily. Members of the family Aphididae are characterised by complex life cycles including host alternation in many species. True-aphids exhibit special traits such as cornicles or *siphunculi*, lack of ovipositor, harbouring of endosymbiotic bacteria and, in some cases, eusociality (Davis, 2012). Fossil evidence (Grimaldi and Engel, 2005) and the fact that many

Figure I.2. A) Phylogeny of order Hemiptera. Phylogenetic relationships of suborders Heteroptera, Fulgoromorpha, Coleorrhyncha, Cicadomorpha and Sternorrhyncha as proposed by Song et al. (2016a). Aphids (Aphidomorpha) belong to the suborder Sternorrhyncha (shown in red), that also includes superfamilies Coccoidea (scale bugs), Psylloidea (psyllids) and Aleyrodidae (white flies) (von Dohlen and Moran, 1995). **B)** Aphidomorpha phylogeny showing the position of different aphid subfamilies within family Aphididae. The species object of study in the present thesis, *Acyrtosiphon pisum*, as well as other mentioned species, such as *Myzus persicae* and *Megoura viciae*, belong to tribe Macrosiphini within subfamily Aphidinae (indicated in red). Modified from Ortiz-Rivas and Martínez-Torres (2010).

aphid species occupying basal positions in currently reported phylogenies (Ortiz-Rivas and Martínez-Torres, 2010) feed on conifers, support the view that ancestral aphids fed on gymnosperms. The radiation of angiosperms (Grimaldi and Engel, 2005) in the Late Cretaceous provided new niches for aphid colonisation that prompted a rapid aphid radiation in the Miocene (Cenozoic), after most aphids became extinct during the Cretaceous-Tertiary boundary (Von Dohlen, 2000). Although there is a clear support for the monophyly of the family Aphididae, as a consequence of the rapid radiation of aphid lineages during the transition from gymnosperms to angiosperms there is still a lack of resolution of phylogenetic relationships at deep subfamily nodes, which has led to different phylogenetic proposals (Ortiz-Rivas et al., 2004; Ortiz-Rivas and Martínez-Torres, 2010; Pérez-Brocal et al., 2011; Nováková et al., 2013).

1.2. General Morphology and Anatomy

In general, aphids are ovoid-shaped, soft-bodied, small insects. As most other insects, aphids have a segmented body that can be divided into three main parts: the head, the thorax and the abdomen (Figure 1.3). These parts are hardly discernible in aphids due to a high degree of fusion between segments. The head contains sensory organs such as the antenna, compound eyes, *triommatidia* and *ocelli*, as well as the neural organs to process the information. Additionally, the head includes the mouthparts and associated organs. The compound eyes can be absent in some species or particular morphs. The *triommatidia* consist of three faceted cells located at the posterior region of each of the compound eyes. The three *ocelli* are specific of winged aphid morphs and are also present in apterous males. The *ocelli* are placed on the dorsal region of the head, one next to

each of the compound eyes and the other located on the antero-medial region of the head. In the antenna reside the *rhinaria*, the olfactory organs. As other hemipterans, aphids have modified maxillary and mandibular piercing mouthparts that form the stylet. The stylet bundle rests over a modified *labium* also known as *rostrum* that sheathes the stylet (Miyazaki, 1987b). The stylet penetrates the plant allowing to reach the phloem sap within the sieve elements. Aphids produce two types of saliva: gelling saliva, from principal salivary glands, forms a lubricated sheath for stylet penetration in plant tissue and watery saliva, secreted from accessory salivary glands, acts as lubricant, host recognition, suppression of host defences and external digestion among other functions (Moreno et al., 2011). Plant sap is an unbalanced diet rich in carbohydrates but missing essential amino acids which makes it a resource not suitable for all species (Akman Gunduz and Douglas, 2009). The capability to exploit such an unbalanced diet was provided by an endosymbiotic association with the γ -proteobacteria *Buchnera aphidicola*, which allowed aphids to improve their ecological success by means of exploitation of niches with poor competition such as the phloem sap (Baumann, 2005). Ancestral aphids were able to take advantage of plant sap by a single event association with the ancestor of *Buchnera aphidicola* (γ -proteobacterium) 80-200 Mya (Bracho et al., 1995; Latorre et al., 2005; Gil et al., 2006; Lamelas et al., 2011). Since the original infection, aphids and their bacterial endosymbionts have coevolved, becoming obligate partners. The bacteria are located in a bilobed bacteriome, a specialised structure in the abdomen consisting of aphid cells, called bacteriocytes, which harbour *B. aphidicola*. Besides *B. aphidicola*, which is considered the primary endosymbiont, aphids also may contain secondary, facultative endosymbionts such as

Figure I.3. Side view of the apterous parthenogenetic morph of *Macromyzus woodardiae* (Aphidinae) depicting the main external morphology. Abd, abdomen; An, antenna; Ca, *cauda*; Ce, compound eyes; Cx, *coxae*; Fm, femur; Hd, head; Ms, mesothorax; Mt, metathorax; Pr, prothorax; Rt, *rostrum*; Si, *siphunculum*; St, stylet; Tb, tibia, Th, thorax; To, *triommatidium*; Ts, tarsus. Modified from Miyazaki (1987b).

Regiella insecticola, *Hamiltonella defensa*, *Rickettsia viridis*, *Wolbachia sp.* and *Serratia symbiotica*, whose functions are more heterogeneous. For example they can provide defence against parasitoid wasps, heat resistance or defence against fungal infections (Baumann, 2005; Lamelas et al., 2008; Manzano-Marin and Latorre, 2014). As previously explained, aphids feed continuously on phloem sap, an unbalanced diet rich in sugars but poor in

amino acids (Sandström and Moran, 1999; Douglas, 2006). The excess of sugars is secreted through the anus as small droplets of honeydew. Honeydew still represents a precious resource which is used by many insects, birds and even flying foxes. The case of ants is noteworthy and has been well studied. Ants and aphids have developed a mutualistic relationship in which ants obtain honeydew as a nutritional resource and aphids gain protection from natural enemies and hygienic services (Stadler and Dixon, 2005). The feeding activity of aphids produces a direct damage to plants by diverting plant nutrients for their own profit and as a result of the phytotoxicity of the aphid saliva. Additionally, aphids may also cause indirect damage by transmission of phytoviruses that can be carried in the cuticle or in the salivary glands, as well as saprophytic ascomycetes growing encouraged by the deposition of honeydew (Dedryver et al., 2010). Damage to plants is further enhanced by cyclical parthenogenesis and telescoping of generations (Dixon, 1985) displayed by aphids that confer a high demographic potential.

The thorax is the region specialised in aphid movement. It comprises three pairs of legs (see Figure 1.3). It is composed of three fused segments, antero-posteriorly named prothorax, mesothorax and metathorax (also referred to as T1, T2 and T3, respectively). Each of the legs consists of a *coxae*, femur, *tibiae* and *tarsi*, being the *coxae* the joining to the thorax and the *tarsi* the more distal part (see Figure 1.3). Hind leg *tibiae* of oviparous sexual females of many aphid species are swollen compared to those of asexual viviparous females, due to the development of scent plates (Harrington, 1985). Winged aphid morphs show heavier sclerotisation in head and thorax, and have two pair of wings in meso- and metatoraces (T2 and T3, respectively), being the fore pair larger than the hind pair, with

associated flight musculature (Braendle et al., 2006; Ogawa and Miura, 2013).

The abdomen originally consisted of ten segments of which the 9th is usually atrophied and the 10th is modified to form the *cauda*, a specialised structure to prevent the honeydew droplets flowing towards the abdomen (see Figure I.3). The *cauda* also facilitates flicking off the droplets or holding of the honeydew to help its delivery to ants in myrmecophilous species (Heie, 2009; Sorensen, 2009). At the posterior dorsal region it is commonly found the *siphunculi* or cornicles, which are tubular shaped organs with glandular cells at their base that produce alarm pheromones (Dewhirst et al., 2010).

Central nervous system

Given the relevance for the present work, the aphid central nervous system (CNS) will be described in more detail. The CNS of Hemiptera is characterised by the complete fusion of all abdominal neuromeres and, in the case of aphids (Figure I.4), also the fusion of the thoracic neuromeres (Niven et al., 2008; Kollmann et al., 2011). The aphid CNS (see Figure I.4 A) consists of four main parts: the brain (BR), the suboesophageal ganglion (SOG), the thoracic ganglionic mass (TGM) and the ventral nerve cord (VNC). The aphid brain anatomy has been recently updated by Kollmann et al. (2011), which describe three main parts: the *protocerebrum* (PC), the *deutocerebrum* (DC) and the *tritocerebrum* (TC). The PC (see Figure I.4 B) is the largest and more dorsal part. It is formed by two hemispheres that include the well developed optic lobes (OL), the central complex (CC) which comprises the central body (CB), the protocerebral bridge (PB), the lateral

Figure I.4. Central nervous system (CNS) of the aphid *A. pisum*. **A)** Dorsal view of a dissected CNS including the brain (BR), the suboesophageal ganglion (SOG), the thoracic ganglionic mass (TGM). The neuromeres corresponding to the SOG and the TGM are respectively indicated with numbers (S1, S2, T1, T2 and T3). **B)** Anterior view of a representation of the brain and selected neuropils. AL, antennal lobe; CB, central body; DL, dorsal lobe; La, lamina; LAL, lateral accessory lobe; LoX, lobula complex; Me, medulla; MB, mushroom body; PB, protocerebral bridge. Taken from (Kollmann et al., 2011). Bar = 100 μ m.

accessory lobes (LAL) and the poorly developed mushroom bodies (MB). Each of the OL consists of three main parts: the closest to the retina is the lamina (La), the medial part is the medulla (Me), and the proximal part is the lobula complex (LoX), which is subdivided into outer, inner and dorso-medial lobes (see Figure I.4 B). The posterior region of the PC is connected to the *corpora cardiaca* through the *nervi corpori cardiaci* (NCC) (Hardie, 1987a; Emden, 1989). The DC lays ventrally to the PC and it encloses the antennal and dorsal lobes. The antennal lobes are located ventro-medially to the oesophagus and consist of several *glomeruli* structures (Kollmann et al., 2011). The TC is the most ventral region and consists of two conical lobes connected by a dorsal commissure that innervate the mouthparts.

The SOG lays ventrally to the oesophagus and posteriorly to the brain (see Figure I.4 A), to which is connected by a pair of circumoesophageal commissures. It consists of two suboesophageal neuromeres fused together, named S1 and S2 (see Figure I.4 A). The three thoracic neuromeres are referred to as T1, T2 and T3 (also pro-, meso- and metathorax, respectively). The thoracic neuromeres are fused together with the first abdominal ganglia forming a compact mass known as TGM. From the dorsolateral part of the TGM small nerves arise that innervate spiracle musculature while large ventral nerves innervate the legs. In winged morphs, extra innervation for wing musculature is present. The ventral nerve cord emerges from the posterior part of the TGM and runs through the abdomen where it innervates the reproductive tract and the hind gut.

In a series of classical studies on brains of the vetch aphid *M. viciae* (Steel, 1977, 1978; Steel and Lees, 1977) the repertoire of neurosecretory cells (NSC) in the aphid central nervous system was characterised, particularly in the *protocerebrum* (Figure I.5). By using a para-aldehyde fuchsin (PAF), a staining specific to neurosecretory material, five bilateral groups of NSC were identified in the aphid brain (see Figure I.5 A) (Steel, 1977). In comparison to the NSC repertoire of other insects, aphids have a rather small number of NSC but more widely separated (Steel, 1977). The NSC group I consists of two groups of five cells with well developed endoplasmic reticulum located in the dorsal anterior region of the *protocerebrum* known as *pars intercerebralis* (PI). The axons of these cells run through the neuropil ventral to the central body and posteriorly into the protocerebral neuropil (see Figure I.13 B). Additionally, shorter

Figure 1.5. Schematic drawings of *Megoura viciae* central nervous system showing the neurosecretory cell (NSC) repertoire. **A)** Dorsal view of the brain in which the position of different NSC groups is shown. Destruction of pars intercerebralis (in blue) or pars lateralis (in red) averted photoperiodic response in aphids reared in SD condition (for details see Photoperiodic effectors in section 1.2.2). A, antenna; CE, compound eye; TO, triommatidium; OE, oesophagus; NCC, nervi corpori cardiaci; CC, corpus cardiacum; CA, corpus allatum. **B)** Dorsal view of aphid ganglia in which the localisation of different NSC are indicated. COC, circumoesophageal connective; DNT, dorsal longitudinal neuropilar; LN, labial nerve; PI, *pars intercerebralis*; PL, *pars lateralis*; SN, nerves to mandibular and maxillary stylet muscles; SOG, suboesophageal ganglion; TGM, thoracic ganglionic mass; VNC, ventral nerve cord. Bars = 100 μ m. Modified from Steel (1977).

collaterals¹ bifurcated close to the soma and ran posteriorly along the dorsal neuropil of the central body originating arborisation patterns that produced synapses in this region. The main processes, continued ventrally and posteriorly through the protocerebral neuropil and had characteristic swollen regions that could be seen along all the process reaching the ganglia. These main axons followed through the circumoesophageal connective entering the suboesophageal ganglion (SOG) (see Figure I.13) and the thoracic ganglionic mass (TGM) and finally emerged from the posterior part of the TGM continuing through the ventral nerve cord, probably reaching the ovarioles (Steel and Lees, 1977). This group of NSC was also found in *Aphis fabae* but the axonal projections could not be distinguished (Johnson, 1963). The NSC group II were located more dorsal and lateral than NSC group I (see Figure I.5 A). This group consisted of two cells of different morphology: a lateral spherical neuron and a medial teardrop-shaped neuron. As also seen in *A. fabae* (Johnson, 1963), the axons of the teardrop-shaped NSC could be traced ventromedially along the posterior protocerebrum, where they met with the axon of the contralateral equivalent. A distension is formed in this region generating a reservoir of neurosecretory material (NSM). A single axon emerges posteriorly from the reservoir that bifurcates: one collateral enters the *nervi corpori cardiaci* II (NCC II) and the *corpus cardiacum* (see Figure I.13 B) while the other joined the main tracts of the NSC group I reaching the ventral nerve cord (Steel, 1977). The NSC group III is located posterior and laterally to the NSC group II and it consisted of a single cell per brain hemisphere (see Figure I.5 A). Finally, the NSC group IV were located deeply in the posterior part of the *protocerebrum*, near to the underlying neuropil

¹ Secondary tracts that branch from the original main axon.

and close to the tentorial muscles (see Figure I.5 A). The NSC group V was comprised by three or four cells located in the lateral protocerebrum, very close to the optic lobe (see Figure I.5 A). Axons originating from groups IV and V could not be traced much further than the neuron soma. The SOG and TGM also contained NSC in the dorsal lateral cortex that were arranged in pairs, each neuromere containing two pairs of cells (see Figure I.5 B). The SOG contained two additional NSC. The posterior part of the TGM contained a large group of approximately 15 cells located ventrally to the neuropil.

1.3. Aphid Life Cycles and Polyphenisms

The general aphid life cycle is characterised by cyclical parthenogenesis in which several successive generations of viviparous asexual (clonal) females that occur during favourable seasons (spring and summer) alternate with a single sexual generation in autumn consisting of males and oviparous females that, after mating, will produce winter resistant eggs (Figure I.6). In evolutionary terms, parthenogenesis was acquired approximately 250-200 Mya by the Aphidomorpha ancestor (Simon et al., 2002; Davis, 2012; Ogawa and Miura, 2014). Later, between 200 and 140 Mya, viviparity appeared in the asexual phase of the ancestor of current Aphididae, while Phylloxeridae and Adelgidae retained oviparity (Dixon, 1985; Davis, 2012). This type of cycle has allowed aphids to reach high population growth rates during the favourable seasons reproducing by parthenogenesis while retaining the faculty to endure harsh winters through the sexual egg. Although viviparous and oviparous females of the same lineage are genetic clones, their respective morphology shows several differences. As previously described, viviparous females, usually referred to as *virginoparae*, can be

Figure 1.6. Life cycle of monoecious species *A. pisum*. In spring, the first generation of parthenogenetic females, known as *fundatrix*, hatches from diapausing overwintering eggs. During the favourable seasons successive generations of viviparous parthenogenetic females occur. Winged morphs specialised in dispersion may appear as a consequence of stress signals, such as overpopulation during the parthenogenetic phase of the cycle. In autumn, short day photoperiods induce the sexual phase of the cycle by triggering the appearance of *sexuparae*, the last parthenogenetic generation that gives birth to to the sexual morphs. Finally, males and sexual females mate and the latter produce diapausing eggs that will endure the harsh, cold winter. Adapted from Cortés (2010).

either winged or apterous (wingless) with many morphological and physiological differences. The flight-adapted winged morphs represent an adaptation for dispersal, being thus characterised by a specific behaviour, a functional flight apparatus and specialised sensory organs (Emden, 1989; Braendle et al., 2006). On the other hand, the apterous parthenogenetic females are adapted for rapid colonisation being thus characterised by fast growth and high fecundity (Braendle et al., 2006).

Although many characteristics that will be discussed below are general for aphids, most of the morphological descriptions below correspond to the aphid *Acyrtosiphon pisum*, which is the species object of the present study. The first generation of aphids hatching from the sexual eggs, usually in spring, are classically known as *fundatrix*. Generally, this morph has shorter antenna, legs and *siphunculi*, and its head is smaller than those of *virginoparae* of the next generations. Although fundatrices are also viviparous and parthenogenetic, the term *virginoparae* is restricted to the parthenogenetic generations following *fundatrix* (Miyazaki, 1987a). In many aphid species adult *virginoparae* are easily distinguishable from *oviparae* by the red dots visible through the abdomen corresponding to the compound eyes of the more developed embryos developing inside the abdomen of their mother (see Figure 1.6). In fact, the parthenogenetic phase of the aphid life cycle is characterised by the so called telescoping of generations, which means that the developing embryos within the adults already contain embryos developing inside (Dixon, 1985). Thus, the abdomen of an adult *virginoparae* already contains developing embryos of the two following generations. On the other hand, oviparous females are characterised by having swollen metathoracic *tibiae*, where the scent plaques are located (Hardie and Lees, 1981; Harrington, 1985), and an

abdomen lacking any visible red dots (see above) but with a greenish coloration instead consequence of the deposition of the chorion on the eggs developing inside (Miyazaki, 1987a; Miura et al., 2003). Parthenogenetic females that will give birth to the sexual morphs are known as *sexuparae*, which externally are similar (usually indistinguishable) to *virginoparae* (see Figure I.6). Males have a much smaller size and a fusiform body (see Figure I.6), while females are often round or pear shaped. Irrespective of the morph (apterous or winged parthenogenetic females, sexual females and males), most aphids undergo four larval instars named L1 to L4 which are the result of three larval moulting processes. The L4 individuals experience a final moult from which the adult emerges.

Most characteristic of aphids is the diversity and complexity of their life cycles (Moran, 1992). Aphids are able to cope with different changing conditions by switching to different alternative discrete morphs with specific morphology and behaviour (Sorensen, 2009). This adaptation is known as phenotypic plasticity, which is the ability to produce a wide range of phenotypes from a single genotype (Nijhout, 2003). Aphids display a particular type of phenotypic plasticity known as polyphenism (Nijhout, 1999), in which different environmental conditions induce the development of appropriate discrete phenotypes or specific morphs in order to improve survival to external environmental conditions (Tagu et al., 2005; Ogawa and Miura, 2013). This capability to adapt to changing environments based on polyphenisms has placed aphids in a exceptional position to colonise dynamic niches (Nijhout, 2003). Among the polyphenisms displayed by aphids, some are widely distributed across aphid groups, such as dispersal (winged vs apterous) dimorphism (Braendle et al., 2006; Brisson, 2010) or the seasonal or reproductive polyphenism (Tagu et

al., 2005; Le Trionnaire et al., 2008; Simon et al., 2010; Ogawa and Miura, 2014). Other aphid polyphenisms include host plant specialised morphs or feeding polyphenism (Miyazaki, 1987a; Kim et al., 2011) and, in eusocial species, even defensive soldier morphs (Miyazaki, 1987a; Shibao et al., 2010; Hattori et al., 2013) among others.

Some aphid species alternate between two plant hosts, having therefore developed specific morphs for each host and for migrations between them (Moran, 1992). Thus, based on the number of plant hosts, aphids can be monoecious (or autoecious) if the whole cycle occurs in one plant species or closely related species (usually herbaceous) or heteroecious (or dioecious) if the life cycle takes place alternating between two (usually a woody and a herbaceous) hosts (Dixon, 1985; Moran, 1992). Some aphid species have acquired a secondary plant host (usually herbaceous) to better adapt to seasonal changes, probably due to the low nitrogen content in the phloem of the primary host (usually woody) during summer (Sorensen, 2009). In heteroecious species, the sexual morphs usually meet in the primary host, where the sexual eggs are laid (Miyazaki, 1987a). Furthermore, many species have acquired secondary monoecy on herbaceous hosts as a derived trait, by losing their primary host (Miyazaki, 1987a; Moran, 1992).

Such a wide repertoire of adaptations make aphids an exceptional model to study phenotypic plasticity (Nijhout, 2003; Hardie, 2009; Hartfelder and Emlen, 2012). Among the polyphenisms described, reproductive polyphenism is specially relevant and is the one we will be dealing with in the present thesis. Indeed, one of the adaptations that have allowed aphids to colonise the changing environment of temperate areas is the

development of a life cycle based on cyclical parthenogenesis, that lead to a characteristic reproductive or seasonal polyphenism (Moran, 1992). The decision to reproduce either by parthenogenesis or sexually has been found to depend on external factors. Photoperiod¹ is the main factor governing the mode of reproduction in aphids (Marcovitch, 1924; Lees, 1989), though temperature has also been shown to play some role (Lees, 1986). As already described, during the favourable seasons, successive asexual generations follow one another in which the viviparous parthenogenetic females give birth to genetically identical (clonal) offspring. At the end of the summer, the shortening of the photoperiod induces the production of the single annual sexual generation consisting of sexual oviparous females and males. The development of the sexual morphs eventually leads to the production of winter-resistant eggs capable of surviving the harsh conditions of winter. Thus, retaining sexual reproduction in aphids has a clear evolutionary selective advantage in regions with severe winters. In addition to the above mentioned basic cycle, referred to as holocycle, some aphid species or lineages within species are described as anholocyclic as they undergo an incomplete cycle in which the sexual phase has been lost. This renders a life cycle consisting of a succession of parthenogenetic females all year round. This type of cycle tends to evolve in regions with mild winters in which parthenogenetic females can survive the unfavourable but mild season or in dioecious species found in regions where the primary host is absent (Moran, 1992).

¹Photoperiod: the time of light in a light/dark cycle (Dunlap et al., 2004), although it is often used colloquially to denote the entire light:dark cycle as in an L:D = 12:12 photoperiod (Bradshaw and Holzapfel, 2010b).

Reproductive system of female aphids

The reproductive system of female aphids (Figure 1.7) basically consists of two ovaries each one containing a variable number of ovarioles, from four to nine in viviparous morphs and from one to six in oviparous morphs, depending on the species and morph (Michalik et al., 2013). The ovariole can be subdivided in four main regions (see Figure 1.7 B): a terminal filament, a *tropharium* or trophic chamber, a *vitellarium* and ovariole stalk or pedicel (Michalik et al., 2013). The apical part of each ovariole ends in a terminal filament that joins the terminal filaments from the rest of the ovarioles finally attaching to the dorsal diaphragm or the body wall (Blackman, 1987). The *tropharium* contains trophocytes (nurse cells) and previtellogenic oocytes both derived from the germinal line, that are surrounded by a monolayer of somatic cells. The *vitellarium* consists of a layer of follicle cells (somatic line). Each trophic chamber contains a cluster of 32 germ cells, of which those located posteriorly will become oocytes and the anteriorly remainder ones will differentiate into trophocytes (Miura et al., 2003; Tagu et al., 2005). All cells within the *tropharium*, including arrested oocytes and trophocytes, are connected to the central part of the *tropharium* known as trophic core (Michalik et al., 2013). Aphid ovarioles are of the typical hemipteran merostic thelotrophic type, in which the trophocytes (nurse cells) originate from the germ line and remain in the *tropharium* (Blackman, 1987; Lynch and Roth, 2011; Michalik et al., 2013). In this type of ovarioles, the nurse cells supplement developing eggs or parthenogenetic embryos in the *vitellarium* with mRNAs and cytoplasmic content through a trophic cord. The first stages of development of oocytes are similar in sexual and parthenogenetic development. Under short day conditions, the oocytes of the posterior region of the *tropharium* enter

Figure I.7. *Acyrthosiphon pisum* ovaries. **A)** Light microscope images of a parthenogenetic (left) and oviparous (right) female ovarioles. Taken from Davis (2012). **B)** Schematic representations of parthenogenetic (left) and oviparous (right) aphid ovarioles . AO, arrested oocyte; BL, blastoderm; E, embryo; F, follicular epithelium; NC, nutritive cord; OC, oocyte; ON, oocyte nucleus; P, pedicel; T, trophocyte; TC, trophic core; TF, terminal filament; TR, tropharium; VIT, vitellarium. Taken from Michalik et al. (2013).

meiosis and remain arrested at metaphase I. The development of sexual oocytes undergoes three stages occurring in the *vitellarium*: during previtellogenesis the arrested oocyte accumulates RNAs and organelles; vitellogenesis is characterised by the accumulation of yolk granules and lipid droplets; and during choriogenesis the egg envelopes are laid on the egg. At the end of oogenesis, the egg is fertilised by the sperm that the female has stored in the spermatheca. Embryogenesis begins after fecundation and takes place mostly after oviposition (Blackman, 1987; Miura et al., 2003; Michalik et al., 2013). After fecundation, the eggs turn dark green by the deposition of serosa. The fertilised egg undergoes embryonic diapause in which development slows considerably down taking approximately 100 days to be completed (Shingleton et al., 2003). On the other hand, during asexual reproduction that occurs under long days, the parthenogenetic embryogenesis begins within the ovarioles as soon as the germaria are formed. The arrested oocytes (2n) of asexual aphids begin development in the *vitellarium* up to the previtellogenesis phase, after which the oocyte enters a series of mitotic divisions and begins differentiation that will finally form an embryo (Blackman, 1987; Miura et al., 2003; Michalik et al., 2013). In this case, the egg envelope is not laid. Asexual embryogenesis is completed within 10 days, much shorter than the 100 days of sexual egg embryogenesis (Shingleton et al., 2003). In both types of embryo development –sexual and asexual– the endosymbionts are transferred from the mother (Miura et al., 2003; Wilkinson et al., 2003).

Sex determination

During the asexual phase of the life cycle, aphids reproduce parthenogenetically by thelytoky, in which parthenogenetic females

develop from unfertilised eggs (Simon et al., 2002; Normark, 2003). In this type of reproduction, the parthenogenetic females produce a diploid female embryo by means of an apomictic meiosis, in which only a single maturation division takes place producing a polar body and a female oocyte (both $2n$). Given that the typical recombination in the meiotic profase I does not occur, the oocyte generates a clonal copy of the mother (Hales et al., 2002). During the parthenogenetic phase of the life cycle, the oocyte commences development immediately after cleavage (see above) (Blackman, 1987; Le Trionnaire et al., 2008). Moreover, oocytes of asexual females are able to assemble new centrosomes by synthesizing microtubule asters *de novo*, which in the sexual phase are provided by the spermatozoa after fertilisation (Riparbelli et al., 2005; Davis, 2012). As previously explained, a switch from asexual to sexual reproduction occurs in autumn, and therefore it implies that the last generation of parthenogenetic females, the so called *sexuparae* (see Figure I.6), will bear inside their abdomen embryos of males and sexual females. Sex determination in aphids is of the XX/XO type, in which sexual females and parthenogenetic females have exactly the same chromosome set and are genetically identical (Blackman, 1987; Davis, 2012). On the other hand, males have a complete diploid set of autosomes but only one X chromosome, thus being hemizygous for the X chromosome (Davis, 2012). Although the arrhenotoky term is generally used for haploid male determination (e.g. honey bees), some authors classify the XO determination as a special kind of arrhenotoky (Blackman, 1987). Oocytes to become males undergo a special meiosis in which during metaphase the X chromosomes join in a C-shape and finally the X chromosome closest to the cell membrane is lost (Orlando, 1972; Blackman, 1987). This mechanism

ensures that all male embryos have only one X chromosome. The cycle is closed by the generation of a winter-resistant egg from which a diploid XX parthenogenetic female, known as *fundatrix*, always hatches (see Figure I.6). This is accomplished by a special male spermatogenesis involving the degeneration of secondary spermatocytes lacking X chromosomes (Blackman, 1985, 1987). Therefore, during the fertilisation of the female egg (n) by spermatozoon (n) that carry an X chromosome, the diploidy for the sex chromosomes is restored. The rate of males and oviparous female production is modulated by the length of photoperiod (MacKay, 1987). In *A. pisum*, longer photoperiods (e.g. 16L:8D) produce only viviparous parthenogenetic females. Intermediate photoperiods with shorter photophase induce the production of males, while, in order to obtain oviparous females, photoperiods with even shorter photophases are needed. A clinal variation in photoperiodic responses of pea aphid populations has been reported (MacKay et al., 1989), thus showing the adaptive character of this aphid trait.

A note on wing polyphenism

Since it is a rather conspicuous trait, we will briefly summarise what is known as wing polyphenism in aphids. Although the ability to fly has granted insects with notable advantages in important activities such as food search or colonisation of new habitats, the development and usage of wings is costly. For this reason, many insects have secondarily lost the wings along evolution, or even others, have done so facultatively by developing a wing polyphenism (Dixon, 1985). Aphids' asexual phase consists of a succession of parthenogenetic female generations which are either winged (see Figure I.8) or wingless depending on environmental factors

Figure I.8. A) Adult parthenogenetic winged morph of *Acyrthosiphon pisum*. **B)** a detail of winged aphid morphology. *Ocelli* are indicated with white arrowheads. Note the red dots in the abdomen that represent the eyes of the most developed embryos that can be seen through the cuticle.

(Sutherland, 1969; Dixon, 1985; Moran, 1992). On the other hand, oviparous sexual females and fundatrices are monomorphic apterous (Brisson, 2010), while males are winged or, as it is the case of *A. pisum*, they exhibit wing dimorphism which is determined by the locus *aphicarus (api)* in the X chromosome (Braendle et al., 2005). Male wing dimorphism is, therefore, a case of genetic polymorphism, not polyphenism. Winged aphids are adapted for flight, as can be observed by their characteristics: presence of functional wing musculature, increased sclerotisation in head and thorax, improved sensory system (more developed compound eye, ocelli, more rhinaria and larger antenna) and larger *siphunculi* and cauda (Braendle et al., 2006). Winged aphids are also characterised by longer time for nymphal development, lower fecundity and greater resistance to starvation (Hazell et al., 2005), among other characteristics.

Although there is some controversy about the contribution of different factors on the induction of development of winged *virginoparae*, it has been demonstrated that wing development can be induced by poor nutritional quality of the host plant in some species (Müller et al., 2001), tactile stimuli that often happens in crowded populations (Ishikawa and Miura, 2013), and also by alarm pheromones upon predatory pressure (Kunert et al., 2005). It is important to note that all this factors are tokens of unfavourable environments, therefore the production of winged morphs is relevant to disperse the clone to places with likely better conditions. Depending on the species, the factors promoting wing development in their offspring can be directly sensed by the nymphs, maternally transmitted to the developing embryos (Brisson, 2010; Walsh et al., 2010) or both (Ishikawa and Miura, 2013). In this respect, decapitation of aphids affected wing development in *Aphis craccivora* (Johnson and Birks, 1960)

and *Megoura viciae* (Lees, 1966). Thus, it seems that the signal determining developmental fate of embryos in these species would be maternally inherited (Braendle et al., 2006). As generally seen for other polyphenisms, the regulation at the molecular level of wing development was proposed to be controlled by the Juvenile Hormone (JH) because apterous morph development can be interpreted as a retention of juvenile features (i.e. absence of wings). Accordingly, elevated JH titres should correlate with wingless development (Braendle et al., 2005; Ishikawa et al., 2013). Nevertheless, studies on the role of JH in wing development assessed indirectly by application of JH extracts, JH analogues or involving the destruction of *corpus allatum* with precocenes are not conclusive on the role of JH on wing polyphenism (Brisson, 2010). In this context, JH III quantification in haemolymph of aphids producing winged or wingless progeny showed no significant differences (Schwartzberg et al., 2008), while quantification of JH in aphid larvae revealed lower titres in L3 aphids that were determined to become winged morphs (Ishikawa et al., 2013).

2. Biological Rhythms

The two main astronomical movements of the Earth, rotation around its axis and translation around the sun, originate two major oscillations in Earth's environment commonly known as days and years, respectively. The environmental changes associated to this oscillations are rhythmic and, therefore, predictable. Consequently, living organisms with the capability to organise their biological activities according to these predictable changes would certainly have an advantage. In fact, life has adapted to deal with these external, predictable changes in their environment by evolving endogenous biological rhythms to, accordingly, coordinate the temporal patterns of internal physiology and behaviour of most organisms with the external environment.

2.1. Circadian rhythms

Circadian rhythms consist of oscillations in physiological activities and/or behaviour of organisms that have a periodicity of approximately 24 h. Circadian rhythms are widely distributed, being found in cyanobacteria (Dong and Golden, 2008; Johnson and Egli, 2014), fungi (Harmer et al., 2001; Roenneberg et al., 2009; Baker et al., 2012), plants (Harmer, 2009; Putterill et al., 2009; Imaizumi, 2010) and animals (Gachon et al., 2004; Dibner et al., 2010; Wood and Loudon, 2014). Circadian rhythms are the outcome of a circadian clock, a mechanism conserved in a wide range of organisms that includes the interaction of several regulatory proteins in a network of negative and positive feedback loops (Doherty and Kay, 2010). The different components of the central circadian clock can be organised in

Figure I.9. Simplified scheme of the circadian clock that can be subdivided into three components. The input is responsible of sensing the external cue or *zeitgeber* conveying the information to the circadian clock core. Within the core resides an autonomous oscillator that is synchronised with the external environment via the input. The circadian clock core generates rhythmic oscillations that control rhythmic events in the rest of the organs and tissues through output signalling such as hormones and neuropeptides.

three categories: input elements, core elements of the clock itself and output elements (Figure I.9). The core of the clock is an autonomous oscillator that is synchronised with the environment by external cues (also known as *Zeitgebers*), mainly driven by light but also receiving input from other factors such as the external temperature, availability of food or gradients of chemical signals, among others (Dunlap et al., 2004; Kohsaka and Bass, 2006; Dibner et al., 2010; Ito et al., 2011). The circadian information processed by the clock is then relayed to the rest of the organism via hormones, neuropeptides and other means. Circadian clocks are defined by a series of characteristics: 1) are self-sustainable in free running conditions with a periodicity of approximately 24 h even in the absence of external cues, 2) the oscillation is compensated in a wide range of temperatures and 3) they can be entrained (i.e. synchronised with the external environment) by external stimuli, mainly light (Bell-Pedersen et al., 2005).

In animals, the circadian clock is highly conserved at the molecular level, being the best characterised circadian clocks those of *Drosophila* and mouse (Looby and Loudon, 2005). The circadian clock of *Drosophila* is the most exhaustively studied insect clock (Weber, 2009; Hardin, 2011; Özkaya and Rosato, 2012), and is generally used as a model in insects. The core of the *Drosophila* circadian clock is composed of six main transcription factors (Figure I.10): the PAS¹ domain factor PER encoded by gene *period* (*per*) that dimerises with the TIM factor encoded by gene *timeless* (*tim*), the two bHLH²-PAS proteins CLK and CYC respectively encoded by genes *Clock* (*Clk*) and *cycle* (*cyc*), and the two bZIP³ (basic Leu zipper) domain factors PDP1 and VRI respectively encoded by genes *PAR domain protein 1* (*Pdp1*) and *vri* (*vri*). Additionally, the blue light photoreceptor CRY1 encoded by the gene *cryptochrome1* (here named *Drosophila*-like *Cry* or *Cry1*; see below for further details) plays a role in synchronizing the clock with the environment. The molecular interactions between the transcription factors is fine tuned by a series of ancillary kinases and phosphatases such as casein kinase 2 (CK2), protein phosphatases 1 and 2a (PP1 and PP2a, respectively), double-time (DBT), shaggy (SGG) and the F-box proteins Jetlag (JET) and supernumerary limbs (SLMB), that regulate the phosphorylation levels and ubiquitination of the main elements of the clock and therefore, their degradation and cellular localisation (Weber, 2009). The core of the clock is established by two interlocked transcription/translation feedback loops. In the negative feedback loop, heterodimers of CLK:CYC are accumulated in the early day that activate the expression of *per* and *tim* by binding

1 PAS is a protein interaction domain named after the three proteins in which it was first discovered: Period (PER), aryl hydrocarbon receptor nuclear translocator protein (ARNT) and single-minded protein (SIM).

2 BHLH is a basic helix-loop-helix protein domain involved in sequence specific DNA binding.

3 BZIP is a basic-leucine zipper protein domain involved in sequence specific DNA binding.

upstream E-box elements (consensus sequence CACGTG) (Stanewsky, 2003). At early night, the levels of *per* and *tim* transcripts peak and, in the middle of the night, TIM:PER heterodimers are accumulated and enter the nucleus repressing CLK:CYC activation of their own transcription (Hardin, 2005). In the second feedback loop, CLK:CYC heterodimers promote transcription of *vri* which accumulates early in the night and immediately combine in VRI:VRI homodimers that inhibit the transcription of the genes *Clk* and *cry1* by binding to upstream V/P (VRI/PDP1) boxes (consensus sequence TTATGTAA) (Blau and Young, 1999; Cyran et al., 2003; Glossop et al., 2003). *Pdp1ε* isoform transcripts accumulate at the same time than *vri* transcripts, but PDP1 accumulates later in the late night, displacing VRI from V/P boxes and activating the expression of *cry1* and *Clk* (Cyran et al.,

Figure I.10. Schematic diagram of the two interlocked transcription feedback loops that constitute the genes of the *Drosophila* circadian clock. The negative feedback loop is constituted by the transcription repressors PER and TIM. The positive feedback loop is established by the transcriptional repressor and activator VRI and PDP1, respectively. The circadian clock proteins are represented by coloured shapes and circadian rhythmic transcription is indicated by wave symbols. Modified from The International Aphid Genomics Consortium (2010).

2003). The system is synchronised at the beginning of each photophase when light induces a conformational change in the photoreceptor CRY1, which relays photic information by inducing the phosphorylation of TIM by SGG (Martinek et al., 2001). Finally, phosphorylated TIM is ubiquitinated and subsequently tagged for degradation by the proteasome, releasing the E-boxes back for CLK:CYC-mediated transcription activation (Koh, 2006; Peschel et al., 2009). Recently, two more transcription factors have been discovered to be involved in the regulation of the first loop: the bHLH repressor clockwork orange (CWO) whose transcription is activated by CLK:CYC and binds to E-box elements (Kadener et al., 2007; Lim et al., 2007a), and the histone acetyl transferase Nejire (NEJ), whose role in the circadian regulation is not yet well understood (Hung et al., 2007; Lim et al., 2007b). Even though the circadian clock elements are particularly conserved among animals, there are some differences between the mammalian and the *Drosophila* circadian clocks at the functional level. As a consequence of genome duplications, the mammalian circadian clock includes various copies of the core genes: four *period* genes, two mammalian-type *cryptochromes* (which are not orthologous of the *Drosophila Cry1*), two paralogues of *Bmal* (homologues to *Clk*) and two paralogues of *Clk* (Looby and Loudon, 2005). Moreover, the so called mammalian *Timeless* (*mTim*) is not a true orthologue of *Drosophila Tim*, but instead a paralogue of the *Drosophila* gene *timeout*, whose role in the circadian clock is not clear (Benna et al., 2000).

In mammals, the synchronisation of the central circadian clock with the external photoperiod is carried out by the retinal non-visual photoreceptor *melanopsin* or *OPN4* (Wood and Loudon, 2014), instead of cryptochrome as described in *Drosophila* (see above). The light information from the retina is

relayed to the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN) of the hypothalamus, where the central circadian pacemaker resides (Looby and Loudon, 2005). In the central circadian clock of mammals, the mammalian-type *cryptochrome* (mCRY) acts as the main repressor of CLK:CYC in the negative feedback loop (Stanewsky, 2003), however mTIM (homologous to *Drosophila timeout*, a paralogue of *DmTim*) could be also be involved in the negative loop as partner of PER and mCRY (Looby and Loudon, 2005).

Although the circadian system of *Drosophila* has been the most well studied, the increasing availability of genomes from other insects has favoured the analysis of other insect circadian clocks. The most noteworthy difference between drosophilids and the rest of insects is the presence of a gene orthologous of mCRY, firstly discovered in the monarch butterfly *Danaus plexippus* (Zhu et al., 2005), that is absent in *Drosophila*, but later found in all other insects except drosophilids (Yuan et al., 2007). In the literature related to insects, this mammalian CRY is generally referred to as mCry or *Cry2*. In recent years, evidence from cultured insect cell assays (Yuan et al., 2007; Zhu et al., 2008) and targeted mutagenesis experiments on Lepidoptera (Merlin et al., 2013) revealed that insect CRY2 would not act as a circadian clock photoreceptor, but rather as a repressor partner of PER and TIM. This CRY-centered circadian clock would therefore be more similar to that of vertebrates than to the drosophilid type (Numata et al., 2015; Reppert et al., 2016). On the other hand, Hymenoptera (and probably Coleoptera) only have CRY2 present in the circadian gene repertoire, whose function either as CLK:CYC repressor, as light sensor or both is still not known (Yuan et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2013a). Thus, depending on the composition on cryptochrome genes, there are three types of circadian systems in insects (Figure I.11): the proposed ancestral type found in

Figure I.11. Insect circadian clock models proposed by Yuan et al. (2007). In insects, two type of cryptochromes exist, the *Drosophila*-like CRY or CRY1 and the vertebrate-like CRY or CRY2. Depending on the cryptochrome genes present in the genome insect circadian clocks can be classified into three main types: type 1, described in *Drosophila*, in which only CRY1 is present; type 2, described in Lepidoptera includes both CRY1 and CRY2; and type 3, found in Coleoptera and Hymenoptera, in which CRY1 is absent. CRY1 is involved in light-mediated synchronisation of the central circadian clock (type 1a and 2) and as a repressor partner of PER in peripheral clocks (type 1b), while CRY2 participates in the negative feedback loop inhibiting transcriptional activation mediated by CLK:CYC (type 2 and 3). Moreover, Hymenoptera lack a TIM homologue.

Lepidoptera would have both CRY1 and CRY2 in which the former is the photoreceptor and the latter would be the main repressor of CLK:CYC transcription activation; the drosophilid type, with only CRY1, in which PER along with TIM are the main repressors; and the derived in Hymenoptera and Coleoptera, in which CRY1 is absent and CRY2 is present (Yuan et al., 2007). Moreover, hymenopterans lack a *Drosophila*-like TIM whose role might have been taken by the mammalian TIM orthologue *timeout* or *tim2* (Rubin et al., 2006; Gu et al., 2014). In *Drosophila*, TIMEOUT is involved in

DNA metabolism and chromosome integrity, but also plays a role in the entrainment of the central circadian clock by optic lobe photic input (Benna et al., 2010). Probably, the absence of JET is a consequence of a previous loss of any of the other elements involved in the relay of photic information, namely CRY1 (lost in coleopterans and hymenopterans) and TIM (lost in hymenopterans) (Cortés, 2010).

In insects, the architecture of the circadian clock cells varies between species. However, it appears that neurons important for circadian rhythms are generally found in a group of specialised neurons located in the region between the *protocerebrum* and the optic lobes, with the exception of crickets (Numata et al., 2015). The central clock produces endogenous signals that entrain peripheral clocks present in some tissues or directly provide input to other cells (Bloch et al., 2013). In *Drosophila*, and probably in other insects, pigment dispersing factor (PDF), a highly conserved neuropeptide, is the main output element of the central pacemaker that regulates circadian behaviour (Shafer and Yao, 2014). PDF is expressed in a circadian fashion in a subset of clock cells, known as the small ventral lateral neurons (s-LN_vs), in the *Drosophila* brain that also coexpress circadian clock proteins (Helfrich-Förster, 2004). PDF is required for a normal circadian rhythmic behaviour in several insects (Saunders, 2002; Lee et al., 2009; Hassaneen et al., 2011; Helfrich-Förster et al., 2011), while it seems to be not necessary in some others (Ikeno et al., 2014). In addition, the PDF receptor (PdfR) is also expressed in some of the clock neurons of *Drosophila*, thus providing the key to a feedback of PDF signalling that coordinates the clock neuron network (Shafer and Yao, 2014). The JH has also been proposed as a circadian output downstream of the central pacemaker (Bloch et al., 2013). In this respect, a circadian rhythm of JH

content was described in the haemolymph of crickets (Zera, 2016) and honey bee foragers (Elekovich et al., 2001), as well as JH influence on insect behaviour (Bloch et al., 2013). In the hemipteran *Rhodnius prolixus*, the circadian rhythm in ecdysteroid haemolymph levels is regulated by the autonomous clock in prothoracic glands (PG). The PG clock, in turn, is coupled to the central pacemaker in the brain by means of circadian prothoracicotropic hormone (PTTH) signalling (Vafopoulou et al., 2012; Vafopoulou and Steel, 2014). The biogenic amine melatonin (N-acetyl-5-methoxytryptamine) is an important internal *zeitgeber* or output of the circadian clock in mammals (Dunlap et al., 2004; Wood and Loudon, 2014). The mammalian central pacemaker in the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN) of the hypothalamus controls melatonin biosynthesis in the pineal gland via polysynaptic pathways that produce an increase of circulating melatonin during the night (Iuvone et al., 2005; Challet, 2007; Borjigin et al., 2012). The penultimate and rate-limiting enzyme in the melatonin biosynthesis pathway is the vertebrate-like arylalkylamine N-acetyltransferase (v-AANAT), which is known as the “timezyme” given its role in melatonin biosynthesis (Klein, 2007). Among other roles (Hardeland, 2008), mammalian melatonin is important in mediating the signalling of seasonal rhythms (Dardente et al., 2010; Dardente, 2012; Wood and Loudon, 2014). Melatonin has also been found in many insect species, generally at higher levels during the night (Vivien-Roels and Pévet, 1993). Even though the function of insect melatonin is not as well understood as in vertebrates, in a few cases it has been found to participate in establishing circadian rhythms (Richter et al., 1999, 2000; Richter, 2001; Yamano et al., 2001).

2.2. Photoperiodism

Earth's translation movement around the sun originates changes in the environment at any given time that oscillate rhythmically on a year basis. In temperate regions, the major changes associated with this Earth movement give rise to the seasons. Annual endogenous rhythms have arisen in many organisms in order to adjust the timing of important biological events (e.g. breeding, migration or hibernation) with these yearly-based environmental changes to maximise their fitness. Annual biological rhythms can be classified into two classes. Type II circannual rhythms (also known as true circannual rhythms) are self-sustained under constant conditions with free-running periods of *ca.* 12 months, and are usually entrained by photoperiod. Type I circannual rhythms combine endogenous timekeeping elements with obligatory exogenous components, therefore, the cycling is lost in the absence of external cues (Dunlap et al., 2004). Most of the circannual rhythms displayed by living organisms that have been studied fall into type I, and these organisms are commonly described as photoperiodic or seasonal. Photoperiodism has been defined as "the use of changes in the day length on an annual basis to regulate seasonal behavioural or physiological processes" (Dunlap et al., 2004). A wide range of organisms, mainly higher plants and animals living in a terrestrial environment, use this "noise-free" information to control various seasonally appropriate switches in metabolism, most of which have a clear functional significance or survival value. Photoperiodism was first discovered in plants (Garner and Allard, 1920), and shortly followed by the discovery of photoperiodism in animals, particularly in the vetch aphid *Megoura viciae* (Marcovitch, 1923, 1924). Indeed, insects, being

poikilotherms, make their development prone to be directly influenced by the impact of the low temperatures of winter or, in phytophagous insects, indirectly by the effects of winter on their plant hosts (Saunders, 2002). In plants and mammals, the pathways linking a circadian clock with the photoperiodic response cascade have been discovered (Dardente et al., 2010; Imaizumi, 2010; Hut, 2011). However, it remains to be elucidated if these pathways connecting the circadian clockwork with photoperiodism do exist in insects (Saunders, 2002, 2011; Dunlap et al., 2004; Bradshaw and Holzapfel, 2010b; Tomioka and Matsumoto, 2010). In general, insects have developed more or less complex life cycles in which they synchronise the appropriate phase of their life cycles with the season they are specialised for. Different insects overcome the adverse season following different strategies such as a programmed migration (Reppert et al., 2016), diapause (Saunders et al., 2004; Denlinger and Armbruster, 2014; Goto, 2016; Omura et al., 2016) or developing specific morphs (Shingleton et al., 2003; Tagu et al., 2005; Hardie, 2009; Nijhout, 2009; Simon et al., 2010). Some organisms, including insects, can also develop a stage of quiescence that also involves a metabolic arrest but, unlike diapause, quiescence is rather a direct response to the adverse environmental component and it is initiated and terminated by the unfavourable condition itself (Denlinger et al., 2012). Diapause was originally understood as a period of arrest in which the organism underwent a cessation of development to overcome the unfavourable season. However, this vision has been substituted and nowadays it is seen as an alternative developmental program (Denlinger and Armbruster, 2014; Dolezel, 2014).

Photoperiod is the most predictable and reliable cue to track the timing of the seasons. Consequently, photoperiodic time measurement is

ubiquitously found among different taxa for timing their seasonal rhythms (Nelson et al., 2009). Only in regions close to the equator the photoperiodic variation is exiguous and has been substituted by other tokens such as temperature or humidity (Nelson et al., 2009).

By analogy with the circadian pacemaker that governs circadian rhythms described in the previous section, it has been hypothesised that the photoperiodic response is controlled by a photoperiodic clock (also referred to as photoperiodic calendar) whose structure could be schematised similarly (Figure I.12). This photoperiodic calendar would consist of a minimum set of elements including a photoperiodic photoreceptor that would allow a photoperiodic clock to differentiate between different photoperiods (i.e. short from long nights), a counter that would keep track of the number of consecutive photoperiods of a particular length, and output elements that would, over a certain threshold, produce a seasonal response through neuroendocrine effectors (Košťál, 2011; Saunders, 2013).

In mammals, ganglion cells in the retina expressing melanopsin (OPN4) are the photoperiodic photoreceptors that provide electrical input to the ventrolateral part of the SCN (suprachiasmatic nucleus), where the expression of vasoactive intestinal peptide (VIP), a known output element of the mammalian circadian clock takes place (Dibner et al., 2010; Lucas, 2013). The photoperiodic information is processed in the central pacemaker from which efferents provide direct entrainment to peripheral clocks in other tissues and organs via neural and humoral cues (Dibner et al., 2010). A crucial element in mammalian photoperiodism is the circadian synthesis of melatonin in the pineal gland. Melatonin synthesis is under

Figure I.12. Simplified scheme of the proposed photoperiodic calendar (Košťál, 2011). The input is responsible of sensing the external cue, generally the photoperiod, that conveys the information to the core machinery. Within the core resides a photoperiodic clock and a counter. The clock is capable of discriminating long from short days and, depending on the model assumed, it could be a circadian oscillator or an hourglass mechanism (see section **Photoperiodic clock**). The counter would keep track of the number of long or short day events that have been experienced. The decision to activate a seasonal response is relayed to the rest of the organism by hormonal and neuroendocrine effectors that constitute the coordinated output signalling.

control of the SCN by means of circadian rhythmic regulation of expression of arylalkylamine N-acetyl transferase (AANAT), the rate limiting enzyme of melatonin biosynthesis (Cazaméa-Catalan et al., 2014; Wood and Loudon, 2014). Melatonin receptors in the *pars tuberalis* (PT) of the pituitary gland receive the melatonin signal, that inhibits the production and release of thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) (Dardente et al., 2014). TSH provides signalling to hypothalamic ependymian cells (tanycytes) where it activates the expression of *deiodinase 2* (DIO2), the enzyme that converts thyroid prohormone (T_4) into the active hormone (T_3) (Ikegami and Yoshimura, 2012). The local increase of T_3 in the hypothalamus induces the production of gonadotropic release hormone (GNRH) that eventually activates gonadal development. Thus, melatonin is used in vertebrates as a token of the duration of the night length that controls the seasonal rhythms of mammals via regulation of the thyroid hormone (TH) metabolism in the pituitary gland (Dardente et al., 2010; Hazlerigg, 2012; Wood and Loudon,

2014). The photoperiodic mechanism of birds is conserved with respect to mammals, except that the three photoperiodic photoreceptors Opn4 (melanopsin), Opn5 (neuropsin) and VAOpn (vertebrate ancient opsin) are located in the brain instead of the retina (Kang and Kuenzel, 2015; Ikegami and Yoshimura, 2016).

In the next paragraphs I will summarise available information on these elements in the putative insect photoperiodic system (Saunders et al., 2004; Košťál, 2011; Saunders, 2013). Since aphids are paradigmatic photoperiodic insects (Marcovitch, 1924; Hardie and Vaz Nunes, 2001), a high proportion of evidence come from experiments on aphids. As previously described, aphids have a strong seasonal response. This response is characterised by the switch from asexual parthenogenetic reproduction, typical of spring and summer, to the production of sexual morphs that, eventually, will produce a winter resistant egg in which the embryonic diapause takes place (see section I.1.3).

Photoperiodic photoreceptors

By using different methodologies such as ablation, covering, local illumination and tissue transplant, the photoperiodic photoreceptors of insects have been localised at the tissue level in a few species. Depending on the species, the photoperiodic receptors were found in the compound eyes, in the brain, or in both tissues (Goto et al., 2009; Saunders, 2012). However, the tissue distribution of photoperiodic receptors does not seem to correlate with phylogeny (Goto et al., 2009). Classical localised illumination experiments with the aphid *Megoura viciae* (Lees, 1964) revealed that the photoperiodic photoreceptors were located on the

dorsal anterior region of the head capsule (Figure I.13 A). It was demonstrated that in aphids reared under short day conditions, therefore programmed to give birth to sexual morphs, a supplement of 2 h of light directed to the dorsal head region induced a reversion to *virginoparae* production disrupting the photoperiodic response. The absence of any evident morphological structure in the cuticle that could act as a receptor led to the suggestion that the photoperiodic receptors would be located in the *protocerebrum* (Lees, 1964; Hardie and Vaz Nunes, 2001). Furthermore, localised illumination in the abdomen demonstrated a direct photoperiodic sensibility in the most developed embryos through the cuticle of the progenitors (Lees, 1964). Additionally, ablation experiments showed that the optic lobes were not necessary for the photoperiodic response (Lees, 1964), while the anterior region of the protocerebrum, including *pars intercerebralis* (PL) and *pars lateralis* (PL) (see Figure I.5 A), were essential for the response (see section **Photoperiodic effectors** below) (Steel and Lees, 1977; Steel, 1978). Saunders (2012) reviewed several experiments owing to study light sensitivity to different wavelengths in different insects species. Although the maximum photoperiodic sensitivity is usually found in the blue or blue-green region of the spectrum (400-550 nm), in some species it extends into the UV and the red spectra. The diversity and wide range of light sensitivity suggests that different light receptors are most probably involved in the perception of photoperiod. Lees (1973) tested the effect of complex night interruption photoperiods in the seasonal response of *M. viciae*. The experiment identified two time points in the scotophase¹ at which light interruption produced a long day effect (i.e. a reversal of the seasonal response). The first point, named A, occurred early in the night

¹The term scotophase is used in photoperiodism to refer to the segment of the day that is in darkness.

Figure 1.13. Schematic drawings showing the localisation of the putative photoperiodic photoreceptors in *Megoura viciae*. **A)** Dorsal view of the aphid head showing the localisation of light sensitive regions relevant for the photoperiodic response. Plus symbols show regions in which a 2 h supplement of light in a short day photoperiod rearing context reverted the photoperiodic response, negative symbols show regions in which supplement light did not affect the photoperiodic response. Adapted from (Steel, 1978). **B)** Near sagittal section of the aphid brain showing the location of the opsin immunoreactive region (opsin-ir) in relation to neurosecretory cells (NSC) groups I and II. The essential *pars intercerebralis* region for the photoperiodic response is shown in blue. NCC I, *nervi corpori cardiaci* I; NCC II, *nervi corpori cardiaci* II; PC, *protocerebrum*; CB, *central body*; DC, *deutocerebrum*; TC, *tritocerebrum*. Adapted from Gao et al. (1999).

and its long day effect could be reversed by following scotophases longer than a critical night length (CNL; 9.5 h). Point B occurred late in the night (6-9 h after dusk) and the corresponding long day effect could not be reversed with a following scotophase longer than CNL. The spectrum sensitivities of points A and B were further investigated in the vetch aphid *M. viciae*. Blue light pulses of 1 h early in the scotophase reversed the induction of the seasonal response, while interruptions in the late night showed also a reversion in the blue but also extending into red and yellow wavelengths (Lees, 1981). Differential spectrum sensitivities of points A and B, as well as a wider range of wavelengths found in point B suggest that different photoreceptors may be participating in the seasonal response of aphids. In an effort to identify the nature of the photoperiodic photoreceptors (Gao et al., 1999), several opsin and other visual related protein antibodies were used to find opsin immunoreactivity (opsin-ir) in the anterior frontal protocerebrum neuropil, in a region located antero-ventrally to the NSC group I (see Figure I.13 B). Microcauterisation of NSC group I had no effect on the opsin-ir and thus, were discarded as the neurons originating opsin-ir axons. The authors do not clearly describe if the lesions affected a region distal to the NSC group I known as *pars lateralis*, that was also found to disrupt the seasonal response upon microcauterisation (see section **Photoperiodic clock** below). Thus, the neurons from which these axonal projections with opsin-ir originate were not finally found. Furthermore, two opsin genes were later described in *M. viciae* (Gao et al., 2000). Although good candidates to be photoperiodic receptors, *in situ* hybridisation experiments did not localise them in the *protocerebrum* but in the *retinula* cells within the *ommatidia*, discarding them as the main photoperiodic photoreceptors. A search for opsin genes

in the pea aphid genome carried out in our group (Collantes-Alegre et al., in preparation) revealed the presence of seven opsin genes, thus providing new opsin candidates to play a role in photoreception in the context of photoperiodism. Cryptochromes, flavin-based photoreceptors that are involved in circadian and photoperiodic light sensing in mammals, are also candidates to play a role as photoperiodic photoreceptor in insects. Cryptochromes that belong to the *Drosophila*-type cryptochrome (dCRY or CRY1), are blue-light photoreceptors that have been found to participate in the synchronisation of the circadian clock by light in different types of clocks (see section I.2.1) such as the *Drosophila*-type clock, and also in the ancestral type clock found in mosquitoes and *Lepidoptera* (Yuan et al., 2007; Benito et al., 2008; Zhu et al., 2008). In *Drosophila*, CRY1 is known to reset the circadian clock by relaying light information that eventually assists degradation of TIM (Lee et al., 1996). In other insects in which CRY1 is present, the clock resetting role seems to be conserved (Zhu et al., 2008). On the other hand, RNAi experiments revealed that *Cry2* (also known as mammalian-type CRY or *mCry*) expression is necessary for a normal seasonal response in the hemipteran *Riptortus pedestris* (Ikeno et al., 2011c) and in *Culex pipiens* (Meuti et al., 2015). As previously mentioned, the fact that blue light has maximum effect on the aphid seasonal response and that aphids possess a dCRY orthologous gene, places aphid CRY1 as a good candidate to be the putative photoperiodic receptor, although no information about the circadian expression pattern nor localisation in aphids has been yet published.

Photoperiodic clock

Similar to what is known in vertebrates, a role for the circadian clock in insect seasonal response or photoperiodism has been proposed by several groups (Denlinger and Armbruster, 2016; Hand et al., 2016; Omura et al., 2016; Reppert et al., 2016). However, the implication of the circadian clockwork in the photoperiodic response is not yet fully understood and some authors strongly put this proposal into question (Bradshaw and Holzapfel, 2007, 2010b, Emerson et al., 2009a, 2009b). Different models have been proposed that explain the role of the circadian clock in photoperiodism. Bünning (1960) first introduced the idea of a link between circadian rhythms and seasonal response, that later developed into the "Circadian Oscillator Model". Under this model, the endogenous daily circadian cycle is divided in two 12 h phases, the photophil and the scotophil phases (also known as subjective day and night, respectively). Under short days (photophase < 12 h), the light only stimulates the photophil part of the cycle, while in long days (photophase > 12 h) the light extends into the scotophil phase. Thus, in this model, the light has two roles: entrainment of the endogenous circadian cycle, and stimulation, or not, of the scotophil phase. Later, this model was extended when Pittendrigh (1964) updated Bünning's model and proposed the External Coincidence Model (Figure I.14 A). Pittendrigh's model differs from Bünning's model in that the photoinducible segment occurs at the end of the subjective night instead of encompassing the whole scotophil phase. Thus, long days would be determined by the illumination of the photosensitive segment (designated as ϕ^i) at the end of the scotophase while in short days ϕ^i would not be stimulated. Pittendrigh postulated a further circadian based mechanism called Internal Coincidence or Dual

Figure I.14. Schematic drawings of the classic photoperiodic models proposed to explain LD and SD responses. **A)** in the external coincidence model light has two roles. It synchronises the photoinducible phase (ϕ_i , shown in red) with external photoperiod that in long days is illuminated while in short days is in darkness. **B)** in the internal coincidence model the phase relationship between two oscillators determines length of photoperiod. **C)** in the hourglass model the length of the night is measured by the accumulation of factor. When the nights are longer than the critical night length (CNL, shown in blue), the factor levels reach a certain threshold that triggers the photoperiodic response.

Oscillator Model (Pittendrigh and Daan, 1976; Daan and Berde, 1978) in which the measurement of the photoperiod relies on the phase relationship between two circadian oscillators, a dusk- and a dawn-entrained oscillators, both entrained by light, but not involving any photosensitive phase (see Figure I.14 B). The participation of the circadian

clock in the photoperiodic response can be tested by a series of experiments using complex photoperiods such as Nanda-Hamner and Bünsow protocols. The Nanda-Hamner protocol consists of a fixed short day photophase accompanied of scotophases ranging from 4 to 72 h (Nanda and Hamner, 1958). In the Bünsow protocol, a variation of the night interruption technique, the organisms are exposed to photoperiods of 12 h photophases coupled with long scotophases of different lengths (12, 36 or 60 h) that are systematically interrupted with a light pulse (Bünsow, 1960). Organisms with a seasonal response based on a circadian oscillator display typical peaks of seasonal response incidence with a 24 h periodicity in both protocols. The vetch aphid *M. viciae* failed to show the typical peaks and troughs of *oviparae* production when tested with the Nanda-Hamner protocol (Hardie and Vaz Nunes, 2001; Saunders, 2002, 2009). These results prompted the authors to suggest a non-circadian based model for the seasonal response (Lees, 1973) known as the Hourglass Model (see Figure I.14 C). In this model, the measurement of the photoperiod would depend on a partially temperature-compensated biochemical process that would generate an accumulation of an active product during the scotophase, which after exceeding a certain threshold would induce the photoperiodic response. The process of accumulation of the unknown product described above would be reset by light at dawn. Nevertheless, night interruption experiments in the vetch aphid *Megoura viciae* reared under short day (sex inducing) conditions showed that early and late night light pulses abolished the photoperiodic response producing a long day effect (i.e. promoting parthenogenesis) (Lees, 1973). When the light pulse took place before a critical night length (CNL) of 9.5 hours, the seasonal response was abolished and aphids reproduced by parthenogenesis, while shifting the

light pulse after the CNL had no effect and the aphids reproduced sexually. Given that the photoperiodic response curves did not reveal a clear involvement of a circadian element in the aphid seasonal response, the issue remained at debate. The question was solved with further experiments (Vaz Nunes and Hardie, 1993) in which they compared *virginoparae*-inductive percentages of scotophases of 12, 36, 60 and 84 h (i.e. 12 h of light + $n \times 12$ h of darkness; $n = 0, 1, 2$ and 3 , respectively) to canonical long nights (LN, 12L:12D). If the clock was based in an hourglass mechanism, the extremely long nights would be measured as a single canonical LN, while in a circadian-based mechanism it would correlate with increasing amounts of LN. This study clearly showed that in aphids, the measurement of night length was repetitive, probably involving a circadian oscillator, thus questioning the hourglass model proposed previously by Lees (1973). The conflicting views on aphid night length measurement was settled by the proposal of the instantly damping oscillator (Vaz Nunes and Hardie, 1987, 1993; Hardie and Vaz Nunes, 2001) an adaptation of the External Coincidence model in which long dark periods dampen the circadian oscillator (Figure I.15). This would produce a decrease in the number of diapause-promoting cycles accumulated finally reducing the incidence of the seasonal response in the population (Saunders, 2010). Moreover, in recent years, evidence of circadian genes involved in the seasonal response in different insects have been accumulating. RNAi experiments on circadian genes have shown to have an effect on both circadian rhythms and seasonal responses in the dipteran *Chymomyza costata* (Pavelka et al., 2003), the orthopteran *Modicogryllus siamensis* (Sakamoto et al., 2009), the hemipteran *Riptortus pedestris* (Ikeno et al., 2010; Ikeno et al., 2011; Ikeno, Numata, & Goto, 2011a, 2011b; Omura et

Figure I.15. The dampened oscillator model. Under constant darkness, the amplitude of the circadian oscillator falls below a threshold (red dashed line) required to elicit a photoperiodic response. The extremely long nights of Nanda-Hamner and Bünsow protocols are enough to produce a dampening in the circadian oscillator that would render its amplitude under the critical threshold (see text for details).

al., 2016), the lepidopteran *Antheraea pernyi* (Mohamed et al., 2014) and the dipteran *Culex pipiens* (Meuti et al., 2015). In addition, mutant alleles of circadian clock genes in *Drosophila* have been shown to correlate with differential seasonal responses (Sandrelli et al., 2007; Pegoraro et al., 2014). However, currently there is no consensus on the involvement of the circadian system not only in the aphid seasonal response, but in insect photoperiodism in general (Bradshaw and Holzapfel, 2007; Goto, 2013; Meuti and Denlinger, 2013; Dolezel, 2014; Numata et al., 2015).

The location and number of circadian clock neurons differs greatly among insect species (Numata et al., 2015), probably as a consequence of multiple evolutionary origins of diapause in insects (Saunders, 2012). In drosophilids, it seems that the distribution of clock neurons is found in two regions of the brain. The *pars lateralis* contains dorsal clock neurons, and the lateral clock neurons are in a region of the protocerebrum close to the optic lobes (Sandrelli et al., 2008; Shiga and Numata, 2009). On the other hand, crickets

also have clock neurons in the optic lobe (Tomioka, 2014) and cockroaches have them both in the optic lobe and the dorsal *protocerebrum* (Bembenek et al., 2005; Tomioka and Matsumoto, 2010). In Lepidoptera, neurons expressing circadian clock proteins were found in the *pars lateralis* and *pars intercerebralis* of the dorsal protocerebrum (Sauman and Reppert, 1996a; Sauman et al., 2005). The brain of the hemipteran *Rhodnius prolixus* also contains two groups of neurons expressing circadian clock genes: the dorsal neurons in the posterior *protocerebrum* and the lateral neurons in the accessory medulla, the latter group being the main circadian pacemaker (Vafopoulou et al., 2010; Vafopoulou and Steel, 2012). In another hemipteran, *Riptortus pedestris*, a group of neurons in the accessory medulla express the circadian effector PDF (Ikeno et al., 2014), even though the localisation of circadian clock transcripts or clock proteins are still unknown in this species.

Photoperiodic counter

The concepts of photoperiodic counter and photoperiodic clock were proposed within the field of insect and mite photoperiodism (Saunders, 1981). The hypothetical photoperiodic counter would keep track of the number of specific photoperiods that have been perceived by the photoperiodic clock or calendar. The counter is specially associated to the hourglass model discussed above. Short day (long night) conditions would stimulate the accumulation of a hypothetical factor synthesised during the scotophase, that over a certain threshold, would activate the photoperiodic response via endocrine factors. If the threshold is not reached, then a long day response is triggered. The majority of studies on the characterisation of the putative insect photoperiodic counter were done using the vetch aphid

Megoura viciae. As mentioned at the beginning of this section, aphids are typical photoperiodic organisms that respond to short photoperiods of winter by inducing the formation of sexual morphs in the progeny. Experiments in which aphids were reared under different photoperiods revealed that the Required Day Number (RDN¹) of long nights (LN, equivalent to short days) accumulated independently of the accompanying photophase (Hardie, 1990), although it was later shown to loose inductive strength with photophases longer than 18 h (Vaz Nunes and Hardie, 1993). Contrarily, short nights (SN, equivalent to long days) did not correlate with the percentage of *virginoparae* producers. The experiments in *M. viciae* also showed that SN accumulated in a temperature dependent manner, while LN accumulation was more stable with respect to temperature (Hardie, 1990). The different characteristics in accumulation of SN and LN prompted the idea that they were measured by different mechanisms. This observation together with the results that suggested a possible circadian based photoperiodic clock (Vaz Nunes and Hardie, 1993) prompted the proposal of the “Dual Circadian Oscillator” model (Vaz Nunes, 1998), in which SN and LN would be measured by two separated circadian oscillators having different properties of dampening and temperature sensitivity (Hardie and Vaz Nunes, 2001; Hardie, 2009). Recently, a model of a photoperiodic counter has been proposed for the lepidopteran *Antheraea pernyi* in which the circadian clock controls the expression of the insect-type arylalkylamil N-acetyl transferase (i-AANAT) and DOPA decarboxylase (DDC), the respective limiting enzymes in melatonin and DOPA synthesis (Wang et al., 2015). *A. pernyi* shows a seasonal response in which pupal emergence is induced by exposure to long days. In this model, melatonin

¹The number of days needed to elicit a 50% of the seasonal response.

and DOPA would mutually inhibit their synthesis and, under long days, melatonin would reach a certain threshold over which the pupae would begin emergence.

Photoperiodic effectors

Insect photoperiodic response includes a variety of different phenomena that include seasonal migration such as that described in *Danaus plexippus* (Reppert et al., 2016), adult reproductive diapause (Tauber et al., 2007; Košťál et al., 2008), embryonic diapause (Emerson et al., 2009a; Denlinger et al., 2012), or seasonal activity rhythms (Tomioka, 2014) among others. Depending on the stage at which the diapause occurs, different effectors have been described. Embryonic diapause is generally regulated by ecdysteroid levels that, depending on the species, it is associated with an increase or a decrease of ecdysteroids (Denlinger et al., 2012). A special case has been described in *Bombyx mori*, in which embryonic diapause is of strict maternal control involving the synthesis of the FXPRL-amide diapause hormone (DH) (Denlinger et al., 2012). Under diapausing conditions, DH synthesis is induced by DOPA in two neurons of the suboesophageal ganglion and released into the haemolymph via *corpus cardiacum*. The ovaries receive the signal through DH receptors that activate the diapause programme in developing eggs (Denlinger et al., 2012). Larval and pupal diapause are associated with low prothoracicotrophic hormone (PTTH) synthesis or release, probably inhibited by DOPA, that prevents ecdysteroid synthesis in the prothoracic glands (PG). In other cases, refractoriness of PG to PTTH signalling has been associated to diapause (Denlinger et al., 2012). PTTH was the first insect hormone to be discovered (Kopeck, 1922). PTTH is an insect neuropeptide synthesised in the brain and released from the

neurohemal organs *corpus cardiacum* (CC) or *corpora allata* (CA) that induces ecdysone (the moulting hormone) secretion from the prothoracic glands (PG). Extensive studies in *Bombyx mori* revealed that PTTH is synthesised as a prohormone that is subsequently cleaved to produce an active shorter peptide (Kawakami et al., 1990). The mature PTTH contains seven conserved cysteines (Cys) that form intramolecular and intermolecular disulphide bonds to form homodimers (Smith and Rybczynski, 2012). In *Rhodnius prolixus* (Hemiptera) PTTH release is under control of the central circadian clock localised in the lateral neurons, a group of cells between the protocerebrum and the optic lobe (Vafopoulou and Steel, 1996). The lateral neurons are known to regulate ecdysteroidogenesis in conjunction with the insulin-like peptide bombyxin, also controlled by the central circadian clock (Vafopoulou and Steel, 2014). In the lepidopteran *Antheraea pernyi*, the central circadian clock regulates AANAT expression, the limiting enzyme in melatonin synthesis (Hardeland and Poeggeler, 2003; Hardeland, 2010). The rhythmic levels of melatonin in clock cells exert control over the adjacent PTTH neurons, triggering a circadian release of PTTH and, consequently, a circadian rhythm in ecdysteroids (Mohamed et al., 2014). Moreover, the exposure of *A. pernyi* to LD cycles upregulated the transcription of i-AANAT while downregulated that of DOPA decarboxylase (DDC), the limiting enzymes of melatonin and DOPA synthesis, respectively. Thus, long days promoted an increase of melatonin and a decrease of DOPA which are known to promote and delay adult emergence, respectively (Wang et al., 2015). Furthermore, insect diapause is generally related to low haemolymph levels of PTTH, that generate low ecdysteroid synthesis and release from the PG (Smith and Rybczynski, 2012).

Another candidate hormone to play a role in the seasonal response is the Juvenile Hormone (JH), which is produced and released in the *corpus allatum* (CA). Insect reproductive diapause seems to be mainly correlated with low JH titres (Denlinger et al., 2012). In aphids, JH was proposed to have an effect on wing dimorphism, although recent results question this view (Schwartzberg et al., 2008; Ishikawa et al., 2013; Ogawa and Miura, 2014). JH has also been implicated in the regulation of aphid reproductive polyphenisms (Hardie, 1987c; Ishikawa et al., 2012; Ogawa and Miura, 2014). Early experiments using topically applied JH and analogues revealed that aphid embryos that should develop as *oviparae* under short day conditions reverted to parthenogenetic development (Hardie, 1981, 1987a; Corbitt and Hardie, 1985). Nevertheless, there was no correlation between the JH levels and the CA volumes (Hardie, 1987d). Moreover, the destruction of the CA by kinoprene treatment induced production of males (Hales and Mittler, 1983, 1988). Although topical application of different JH homologues (JH-I, -II and -III) had effects on the progeny, only JH III has been found in aphids (Corbitt and Hardie, 1985). As proposed by Tagu et al. (2005), JH could be playing a role in the regulation of the seasonal response, although the detailed mechanism remains unknown (Le Trionnaire et al., 2008). In this context, levels of JH III were measured, revealing that aphids reared under SD conditions (*oviparae* producing) had lower JH III titres than aphids reared under LD (*viviparae* producing) (Ishikawa et al., 2012). Furthermore, analysis of expression of genes involved in JH metabolism in the aphid *Acyrtosiphon pisum* showed that JH esterases (JHEs) were overexpressed under short day conditions. Thus, the low levels of JH III found in short days seemed to be the consequence of an increased degradation rather than a decrease of its synthesis (Ishikawa et

al., 2012). The regulation of JH synthesis by allatostatins and allatotropins (allatoregulatory factors that respectively suppress and promote the synthesis of JH in the CA) has also been studied. The involvement of allatostatins in the regulation of the wing polyphenism of *Megoura viciae* revealed allatostatin-like immunoreactivity in the central nervous system, the CA and, specially, in the CC (Tilley et al., 2000). However, no correlation with morph production was found in the expression of transcripts of allatotropin and allatostatin receptors (Ishikawa et al., 2012).

In vertebrates, the ubiquitous hormone melatonin, generally considered as the daily and annual time-keeping hormone, is synthesised in the pineal gland and exhibits a daily rhythm driven by the circadian clock, with plasma levels high at night (thus the name hormone of darkness) and low during the day (Lincoln, 2006). The transmission of the photoperiodic information is encoded in the duration of the melatonin signal (Lincoln, 2006; Dardente et al., 2010), being longer as nights get longer in autumn and shorter as spring advances, therefore activating the molecular pathways that lead alternatively to the winter or summer responses (e.g. reproduction, migration, hibernation, etc.). In vertebrates, arylalkylamine N-acetyltransferase (AANAT) is the penultimate and rate-limiting enzyme in the melatonin biosynthetic pathway (Klein, 2007). Vertebrate AANATs belong to a wide family of proteins (the Gcn5- related N-acetyltransferases or GNAT family) that catalyse the transacetylation of acetyl coenzyme A to different substrates (Vetting et al., 2005). In particular, for melatonin synthesis, AANAT specifically acetylates serotonin to yield N-acetyl serotonin, which is the immediate precursor of melatonin (Hardeland, 2010). The activity of this enzyme increases 10- to 100-fold at night, leading to the observed rhythmicity in melatonin levels. Owing to its unique role in

vertebrate time keeping, AANAT has been regarded as the “Timezyme” (Klein, 2007).

Melatonin is also present in many non-vertebrate taxa, but its precise role is, in most cases, unknown (Hardeland and Poeggeler, 2003). In insects the presence of melatonin has been reported in some species including, amongst others, *Locusta migratoria*, *Drosophila*, the silkworm *Bombyx mori*, the Chinese tasar moth *Antheraea pernyi* and the pea aphid *Acyrtosiphon pisum* (Finocchiaro et al., 1988; Gao and Hardie, 1997; Itoh et al., 1995a; Mohamed et al., 2014; Vivien-Roels and Pévet, 1993). Some reports have also shown a circadian rhythm in the synthesis of the hormone in insects, with a nocturnal peak in some cases (Bembenek et al., 2005; Itoh et al., 1995a, 1995b; Vieira et al., 2005). It is not known, however, whether the synthesis of melatonin in insects follows a pathway similar to that in vertebrates or what role plays, if any, in insect seasonality. In this respect, it is worth noting that AANAT-like activities have been reported in different insect species, in some cases showing rhythmicities concomitant with melatonin levels (Bembenek et al., 2005; Itoh et al., 1995a; Izawa et al., 2009; Mohamed et al., 2014). However, insects (and arthropods in general) lack true vertebrate-like AANAT orthologous genes (from now on v-AANAT) but possess instead arylalkylamine N-acetyltransferases that constitute a separate family within the larger GNAT superfamily although they are also usually referred to as AANATs (from now on insect-like AANAT or i-AANAT) (Coon and Klein, 2006; Klein, 2007; Falcón et al., 2014). It is worth to mention that recent RNAi experiments in *Antheraea pernyi* demonstrated that i-AANAT is essential for melatonin synthesis and is regulated by the circadian clock (Mohamed et al., 2014), thus suggesting a conserved role of melatonin as a circadian output in mammals and insects. In this context, it is

also relevant that melatonin was reported to increase the release of PTTH in a dose dependent manner in *Periplaneta americana* (Richter et al., 2000). The activation of PTTH release by melatonin was also demonstrated in *A. pernyi*. It was shown that melatonin synthesis was dependent on the regulation of the circadian clock over i-AANAT expression in circadian clock neurons. The melatonin signal was detected by melatonin receptors in adjacent PTTH producing neurons (Mohamed et al., 2014). On the other hand, there are very few reports on the participation of melatonin in the insect seasonal response. Most relevant for studies on aphid seasonality, Gao & Hardie (1997) reported that administration of melatonin to *A. pisum* aphids reared under long day conditions resulted in limited production of sexual individuals (which would normally occur only under SD conditions), which suggests a possible participation of melatonin in aphid photoperiodism. Others studies in which melatonin was administered to insects test the effect on the seasonal response were inconclusive, probably as a toxic effect of the melatonin dose used (L'Helias et al., 1995; Niva and Takeda, 2003).

3. Seasonal response in *Acyrtosiphon pisum*

The aphid species used in the present work is the pea aphid *Acyrtosiphon pisum* that belongs to the the subfamily Aphidinae. *A. pisum* is characterised by a holocyclic, monoecious life cycle developed on many herbaceous and some shrubby Fabaceae species, specially *Medicago sativa*, *Vicia faba* and *Trifolium sp.* (Blackman and Eastop, 2006). In addition to holocyclic lineages, anholocyclic and androcyclic¹ lineages can also be found in this species. At 18°C, *A. pisum* takes 10-12 days to reach adulthood. The monoecious life cycle and its short generation time make the pea aphid specially appropriate for laboratory rearing. The pea aphid has been used as a model for phenotypic plasticity in several genetic and physiological studies (Tagu et al., 2005; Hardie, 2009; Srinivasan and Brisson, 2012; Ishikawa and Miura, 2013; Ogawa and Miura, 2013; Brisson et al., 2016), as well as to study endosymbiotic relationships (Wilkinson et al., 2003; Gil et al., 2006; Pérez-Brocal et al., 2011). The publication of the *A. pisum* genome (The International Aphid Genomics Consortium, 2010) provided unprecedented accessible resources that promoted aphid research.

Our research group focused on the molecular bases of the pea aphid seasonal response as a model to gain knowledge on the molecular mechanisms that control aphid life cycles in general but also to learn on how diapause is regulated in insects. The availability of the pea aphid genome sequence (The International Aphid Genomics Consortium, 2010) allowed the search for the pea aphid genes orthologous of those that constitute the circadian clock of *Drosophila melanogaster* and other insects.

¹Aphid lineages that cannot produce sexual oviparous females, but retain the capability to produce males (Dixon, 1985).

The main aphid clock genes that would participate in the two feedback loops (see Figure I.10) were identified (Cortés, 2010; Cortés et al., 2010). By comparing the set of circadian clock genes identified in the pea aphid with those of other insects, the pea aphid circadian clock was classified in the ancestral type (both *CRY1* and *CRY2* are present) (Yuan et al., 2007). Nonetheless, aphids show some particularities (Figure I.16). The comparison of amino acid sequences of aphid clock proteins revealed that some of the circadian clock genes are evolving faster in aphids than in other insects, especially those orthologues of *per*, *tim* and *cry2* (two copies of the latter were found in the pea aphid), and to a lesser degree, of *Clk* and *cyc* (Cortés et al., 2010). It has been hypothesised that *PER*, *TIM* and *CRY2* would be involved in the negative loop in the ancestral type circadian clock, therefore the concurrent faster evolution of the three aphid orthologues is probably a consequence of the related function of these genes. Given the presence of a *CRY1* orthologue, it is surprising the absence of *JET* (Jetlag) in aphids since in *Drosophila* this F box ubiquitin ligase is known to participate in the light-mediated degradation of *TIM* (Koh, 2006). Moreover, the preliminary expression profiles of aphid genes *per*, *tim* and *cry2* in aphid heads showed a circadian rhythm with a maximum early in the night. Orthologous genes encoding *CYC*, *VRI* and *PDP1* also seemed to express rhythmically but with a morning peak in antiphase with *per*, *tim* and *cry2* (Cortés et al., 2010). This pattern is similar to that found in other insects, except for drosophilids in which *Clk* instead of *cyc* is expressed rhythmically (Rubin et al., 2006; Codd et al., 2007; Zhu et al., 2008; Bertossa et al., 2014). It could also be observed that aphid genes *per*, *Cry1*, both copies of *Cry2* and *Pdp1* displayed higher levels of expression in aphids reared in winter-like conditions than those reared in summer-like conditions, possibly

Figure I.16. Model of the circadian clock in *Drosophila* with indication of aphid particularities. Genes (represented by broken arrows) are organised into two interconnected feedback loops (Cyrán et al., 2003) including the orthologues present in *A. pisum* and major differences found in the aphid highlighted in red boxes. Proteins constituting the core of the two feedback loops in *Drosophila* are indicated by different shapes. See text for details. Proteins committed to degradation are indicated by dotted shapes. The pea aphid genome contains two copies of a mammalian-type *cryptochrome*, CRY2, which is absent in *Drosophila*. Their putative role as repressor of CLK:CYC dimers (Yuan et al., 2007) is suggested by a question mark. CLK:CYC dimers and PDP1 attached to broken arrows indicate their roles as transcription activators of corresponding genes. Nuclear localisation signals (NLS) in the aphid PER are highly divergent. Contrarily to *Drosophila*, rhythmic expression of *cyc* instead of *Clk* was found in aphids. JET was not found in the pea aphid genome, suggesting a different synchronisation of the aphid circadian clock by light. Lines ending in bars indicate negative regulation. Wavy and straight lines indicate rhythmic and not rhythmic transcription, respectively. Taken from Cortés et al. (2010).

relating the circadian genes with the aphid seasonal response (Cortés, 2010).

It has been long assumed that, as a result of the putative photoperiodic clock activity, specialised aphid neurosecretory cells (NSC) would send a message to the embryos to determine which path of development—parthenogenetic or sexual—should they be committed to (Steel and Lees, 1977). In this respect, experiments of microcauterisation were performed in order to see the relevance of the different NSC groups described in the aphid brain in different biological events (Steel and Lees, 1977). Destruction of NSC group I produced a depletion of NSM (neurosecretory material) in the respective axons and averted the production of *virginoparae* under long days (see section I.1.3), therefore it was proposed that these cells produced a parthenogenesis promoting factor that was named “virginoparin” (Steel and Lees, 1977; Steel, 1978). On the other hand, destruction of NSC group I in aphids under short day conditions had no effect on the production of sexual females (i.e. *oviparae*). Additionally, ablation of a region adjacent and lateral to the NSC group I, known as *pars lateralis* (PL), without damaging NSC group I (see Figure I.5 A) had the same effect as destroying the NSC group I itself, producing a depletion of axons of NSC group I running to the abdomen and promoting the production of *oviparae* under long days (see Figure I.13 B). It was then concluded that the PL probably contained the photoperiodic clock and counter that would control the photoperiodic effector NSC group I (Steel and Lees, 1977). The effects of microcauterisation of NSC group II were also analysed. However, destruction of NSC group II had no effect on the seasonal response. Destruction of NSC group II on 3rd larval instar allowed moulting to 4th instar but not the imaginal final moult, although it averted the moulting and

tanning process of the next instar. Therefore, the NSC group II cells were proposed to be the production sites of prothoracicotropic hormone (PTTH) and bursicon¹, which are known to control moulting and tanning processes (Steel, 1978; Smith and Rybczynski, 2012; Song, 2012). Bilateral destruction of NSC group III, IV and V had no evident effect in any developmental stage, although ablation of NSC group V was particularly described as technically difficult (Steel, 1978).

Despite the extensive bibliography on the seasonal response of aphids, there is very little information on the location of the putative photoperiodic clock elements and whether it would overlap with localisation of circadian clock elements. Microcauterisation experiments revealed that a region in the dorsal anterior protocerebrum close to the optic lobes known as *pars lateralis* (PL) (see Figure 1.5 A), was required for the production of parthenogenetic females in aphids reared under LD conditions (Steel, 1978).

Previous analysis of expression in aphids identified a putative GABA transporter that was upregulated under SD conditions (Ramos et al., 2003). Moreover, cDNA microarray analyses also revealed differential regulation of genes involved in cellular signalling and transduction, and cuticular proteins (Le Trionnaire et al., 2007). In addition, suppression subtractive hybridisation (SSH) libraries comparing LD and SD reared aphids revealed changes in expression of genes related to gametogenesis and gonad development, and confirmed regulation of cuticular proteins among other proteins, including some lacking homologues in the databases (Cortés et al., 2008). Peptidomic and transcriptomic analyses identified photoperiodic

¹ Heterodimeric neuropeptide constituted by two subunits, α - and β -bursicon, involved in cuticle tanning and wing expansion in insects (Song, 2012).

regulated genes and proteins involved in photoreception, neurotransmission, cuticle remodelling and JH metabolism (Le Trionnaire et al., 2009, 2012). Furthermore, these studies revealed several neuropeptides and neurohormones in the pea aphid *A. pisum*, including various putative Insulin Related Peptides (IRP), being some of them, as well as the insulin receptor, downregulated in SD conditions, while an insulin-degrading enzyme was upregulated in SD conditions (Le Trionnaire et al., 2009, 2012). In addition, JH synthesis genes were downregulated in SD conditions (Le Trionnaire et al., 2012) while genes involved in JH degradation were upregulated in SD (Ishikawa et al., 2013). In this context it is important to recall that low JH titres have been related to sexual morph determination in aphids (Ishikawa et al., 2013). Peptidomic analysis in *A. pisum* failed to detect some neuropeptides such as neuroparsin homologues, probably due to a low conservation among insects, which have been found to be synthesised in medial NSC of other insects (equivalent to NSC group I and II in aphids). Moreover, low levels of PTH have been found in diapause determined lepidopterans (Sauman and Reppert, 1996b; Smith and Rybczynski, 2012), even though the homologue of PTH was not found among the aphid neuropeptides (Huybrechts et al., 2010). Pigment dispersing factor/hormone (PDF/PDH), is an important neuropeptide known as the main transmitter regulating circadian locomotor activities in *Drosophila* (Shafer and Taghert, 2009) and probably in insects in general (Chuman et al., 2002; Sato et al., 2002; Lee et al., 2009; Shiga and Numata, 2009; Vafopoulou et al., 2010; Hassaneen et al., 2011). Despite PDF is regarded as an ubiquitous neuropeptide among insect species and arthropods in general, it was not found in *A. pisum* -omic analysis (Le Trionnaire et al., 2009, 2012; Huybrechts et al., 2010). Some

other neuropeptides seem to be genuinely absent in aphids such as corazonin, commonly used as a circadian clock marker in Lepidoptera (Sehadová et al., 2004; Zhu et al., 2008), sulfakinin and vasopressin (Huybrechts et al., 2010).

Extensive gene duplication has been postulated as one of the factors that facilitated the evolution of developmental plasticity displayed by aphids (Grantham et al., 2015). Epigenetics has been proposed as a regulatory mechanism of polyphenisms in some insects. For instance, the caste polyphenism in *Apis mellifera* is known to be partially regulated by epigenetic mechanisms such as DNA methylation, showing differential methylation patterns between queen and workers (Srinivasan and Brisson, 2012; Grantham et al., 2015). Moreover, the induction of diapause by SD conditions in *Nasonia vitripennis* has been shown to depend on DNA methylation (Pegoraro et al., 2016).

Aphids have a fully functional set of proteins involved in DNA methylation and chromatin remodelling. The search for DNMTs orthologues in the pea aphid revealed a fully functional methylation system, including two genes encoding DNMT1 for maintenance of methylation patterns, one encoding DNMT2 involved in tRNA methylation, and two encoding DNMT3, as well as genes encoding a MBP and a DNMT1 associated protein (Foret et al., 2012). With respect to histone modification, the pea aphid genome encodes a complete set of histones, including the core histones H2A, H2B, H3 and H4, the linker histone H1, and some histone variants, while other histone variants and protamines are absent. In addition to the histones, the pea aphid genome also encodes for different classes of enzymes involved in histone modification such as histone acetyl transferases (HAT) and histone

deacetylases (HDAC) among others, and the main remodelling complexes (SWI/NSF, CHD1, ISWI, and NURD) (Walsh et al., 2010). Current hypothesis propose the switch of developmental fate of aphid embryos by means of epigenetic mechanisms that would regulate the expression of morph specific genes (Simon et al., 2011; Srinivasan and Brisson, 2012; Grantham et al., 2015). This epigenetic regulation would be controlled by a signal cascade triggered by environmental changes sensed by aphid mothers and transmitted to the developing embryos (Rider et al., 2010). Furthermore, aphids display a bimodal methylation profile, as it was found in other phenotypically plastic insect such as *Apis mellifera* (Srinivasan and Brisson, 2012; Grantham et al., 2015). Moreover, some evidence suggests an epigenetically regulated role of JH in aphid wing polyphenism (Glastad et al., 2011).

In the present work, our research has been focused in taking a closer look at the circadian clock genes to complete their characterisation and to analyse their putative role in aphid photoperiodism. The characterisation of transcript sequences has been completed for *per* and *tim*. Furthermore, an intense alternative splicing for most clock genes has been discovered and the expression of circadian clock genes has been analysed in holocyclic and anholocyclic strains in the context of photoperiodism. In addition, *per* and *tim* transcripts have been localised in the aphid brain. Furthermore, the hypothetical implication of melatonin and AANATs in the reproductive polyphenism of *A. pisum* has also been examined. Finally, the gene encoding the aphid PTH, a hormone known to participate in circadian rhythms and photoperiodism in other insects, has been characterised and its transcripts localised.

II. Objectives

II.OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the present work are framed within those of a wider project aimed at investigating whether the circadian clock or some of its components participate in the control of the seasonal response in aphids. In particular, this thesis is centred on the analysis of two sets of elements of the circadian machinery: the genes at the core of the circadian clock and the putative elements that may constitute the output of the clock in the model aphid *Acyrtosiphon pisum*. This general objective has been developed through the following **specific objectives**:

1. complete the characterisation of genes *period*, *timeless*, *Clock*, *cycle*, *Pdp1* and *vriille.*, which make up the core of the circadian clock in the pea aphid *A. pisum*.
2. Characterise and quantify the expression of the pea aphid clock core genes in the context of both circadian rhythms and photoperiodism.
3. Localise where central clock genes *period* and *timeless* are expressed in the pea aphid brain and compare with regions known to be relevant for the aphid photoperiodic response.
4. Identify, characterise and determine the localisation of putative clock output elements including the neuropeptide PDF, the hormone melatonin and aphid insect-type *AANAT* genes, and the hormone PTTH.
5. Quantify melatonin levels and aphid *AANAT* expression in the context of both circadian rhythms and photoperiodism.
6. Investigate a possible role of aphid *AANAT* genes as regulators of melatonin synthesis in the pea aphid.

II.OBJECTIVES

III. Materials And Methods

1. Aphid rearing and induction of the seasonal response

Two strains of the pea aphid *Acyrtosiphon pisum* were used in the experiments presented in this thesis: York Red 2 (YR2) originally collected from York (UK, 53°57'30"N 1°4'49"W) is the holocyclic reference strain used in our laboratory, and Gallur Rojo (GR) originally collected in Gallur (Spain, 41° 52' 09" N, 1° 18' 58" O) is our anholocyclic reference strain (see section I.1.3). *Acyrtosiphon pisum* aphids were grown on broad bean plants (*Vicia faba*) covered with perforated plastic wrap to avoid cross-contamination of strains. Aphid stocks have been kept in this way for more than 10 years as clonal parthenogenetic colonies in chambers with controlled temperature and photoperiod. In order to maintain the aphids indefinitely in the parthenogenetic phase of their life cycle, the insects are kept under long day (LD) photoperiod consisting of 16 h of light followed by 8 h of darkness (16L:8D) at 18°C mimicking summer day length. At 18°C, depending on the strain, pea aphids take roughly 11 or 12 days from birth to onset of parturition of the following generation. Four or five individuals are transferred to a new plant every two weeks starting fresh cultures.

The induction of the seasonal response, i.e. the development of the sexual morphs (males and females), is achieved by transferring aphids to a chamber with short day (SD) photoperiod (12L:12D) that mimics "winter" photoperiod (Figure III.1). This change in photoperiod, without modification of temperature, is sufficient to promote the development of both males and sexual females in the holocyclic strain used in the experiments.

Sampling of aphids for the different experiments always followed the protocol shown in Figure III.1. To reduce the stress levels that would activate the production of winged morphs, a minimum of two generations of aphids are allowed to grow at low population density levels (five aphids per seedling) under LD conditions previous to the sampling of the so called G0 (Generation 0). Synchronised L1 aphids born within a period of 24 h were collected and transferred to new plants maintained in the same LD conditions. These aphids were designated G0. After 5-6 days, these G0 aphids reached the L3 stage and then, the population was split in two groups. One group, referred to as LD G0, remained under LD conditions. The second group was transferred to SD conditions, thereby named SD G0. The next generation of aphids born from SD G0 individuals were named SD G1, which were kept under the same SD conditions as their mothers. In order to sample synchronised SD G1 aphids, adult aphids from SD G0 were allowed to grow and begin parturition. By the time all the SD G0 aphids began parturition, the SD G0 adults were then moved to new *ca.* 10 cm high seedlings in groups of five aphids per plant. Adult SD G0 individuals in new plants were allowed to give birth to a synchronised G1 for a maximum of 24 h and the SD G0 adults were finally removed. Again, to avoid stress on aphids, the population of SD G1 was kept at approximately 25 aphids per plant by removing the excess of SD G1 aphids with a thin brush at the

Figure III.1. Next page. Aphid rearing diagram. Procedure used to obtain LD and SD G1 aphids. LD corresponds to non-induced aphids reared continuously under long-day conditions. SD corresponds to aphids reared under short-day conditions since third nymph instar (L3). Both LD and SD aphids were derived from starting L3 nymphs obtained from low-density reared aphids on excised leaves (indicated as parental generation in the figure). G1 adult aphids reared under both LD and SD were collected for comparative analysis of expression. Adapted from Cortés, (2010).

moment of birth. SD G1 aphids were then allowed to grow under the SD conditions and collected at appropriate times. In parallel, LD G0 aphids were treated in the same way as the SD G0 to obtain the LD G1, except that the LD conditions were maintained. LD and SD aphids of the G1 generation were collected by snap-freezing them in liquid nitrogen and stored at -70°C until RNA extraction. Aphids from plants where more than two G1 winged aphids out of 25 were observed were considered stressed and excluded from the experiments. The induction of the seasonal response was confirmed in all induction experiments by leaving 10-15 SD G1 aphids to give birth to the next generation named SD G2. The SD G2 aphids were allowed to reach adulthood and then inspected for the presence of males and sexual females. In all cases aphids of holocyclic strain (YR2) produced sexual morphs under SD photoperiod while aphids of the anholocyclic strain (GR) maintained parthenogenetic reproduction.

2. General molecular techniques

2.1. Total RNA extraction

The extraction of total RNA was always done under RNase free working conditions. Depending on the experiment, whole aphids or head parts were used as starting aphid material. In those experiments in which aphids were sampled at time points along the day/night cycle corresponding to the dark period, dim red light was used to avoid interference on the circadian rhythm or the induction of the seasonal response (see section III.1). Previously to total RNA extraction, frozen aphids were carefully processed by dissecting the head one by one in ice cold RNase free PBS and quickly pooling the heads in 500 μ l of ice cold TRI Reagent[®] Solution (Ambion). Once all the aphids in a sample (usually 25 or 50 heads) were processed, the excised heads in TRI Reagent[®] Solution were frozen again in liquid nitrogen and stored back at -70°C. Total RNA was extracted following the manufacturer's protocol (Applied Biosystems). Briefly, the samples were homogenised in 500 μ l of TRI reagent in a 1.5 ml centrifuge tube with plastic pestles, incubated for 5 min at room temperature and centrifuged at 12000 x g for 8 min at 4°C. Next, the upper aqueous phase was transferred to a new centrifuge tube and 250 μ l of isopropyl alcohol were added and then vortexed for 5 seconds. After a 5 min incubation at room temperature, the samples were centrifuged at 12000 x g for 8 min at 4°C. The supernatant was discarded. Then, the RNA pellets were washed twice by adding 1 ml 75% ethanol followed by a centrifugation at 7500 x g for 5 min at 4°C. After the second wash, the residual ethanol was air dried and the RNA pellet was resuspended in 20 μ l of RNase free water. Total RNA

was then quantified by spectrophotometry using a NanoDrop ND-1000 (Nanodrop Technologies, Inc.), including the assessment of its quality by looking at ratios A260/A280 and A260/A230. The RNA was then stored at -80°C until cDNA synthesis.

2.2. cDNA synthesis

By using the PrimeScript™ Reverse Transcriptase (RT) (Takara Bio Inc.), RNAs obtained as described above were copied to DNA (cDNA) for the characterisation and the quantification of expression of the different genes analysed. Seeking to maximise enrichment in cDNAs derived from mature mRNAs, reverse transcription was performed using oligo (dT)₁₈ that prime cDNA synthesis based on polyA tails. Each RT reaction consisted of 4 μl of 5x RT buffer (250 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.3, 375 mM KCl, 15 mM MgCl₂), 1 μl of a mixture containing 10 mM of each dNTP, 1 μl of 50 mM oligo (dT)₁₈, 0.5 μl of RNase inhibitor (40 U/ μl), 0.5 μl of RT (20 U/ μl) and a volume of RNA containing 1-5 μg of total RNA. RNase free water was added to adjust to a final reaction volume of 20 μl . Total RNA, H₂O, oligo (dT)₁₈ and dNTPs were firstly mixed, spun down and heated at 65°C for 5 min to break RNA secondary structures and immediately placed on ice. Next, the rest of reagents, previously mixed, were added to each of the RNA samples. An extra sample with no RT was usually prepared to evaluate genomic contamination. Samples were incubated 30 min at 42°C followed by a final incubation at 70°C for 15 min to inactivate RT. cDNAs used for RT-qPCR experiments (see section III.2.7), included a no-RT control sample in which the RT was not included.

2.3. PCR amplification and purification of DNA fragments

Characterisation of different gene transcripts and their respective alternative splice variants was achieved by amplification of cDNA fragments using the PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) technique. Specific sets of primers and PCR conditions were used for each of the studied genes (IX.1). The standard profile used for DNA amplification consisted of an initial denaturation step of 1 min at 94°C followed by 40 cycles each consisting of a 30 seconds at 94°C denaturing step, an annealing step of 30 seconds at a temperature ranging from 54°C to 60°C, and an elongation step of 0.5-2 min at 68°C. A final elongation step of 10 min at 68°C was included after cycling. In cases when the analysed genes showed very low expression, a secondary PCR (nested or heminested) had to be performed. This secondary PCR was usually carried out as previously described but using 1 µl of the primary PCR product as a template instead of cDNA and using at least one primer internal to the previously amplified fragment.

Purification and concentration of amplified DNA fragments was done as a previous step for sequencing, cloning and RNA transcription (see below) following alternative protocols depending on the subsequent particular use of the DNA. Fragments used for sequencing and cloning were purified by ammonium acetate-ethanol precipitation (Crouse and Amorese, 1987). Alternatively, a commercial High Pure PCR Product Purification Kit (Roche) was used.

2.4. Cloning

In cases where PCR amplification of certain gene transcripts produced different amplicons, the purified PCR product was cloned into plasmid vectors. The pGEM®-T Easy Vector System I (Promega) was the vector of choice in the present work. Purified PCR products (see above) were ligated into the pGEM vector as follows. The ligation reaction was prepared in a microcentrifuge tube containing 5 µl of 2x Rapid Ligation Buffer, 1 µl of pGEM®-T Easy Vector (50 ng), a variable volume of the purified PCR product to get a molar ratio vector:insert of 1:3, 1 µl of T4 DNA ligase (3 U/µl) and nuclease-free H₂O up to 10 µl final volume. The ligation reaction was incubated overnight at 4°C. Then, bacterial transformation was carried out by adding 100 µl of DH5α *Escherichia coli* competent cells (Life Technologies) to the ligation, mixed by gentle pipetting and incubated for 30 min on ice. Next, a heat shock at 42°C for 45 sec in a water bath was applied and immediately incubated on ice for 5 min. Afterwards, 900 µl of sterile LB medium (10 g Bacto Tryptone, 5 g Bacto Yeast extract and 10 g NaCl in 1 L of H₂O, pH 7.0) were added and incubated for 1 h at 37°C with shaking at 250 rpm. The cells were collected at the bottom of the tube by centrifuging at 6000 x g for 1 min and subsequently removing 800 µl of supernatant. The cells were resuspended in the ca. 200 µl of medium left and separately plated 20 µl and 180 µl on LB-agar supplemented with 50 mg/ml ampicillin, 4‰ X-Gal and 4‰ IPTG for blue/white colony screening. Then, the plates were incubated overnight at 37°C. In order to detect colonies containing the right insert, 10 to 15 white colonies were picked from plates and subjected to PCR (colony PCR) using the T7 and SP6 primers that flank the cloning site (see “pGEMvector.txt” in ANNEXES). The

resulting amplicons were loaded into an agarose gel and after gel electrophoresis, the size of the inserts was checked. Replicates of the positive colonies were transferred to a new plate.

2.5. Sequencing

Purified PCR products or recombinant plasmids were used as templates for Sanger sequencing. The reactions were set up by adding 0.4 μ l of Big Dye Terminator v2.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit (ABI Prism[®]), 1.6 μ l Sequencing Buffer (400mM TrisHCl pH 9.0, 10mM MgCl₂), 0.5 μ l of 10 μ M sequencing primer and 10-100 ng of the purified DNA template. The final volume was adjusted with milliQ water up to 8 μ l. The sequencing reaction was done in a thermocycler with the following profile: 1 min 94°C, 99 cycles of 10 sec at 94°C, 6 sec at 52°C, and 4 min at 60°C. Sequencing reactions were loaded onto an ABI3730XL automated (ABI). Chromatogram handling and assembly of lectures were done with the Staden Package (Staden et al., 2000).

2.6. Gene model and regulatory elements analysis

The sequences experimentally obtained for the different genes were used to define the transcript models on genome scaffolds. The models were built with Unipro UGENE software 1.25.0 (Okonechnikov et al., 2012), which was also used to annotate alternative exons, conserved domains and sequence polymorphisms, and primers. The search for regulatory elements such as E-box and V/P-box was carried out using the Unipro UGENE search tool and were also annotated. In addition, annotation of primer sequences and other relevant features were also included in the models.

2.7. Analysis of expression through RT-qPCR

Threshold cycle (C_T) values, defined as the fractional cycle number at which the fluorescence reaches a fixed value, were used for estimating relative concentrations of target sequences using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_T}$ method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001). The efficiencies of amplification for any set of primers was considered 100% in all cases. In this method the relative amount of target cDNA is normalised with respect to an endogenous reference control as ΔC_T that is defined for each sample by the following formula:

$$\Delta C_T = C_T^{target} - C_T^{reference}$$

ΔC_T was also calculated from an inter-run calibrator (IRC), a standard cDNA sample that was included in all experiments. As endogenous control of constitutive expression, we used the *A. pisum* ribosomal protein unit L7 (*rpl7*) (Nakabachi et al., 2005). Relative expression (R) was calculated for each sample as follows:

$$R = 2^{-\Delta\Delta C_T}$$

where $\Delta\Delta C_T$ was calculated as follows:

$$\Delta\Delta C_T = \Delta C_T^{SAMPLE} - \Delta C_T^{IRC}$$

In order to minimise pipetting error, the cDNA templates (see section III.2.2) were diluted 1/10 and distributed in 5 μ l aliquots to be used integrally for each of the three technical replicates. Furthermore, three biological replicates per treatment (i.e. cDNAs corresponding to three groups of aphids from the same conditions) were included in the analysis.

Additionally, each assay included two negative controls: a RT-qPCR reaction without cDNA template, to test for non specific amplification and an RT control, a RT-qPCR reaction performed without including the RT enzyme (see section III.2.2) intended to detect possible genomic DNA contamination carried over from the RNA extraction. All reactions were set up by adding 10 μ l of Power SYBR[®] Green PCR Master Mix, 1 μ l of forward and 1 μ l of reverse 10 μ M primers and milliQ water up to 15 μ l. 5 μ l of the previously diluted cDNA were added to each reaction making up a 20 μ l total volume. The RT-qPCR reaction was set up in a Step One Plus Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems) using the following profile: 95°C for 10 min followed by 40 cycles each consisting of a 15 sec denaturation step at 95°C, and 1 min at 60°C for annealing and elongation steps. In all cases, primers were designed to withstand annealing temperatures higher than 60°C. At the end of the amplification steps, a melting curve was immediately performed consisting of 15 sec at 95°C, 1 min at 65°C from which +0.3°C incremental steps of 15 sec followed until a temperature of 95°C was reached. The Step One Software v2.3 (Applied Biosystems) was used to obtain C_T values and to inspect amplification and melting curves for double peaks that might indicate genomic DNA amplification. To avoid amplification of genomic DNA that might be present in the samples, at least one of the gene specific primers was designed across contiguous exons or in exons separated by large introns.

Differences between mean expression values of the variables strain, rearing photoperiod and ZT¹ (*Zeitgeber* Time), were tested for statistical significance using ANOVA. In addition, homogeneity of variances was

¹ The phase of the circadian cycle, i.e. a particular time point, is indicated by the ZT system in which ZT0 corresponds to the time of light onset. E.g. ZT9 refers to 9 h after lights onset.

Figure III.2. Rhythms are defined by a set of parameters. Period is the duration of a full cycle. MESOR (Midline Estimating Statistic of Rhythms) is the central value around which the oscillation occurs. Amplitude is half the range of excursion of the cycle with a given period. Acrophase is the moment at which the amplitude is at maximum. Modified from Refinetti et al., (2007).<

assessed by Levene tests. HSD Tukey and Bonferroni *post hoc* tests were applied when variances were homogeneous, and Games-Howell *post hoc* analyses when variances were not homogeneous. All statistical tests were performed with the SPSS Statistics package v22.0 software (IBM Corp).

When ANOVA tests revealed significant differences in expression between ZTs, a COSINOR analysis (Refinetti et al., 2007; Cornelissen, 2014) was performed to test for circadian rhythmicity and to obtain the parameters defining the rhythm (MESOR, amplitude and acrophase) (Figure III.2).

3. Immunohistochemistry and *in situ* hybridisation

3.1. Aphid central nervous system fixation and dissection

Insects were fixed in PFAT-DMSO (4% paraformaldehyde in 1X PBS¹, 0.1% TritonX-100, 5% DMSO v/v) over night at 4°C. Fixed individuals were washed 3 x 10 min in PBSTx (TritonX-100 0.1% in 1X PBS). Subsequently, dissections were carried out in glass block dishes on ice in either cold PBSTx or PBSTw (0.1% Tween 20 in 1X PBS). The head capsules were carefully opened with tweezers and the central nervous systems (CNS), including brain and ganglia, were dissected out. From this point, CNS that were going to be used only for melatonin or PDH/PDF localisation (see section III.3.2) were pooled in cold PBTx or PBTw, immediately proceeding to detection using the corresponding antibodies. CNS to be used in mRNA localisation by *in situ* hybridisation (ISH) (see section III.3.4) were pooled in ice cold methanol immediately after dissection, washed twice in methanol, and stored at -20°C in tight sealed microcentrifuge tubes until ISH protocol was initiated.

3.2. Detection using antibodies

Individuals from both YR2 and GR pea aphid strains were collected from long day (LD) and short day (SD) conditions (see section III.1). Sampling

¹ Phosphate-buffered saline. For 1 l of 10X PBS add 3.21g NaH₂PO₄ x 2H₂O; 20.7g Na₂HPO₄ x 7H₂O; 90g NaCl. Adjust pH with either H₃PO₄ or NaOH. Following the recipe from Wülbeck and Helfrich-Förster (2007).

included aphids from each larval stage up to 9 days old adults for each strain and photoperiod(YR2 LD, YR2 SD, GR LD and GR SD). All CNS were fixed and dissected as described in the previous section. Afterwards, CNSs were preincubated overnight at 4°C in blocking solution containing PBS, 0.5%, TritonX-100, 10% Normal Goat Serum (NGS, Sigma Aldrich). Next, CNS were incubated in 1:300 rabbit anti-melatonin antibody (Byorbit, UK) diluted in 10% NGS, 0.1% sodium azide and PBST 0.5%, for 5 days at 4°C. The excess, non specifically bound antibody was then removed by washing CNSs for 10 min in PBST 0.1% three times. Detection with a secondary antibody was carried out by incubating with Cy3 goat anti-rabbit 1:300 (Jackson Immunoresearch, UK) in 10% NGS, 0.1% sodium azide and PBST 0.5% for 1-2 days at 4°C. The excess, unspecifically bound secondary antibody was removed by washing CNS for 10 min in PBST 0.1% three times. Finally, CNSs were mounted on microscope glass slides with glycerol containing 3% propyl gallate.

Localisation of PDF/PDH with antibodies was carried out following the same procedure described for melatonin localisation except that two primary antibodies, a polyclonal mouse anti-PDF (1:1000) and a rabbit anti-PDH (1:1000), respectively followed by goat Cy2 anti-mouse (1:200) and goat Cy3 anti-rabbit (1:200), were used for immunohistochemistry (IHC) detection.

3.3. Synthesis of DIG-labelled riboprobes

RNA probes labelled with digoxigenin (DIG) were synthesised by a modification of the method described by Wülbeck and Helfrich-Förster (2007). First, cDNA regions of each gene of interest of approximately 600

to 900 bp were amplified by PCR (see III.1). PCR products were purified by ammonium precipitation and the amplicon size was checked by electrophoresis on agarose gels. Next, the purified PCR product was cloned into pGEM®-T easy vector (Promega) and used to transform *E. coli* thermocompetent cells (see section III.2.4). Then, colony PCR was used to screen for transformants with the appropriate inserts and those that revealed positive, were purified and sequenced from both extremes using SP6 and T7 primers to know the orientation of the insert. Subsequently, minipreps of selected colonies were performed to obtain high amounts of purified insert-containing plasmids using High Pure Plasmid Isolation Kit (Roche). To synthesise the riboprobes, templates were obtained by simply doing a PCR with SP6 and T7 primers (see IX.1) and DNA fragment purification with the High Pure PCR Product Purification Kit (Roche). The purified PCR products were then quantified by spectrophotometry using a NanoDrop ND-1000 (Nanodrop Technologies, Inc., Wilmington, DE, USA) and used as a template for RNA transcription. Taking into account the insert orientation, purified templates were used to synthesise DIG-labelled sense and antisense probes with RNAPol SP6 or RNAPol T7 (both from

Table III.1. Templates used to synthesise RNA probes were amplified with the following primers. Primer sequences can be found in IX.1.

Gene Name	F primer	R primer	Amplicon Size ¹ (bp)
<i>Period</i>	Per-F6	Per-R2	737
<i>Timeless</i>	Tim-F17	Tim-R6	789
<i>AANAT1</i>	AANAT1-F3	AANAT1-R3	715
<i>AANAT2</i>	AANAT2-F3	AANAT2-R2	748
<i>AANAT3</i>	AANAT3-F6	AANAT3-R0	836
<i>AANAT4</i>	AANAT4-F5	AANAT4-R1	803
<i>Ptth</i>	PTTH-F2	PTTH-R2	831

¹ Final probe size includes 178 bp extra corresponding to the plasmid multicloning site.

Roche). Sense probes were used as negative controls. Antisense probes were used to localise gene specific mRNAs. Transcription was carried out in 0.2 ml microcentrifuge tubes following the recommendations (Roche). Each reaction consisted of 200 ng of DNA template, 2 µl of DIG labelling mix 10x, 2 µl of 10x transcription buffer, 1 µl of RNase inhibitor, corresponding SP6 or T7 RNA polymerase (see above), and RNase free H₂O up to 20 µl final volume. All reagents were carefully mixed and incubated 2 h at 37°C in a thermocycler. To stop the reaction, 2 µl of 0.2 M EDTA pH 8.0 were added and the reaction was stored at 4°C until purification. Probe volumes were then brought up to 50 µl by adding 30 µl of RNase free water. Next, the probes were purified with mini QuickSpin RNA columns (Roche) following the manufacturer's instructions, diluted 50% with deionised formamide and stored at -20°C until use. Quantification of the probes was assessed by dot blot assays. Briefly, serial dilutions of the probes and a control DIG-labelled RNA of known concentration were UV-crosslinked to a nylon membrane (BrightStar-Plus, Ambion). Next, the membrane was blocked with Blocking Reagent (Roche) and incubated with alkaline phosphatase (AP) anti-DIG Fab fragments (Roche). After washing the excess of antibody, NBT/BCIP substrate (Roche) was used for detection. Probe concentration was roughly assessed by comparison of signal intensity between spots of our labelled probes with those of control RNA.

3.4. *In situ* hybridisation (ISH)

Localisation of transcripts was carried out using DIG-labelled RNA probes (see section III.3.3). Fixed CNSs (see section III.3.1) stored in 100% methanol were gradually rehydrated in PBTw (0.1% Tween 20 in RNase free 1X PBS), washed in PBTw, and treated with proteinase K (3 µg/ml) for 3 min at room

temperature and 1 h on ice. Proteinase digestion was blocked with 2 mg/ml glycine. Next, CNSs were refixed in PFATw (4% para-formaldehyde in 1X PBS, 0.1% Tween 20) for 20 min and washed 5 times in RNase free PBTw for 5 min each. Then, the samples were incubated for 5 min in a 1:1 mix of PBTw and pre-hybridisation buffer¹ (preHB). Blocking was carried out by incubating for 2 h on a water bath at 65°C in hybridisation buffer² (HB). Next, the hybridisation was done by incubating the blocked CNSs with HB plus the corresponding probe overnight at 65°C in a water bath. Non specifically hybridised probe was removed with the following washes at 65°C: two washes of 15 min in preHB, three washes of 15 min each in increasing mixes of preHB:2xSSC 0.1% Tween 20 (3:2, 1:1, 2:3), a single wash of 15 min in 2xSSC 0.1% Tween 20, followed by two washes of 15 min in 0.2xSSC 0.1% Tween 20. At this point, the following washes were carried out at room temperature: three washes of 10 min each in increasing mixes of 0.2xSSC 0.1% Tween 20: PBTw transition (3:2, 1:1, 2:3), and three washes of 5 min in PBTw. Next, CNSs were blocked to avoid unspecific binding of the AP conjugated anti-DIG antibody by incubation for 2 h in PBTw supplemented with 1% Blocking Reagent (Roche) at room temperature with gentle shaking. Afterwards, the blocking buffer was replaced with fresh blocking buffer plus 1:1000 AP-conjugated anti-DIG Fab fragments and incubated overnight at 4°C with gentle shaking. Two different AP substrates were used to detect hybridised probes: NBT/BCIP³ that produce a blue/purple precipitate and Fast Red/HNPP⁴ that produces a chromogenic

1 5x SSC (saline sodium citrate), 50% formamide, and 0.1% Tween 20.

2 preHB plus 100 µg/ml heparin, 100 µg/ml salmon sperm DNA and 500 µg/ml yeast tRNA, pH 6.0.

3 Nitro blue tetrazolium chloride/5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl phosphate.

4 4-chloro-2-methylbenzenediazonium hemi-zinc chloride salt/2-hydroxy-3-naphtoic acid-2'-phenylanilide phosphate.

red and fluorescent precipitate (Roche). Both substrates were used following the manufacturer's instructions. Times of incubation with substrates varied depending on the expression levels of the transcript being detected. The reaction was stopped by washing three times for 5 min in PBTw. Then, the tissues were immersed in increasing concentrations of glycerol (25%, 50%, 75% and 100%). Finally, the CNS were mounted on microscope glass slides and sealed with nail polish.

3.5. Colocalisation of transcripts and melatonin

Colocalisation of the aphid insect-type AANAT transcripts and MEL was achieved by combining ISH and melatonin detection with antibodies previously described. First, the RNA ISH protocol was applied as described above, except that especial care was taken to protect samples from light to avoid photo-degradation of melatonin (Brömme et al., 2008). After the last wash in PBTw, the tissues were not transferred to glycerol but instead to the blocking step of the IHC protocol (see section III.3.2). To avoid interference of fluorescent signal detection between the secondary antibody Cy3 goat anti-rabbit used for melatonin detection and the AP substrate Fast Red/HNPP, the secondary antibody in the IHC protocol was replaced by an Alexa647 goat anti-rabbit.

3.6. Microscopy and imaging

Transcripts detected in CNS whole mount preparations with NBT/BCIP and FastRed/HNPP were imaged in a DS-Ri1 CCD camera (Nikon) mounted on a Eclipse E800 microscope (Nikon). The objectives used for imaging included a Plan Fluor 20X/0.5 and 40x/0.75 objectives. Images were acquired with NIS-Elements F software v4.30.01 (Nikon).

Whole-mount fluorescent preparations of the CNS were scanned with a confocal laser scanning microscope (FV1000, Olympus) using 20x and 40x objectives. All brains were scanned with a scanning speed of 400 or 200 Hz, a pinhole of 1 Airy unit, a step size of 1.0–0.4 μm , and a line average of 2–4. Kalman filter was activated to remove noise signal. Both melatonin and transcripts detected by ISH using FastRed/HNPP substrate were imaged with a 559 nm excitation laser. Colocalisation of aphid insect-type *AANAT* genes with melatonin were imaged with 559 nm and 635 nm lasers, respectively. Images were processed and arranged with Fiji v1.50i software (Schindelin et al., 2012).

4. Melatonin quantification by HPLC MS/MS

Quantification of melatonin content was carried out following a method we specifically developed for aphids (Escrivá et al., 2016). Three replicate groups of 50 adult aphids from the two strains and both LD and SD photoperiods were sampled and accurately weighted at ZT6 and ZT18 (i.e. 6 and 18 hours after lights on, respectively). The insects were snap frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C until melatonin extraction.

4.1. Sample preparation and extraction

Melatonin extraction from insects was carried out on ice under dark conditions to prevent compound degradation. The aphids were introduced into 2 ml tubes (wrapped in aluminium foil) and 0.5 ml of methanol/water 1:1 (v/v) were added. The samples were completely homogenised using an Ultraturrax T8 IKA (Staufen, Germany) during 1 min and centrifuged at 14,000 rpm at 4 °C for 10 min. The supernatant fraction was filtered through a 0.22 µm filter Phenomenex (Madrid, Spain) and 10 µl were injected into an LC-MS/MS (Liquid Chromatography-Mass/Mass) system.

4.2. LC-MS/MS analysis

Detection and quantitation of melatonin was performed in a 3200 QTrap® LC-MS/MS System (Applied Biosystems) equipped with a Turbo V® ionspray ESI source coupled to Agilent 1200 liquid chromatograph (Agilent Technologies). Chromatographic separation of melatonin was performed with a reversed-phase analytical column (Gemini® C18 column, 3 µm particle size, 150 x 2 mm, I.D.), equipped with a C18 (4 x 2 mm, I. D.; 5 µm

security guard cartridge) all from Phenomenex. Elution was carried out in binary gradient mode. Mobile phases contained 5 mM ammonium formiate and were composed of water/formic acid 99:1 (v/v; eluent A) and methanol/formic acid 99:1 (v/v; eluent B). The flow rate was 0.300 ml/min. The gradient programme started with 70% A and 30% B, reaching 100% B after 3 min (holding time, 5 min). Finally, gradient switched back to 70% A and 30% B after 2 min (holding time, 2 min).

MS/MS was performed in the selected reaction-monitoring (SRM) and the positive ion electrospray mode (ESI+). The source ionisation parameters used were: cone voltage 40 V, capillary voltage 3.80 kV, source temperature 350 °C, desolvation temperature 270 °C, curtain gas 20 psi, ion source gas 1 (sheath gas) 50 psi, ion source gas 2 (drying gas) 55 psi, ion spray voltage 5500 V and collision energy 15 eV.

IV. Results

1. Analysis of the core genes of the aphid circadian clock

1.1. Characterisation of gene transcripts

Transcript sequences of the core genes of the putative pea aphid circadian clock were identified and preliminary characterised in previous studies (Cortés, 2010; Cortés et al., 2010; see section I.2.1). However, the characterisation of some gene transcripts was not complete and the presence of alternative splicing was not investigated. In the present thesis, the experimental characterisation of these genes has been extended and the gene models have been updated and compared to predicted genes from the recently sequenced genome of the aphid *Myzus persicae*. Sequence characterisation included the determination of the complete CDS and a search for regulatory elements in the upstream regions. Additionally, the transcripts of the genes at the core of the circadian clock were screened for splicing variants in aphids of the holocyclic (YR2) and the anholocyclic (GR) strains reared under summer, long day (LD, 16L:8D) and winter, short day (SD, 12L:12D) photoperiods (see section III.1). Despite the presence of several splicing variants (see below), no strain-specific nor photoperiod-specific variants could be identified. The relevance of the detected alternative splicing was also investigated in reference to the coding of conserved domains. The most relevant transcripts that have been obtained experimentally have been deposited at NCBI database with corresponding accession numbers (IX.2 in ANNEXES).

Gene *period*

The complete CDS of the aphid gene homologous to the *Drosophila* gene *period* (*per*) previously described was amplified by PCR obtaining sequences that, after alignment with the aphid genome corresponded to a total of 25 exons and three splicing variants (Figure IV.1). The splicing variant *per-A* was the most abundant, as judged from band intensity on electrophoresis gels, and its sequence coincided with the previously described transcript. The variant *per-B* included the in-frame extra exon 4 upstream the conserved PAS A domain that extended the protein 56 amino acids keeping the ORF (Open Reading Frame). A third splicing variant named *per-C*, included the alternative exon 4 described above and the upstream adjacent intronic region, which introduced a stop codon thus yielding a truncated protein prediction. Nonetheless, this *per-C* transcript included a Met codon in the unspliced intron that could still work as an alternative start codon, yielding a protein that would include the PAS A domain (see Figure IV.1 A and B).

Figure IV.1. Next page. Schematic representation of the structure of the *A. pisum* gene *period*. **A)** Splicing variants deduced from alignments of our experimentally obtained transcript sequences with the aphid genome sequence. Putative initial methionines are indicated by Met and stop codons by STOP. Putative coding DNA sequences (CDS) are shown in grey. Exon numbers are indicated below the *per-A* splicing variant. **B)** Diagram representing the PER aphid protein. The protein region affected by alternative splicing of exon 4 is indicated by a horizontal line. Conserved domains are shown in white boxes; P represents conserved phosphorylation sites; conserved bipartite nuclear localisation signal is indicated by NLS; red horizontal lines indicate TIM interaction domains. **C)** Schematic diagram of the upstream genomic region of the aphid gene *period* showing relevant putative regulatory elements in *A. pisum* and *M. persicae*. E-boxes are represented by yellow bars and V/P-boxes by magenta bars. Assembly gaps are indicated with white boxes and exons with white and grey boxes.

A

B

C

The sequence of the gene and the structure of its hypothetical splicing variants were conserved in the *Myzus persicae per* homologue (see *period* model in ANNEXES).

Gene *timeless*

In a previous work, the transcript of the gene homologous to the *Drosophila* gene *timeless* (*tim*) could not be fully characterised (Cortés et al., 2010). In the present work, previously missed regions at the N-terminal and C-terminal ends were experimentally obtained, thus completing its CDS (Figure IV.2). The aphid *tim* transcript consisted, including the CDS and UTRs (untranslated regions), of 18 exons that were found in the pea aphid genome database distributed in three different scaffolds. The first exon that contain only UTR was found in scaffold GL349835 but was not annotated in the database. The exons comprising the CDS (exons 2 to 17) were located in scaffold GL349627 and were annotated as ACYPI36439. The last two exons –exon 17 that was the last coding exon and it was found in two different scaffolds, and exon 18 containing UTR sequence– were

Figure IV.2. Next page. Schematic representation of the structure of the *A. pisum* gene *timeless*. **A)** Splicing variants deduced from alignments of our experimentally obtained transcript sequences with the aphid genome sequence. Putative initial methionines are indicated by Met and stop codons by STOP. Putative coding DNA sequences (CDS) are shown in grey. Exon numbers are indicated below the *tim-A* splicing variant. **B)** Diagram representing the TIM aphid protein. Position of alternative exons are indicated by horizontal lines. Conserved domains are shown in white boxes; conserved nuclear localisation signals are indicated by NLS; red horizontal lines indicate PER interaction domains. **C)** Schematic diagram of the upstream genomic region of aphid gene *timeless* showing relevant putative regulatory elements in *A. pisum* and *M. persicae*. E-boxes are represented by yellow bars and V/P-boxes by magenta bars. Assembly gaps are indicated with white boxes and exons with white and grey boxes.

found in scaffold GL350105 without any annotation. A total of five splicing variants were experimentally obtained (see Figure IV.2 A), being variants *tim-B* and *tim-A* the most abundant as judged by the intensity of the PCR-amplified bands. It is noteworthy that the proteins predicted from transcripts *tim-A* and *tim-B* only differed in the presence of exon 11 in the latter that contained the NLS (nuclear localisation signal) but maintains the ORF. Some splicing variants contained a newly identified exon 6 that introduced a stop codon in the next exon (see Figure IV.2 A). The complete CDS was found in a single scaffold of the *M. persicae* genome (see *timeless* model in ANNEXES). *M. persicae tim* gene sequence and predicted structure was generally conserved with respect to that of *A. pisum*, except that a sequence equivalent to *A. pisum* exon 6 was not found in *M. persicae*.

Gene Clock

The amplification of the CDS of the aphid gene homologue to the *Drosophila* gene *Clock* (*Clk*) resulted in a sequence that could be arranged in 14 exons and five transcript variants (Figure IV.3). The most common splicing variants were *Clk-A*, *Clk-B* and *Clk-D* (see Figure IV.3 A). The variant

Figure IV.3. Next page. Schematic representation of the structure of the *A. pisum* gene *Clock*. **A)** Splicing variants deduced from alignments of our experimentally obtained transcript sequences with the aphid genome sequence. Putative initial methionines are indicated by Met and stop codons by STOP. Putative coding DNA sequences (CDS) are shown in grey. Exon numbers are indicated below the *Clk-A* splicing variant. **B)** Diagram representing the CLK aphid protein. Position of alternative exons are indicated by horizontal lines. Conserved domains are shown in white boxes, conserved nuclear localisation (NLS) and export (NES) signals are indicated in red and green, respectively. **C)** Schematic diagram of the upstream genomic region of aphid gene *Clock* showing relevant putative regulatory elements in *A. pisum* and *M. persicae*. V/P-boxes are represented by magenta bars. Exons are indicated with white and grey boxes.

Clk-A encoded the transcript with the conserved regions previously described by Cortés et al. (2010). The variant *Clk-B* included an intronic sequence that introduced a stop codon at the end of exon 2. However, the presence of a putative alternative initial methionine could still initiate translation downstream preserving the conserved domains, including the bHLH (basic helix-loop-helix). The variant *Clk-D* differs from *Clk-A* in that the region encoded by exon 11 is absent, although this did not interrupt the ORF. An orthologue of *Clk* was identified in *M. persicae* (see *Clock* model in ANNEXES), in which the alternative splicing of exon 11 seems to be conserved, i.e. the presence or absence of exon 11 did not interrupt the ORF either. Since no conserved domains were identified in exon 11, no putative functionality could be associated to alternative splicing of *Clk-D* (see Figure IV.3 B).

Gene cycle

The amplification of aphid transcripts homologous to the *Drosophila* gene *cycle* (*cyc*) revealed six splicing variants (Figure IV.4). Variants *cyc-A*, *cyc-B*

Figure IV.4. Next page. Schematic representation of the structure of the *A. pisum* gene *cycle*. **A)** Splicing variants deduced from alignments of our experimentally obtained transcript sequences with the aphid genome sequence. Putative initial methionines are indicated by Met and stop codons by STOP. Putative coding DNA sequences (CDS) are shown in grey. Exon numbers are indicated below the *Cyc-A* splicing variant. **B)** Diagram representing the CYC aphid protein. Position of alternative exons are indicated by horizontal lines. Conserved domains are shown in white boxes; conserved nuclear localisation (NLS) and export (NES) signals are indicated in red and green, respectively. **C)** Schematic diagram of the upstream genomic region of aphid gene *cycle* showing relevant putative regulatory elements in *A. pisum* and *M. persicae*. E-boxes are represented by yellow bars and V/P-boxes by magenta bars. Exons are indicated with white and grey boxes.

A

B

C

and *cyc-C* were the most abundant as judged from PCR experiments. Of these, the main splicing variant was *cyc-A*, that corresponded to the previously described transcript (Cortés et al., 2010). The protein encoded by variant *cyc-B* was similar to *cyc-A* except for an extra 31 amino acids region encoded by the alternative exon 4, although no conserved domains were found within that region. The transcript variant *cyc-C* lacked exons 3 to 8 which resulted in a stop codon in exon 9 and putatively produced a truncated protein. However, the use of an alternative Met at the end of exon 9 would still produce a protein lacking the conserved domains bHLH, the NLS, the NES (Nuclear Export Signal) and most of the PAS A (see Figure IV.4 A and B; see also *cycle* model in ANNEXES). The search and analysis of the *M. persicae* orthologous *cycle* in showed that the structure of exons was conserved among both aphid species (see *cycle* model in ANNEXES).

Gene *PAR-domain protein 1*

The aphid homologue of the *Drosophila* gene *PAR-domain protein 1* (*Pdp1*) was amplified yielding two transcript variants (Figure IV.5) that coincided

Figure IV.5. Next page. Schematic representation of the structure of the *A. pisum* gene *Pdp1*. **A)** Splicing variants deduced from alignments of our experimentally obtained transcript sequences with the aphid genome sequence. Putative initial methionines are indicated by Met and stop codons by STOP. Putative coding DNA sequences (CDS) are shown in grey. Exon numbers are indicated below the *Pdp1-A* splicing variant. **B)** Diagram representing the PDP1 aphid protein. Conserved domains are shown in white boxes; not conserved A-rich domain(A) is shown apart; conserved extended (E) motif VKKSRKQ is represented in blue; conserved DNA binding domain (DB) is indicated in yellow. **C)** Schematic diagram of the genomic regions flanking exon 1 of aphid gene *Pdp1* showing relevant putative regulatory elements in *A. pisum* and *M. persicae*. E-boxes are represented by yellow bars and V/P-boxes by magenta bars. Exons are indicated with white and grey boxes.

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A

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with those previously described (Cortés et al., 2010). Both variants encoded the same protein, except that Pdp1-B lacked 21 bp encoding the heptapeptide motif VKKSRKQ at the end of exon 4 (see *Pdp1* model in ANNEXES). Conservation of the Q-rich domain present in Diptera and Hymenoptera seems to be low in the aphid PDP1 protein, and the A-rich domain specific of *Drosophila* seems to be absent.

As seen with previously described genes, no evident correlation was found between a particular transcript variant and a particular strain or photoperiodic condition. A search in the *M. persicae* genome revealed the presence of an orthologous *Pdp1* gene, which included a region of 21 nt with the two donor sites conserved with the homologous region in the *A. pisum* gene. This suggests that the splicing variants differing in the heptapeptide motif mentioned above would also be present in *M. persicae* (see *Pdp1* model in ANNEXES).

Gene *vri*

The amplification of the aphid homologue to the *Drosophila* gene *vri* (*vri*) produced two new splicing variants (Figure IV.6) in addition to that already

Figure IV.6. Next page. Schematic representation of the structure of the *A. pisum* gene *vri*. **A)** Splicing variants deduced from alignments of our experimentally obtained transcript sequences with the aphid genome sequence. Putative initial methionines are indicated by Met and stop codons by STOP. Putative coding DNA sequences (CDS) are shown in grey. Exon numbers are indicated below the *vri-A* splicing variant. **B)** Diagram representing the VRI aphid protein. Conserved domains are shown in white boxes; conserved DNA binding domain (DB) is indicated in yellow. **C)** Schematic diagram of the region flanking exon 1 of aphid gene *vri* showing relevant putative regulatory elements in *A. pisum* and *M. persicae*. E-boxes are represented by yellow bars and V/P-boxes by magenta bars. Exons are indicated in white boxes.

A

C

described by Cortés et al. (2010). The new splicing variants differ from the previously sequenced transcript in that both contain a shorter exon 3 and lack exon 4 (see Figure IV.6 A). The two newly described transcript variants use different donor sites at the end of exon 3 and different acceptor sites on exon 5 which at the end, keep the same ORF in the latter exon. Thus the variant *vri-A* contains an extra peptide that corresponds to the 5' region of exon 5 (see Figure IV.6 A; see also *vri* model in ANNEXES). The variability in the C terminal region did not affect the conserved domains described for this gene (see Figure IV.6 B). Interestingly, in the newly described transcript variants, the acceptor and donor sites between exons 3 and 5 did not fit a canonical splicing structure. However, since the genomic sequence of strain LSR1 was used to align our experimentally obtained transcripts derived from YR2 and GR strains, differences in genomic sequences between strains could explain the apparent lack of a putative canonical acceptor in the new variants. Regarding the conservation of domains at the amino acid level, the new models contain the already described BRLZ and G/S domains described for *Drosophila* (Cyran et al., 2003). The putative aphid VRI would also contain two Q-rich domains that could be specific of aphids (see Figure IV.6 B).

Regulatory elements

For the different clock genes, the genomic region upstream the putative initial methionine was screened for elements described to be relevant in circadian regulation in other organisms (see section I.2.1), including E-boxes and V/P-boxes (IV.1). The number and precise location of these regulatory elements in the genomic regions can be visualised in the corresponding gene models included in ANNEXES.

Table IV.1. Putative regulatory elements found in the genomic regions adjacent to clock genes in *A. pisum* and *M. persicae*.*Acyrtosiphon pisum*

Gene	Accession Number	Scaffold	Region Searched (nt)	n° E-box		n° V/P box	
				canonical ¹	non canonical ²	canonical ³	non canonical ⁴
<i>Per</i>	ACYPI47669	GL349744	8368	4	13	0	8
<i>Tim</i>	ACYPI36439	GL349627	9131	2	22	1	11
<i>Tim</i>	not annotated	GL349835	11900	2	23	2	3
<i>Clk</i>	ACYPI004812	GL350374	9541	0	24	3	5
<i>Cyc</i>	ACYPI004686	GL350506	10160	1	21	2+4	1
<i>Pdp1</i>	ACYPI004812	GL350600	10951	2+3	33	0	7
<i>Vri</i>	ACYPI008851	GL350315	10939	2+3	18	2+1	5
<i>AANAT1</i>	ACYPI002543	GL349852	10024	1	21	2	186
<i>AANAT2</i>	ACYPI000655	GL349852	6089	1	12	0	105
<i>AANAT3</i>	ACYPI000856	GL350487	13229	2	30	3	9
<i>AANAT4</i>	ACYPI060713	GL349956	10879	0	22	0	9

Myzus persicae

Gene	Accession Number (MYZPE13164_0_v1)	Scaffold	Region Searched (nt)	n° E-box		n° V/P box	
				canonical ¹	non canonical ²	canonical ³	non canonical ⁴
<i>Per</i>	000089220	Scaffold_306	10046	4	30	1	12
<i>Tim</i>	000088930	Scaffold_305	10048	3	25	4	8
<i>Clk</i>	000050320	Scaffold_175	10001	0	27	0	5
<i>Cyc</i>	000093520	Scaffold_323	10142	0	26	3+3	7
<i>Pdp1</i>	000172150	Scaffold_748	10305	2+3	26	1	10
<i>Vri</i>	000035260	Scaffold_1409	10213	2+3	32	0+1	7
<i>AANAT1</i>	000100170	scaffold_348	100001	2	29	0	7
<i>AANAT2</i>	000100180	scaffold_348	7670	0	20	0	4
<i>AANAT3</i>	000044650	scaffold_1603	10001	2	22	1	175
<i>AANAT4</i>	000065500	scaffold_215	8908	2	21	1	4

1 canonical E-box CACGTG
2 non canonical E-box CANNTG
3 canonical V/P box TTATGTAA
4 non canonical V/P-box RTTWYRWAAY

The genomic regions upstream of *per* exons in *A. pisum* revealed a group of four canonical E-boxes, distributed in two pairs that were located approximately 5.4 kb upstream the initial methionine (see Figure IV.1 C). The number of E-boxes, their distribution and their relative distance to the first exon in *M. persicae* gene *per* was highly conserved (see Figure IV.1 C).

With respect to the *A. pisum* gene *tim*, given that the CDS was located in the scaffold GL349627 but exon 1 was located in another scaffold (GL349825), two genomic regions were screened for regulatory elements (see Figure IV.2 C). A sequence homologous to *A. pisum* exon 1 could not be found in *M. persicae*, therefore its genomic region was compared to the *A. pisum* scaffold GL349627. Although the three genomic regions that contained fragments of gene *tim* included E-box and V/P-box elements (see Figure IV.2 C), the number and position were not conserved between the two aphid species (see IV.1 and *timeless* gene model in ANNEXES). The upstream genomic region of the *A. pisum* gene *Clk* contained three V/P-boxes and an assembly gap (see Figure IV.3 C). Comparison with *M. persicae* gene *Clk* showed no conservation of these putative regulatory elements between aphid species (see Figure IV.3 C). The search in upstream regions of *A. pisum* and *M. persicae* *cyc* genes revealed V/P-boxes in both species and one E-box in *A. pisum* (see Figure IV.4 C). Furthermore, the presence of V/P-boxes in the intronic region downstream of exon 1 of *cyc* was particularly conserved between *A. pisum* and *M. persicae* (see Figure IV.4 C). The search for regulatory elements in the *Pdp1* gene included genomic regions upstream and downstream exon 1 (see Figure IV.5 C). It was noteworthy the finding of two E-box elements upstream and three E-boxes in the intron between exons 1 and 2 conserved in number and distribution in both aphid species. Additionally, a V/P-box was found only in the *M. persicae* upstream region (see Figure IV.5 C). The search of regulatory elements in *vri* revealed two E-boxes upstream exon 1 and three E-boxes in the intron between exons 1 and 2 (see Figure IV.6 C). Even though the number of E-boxes was conserved between *A. pisum* and *M. persicae*, its distribution along the genomic sequence differed.

1.2. Quantification of expression of aphid clock genes

The expression profiles of genes at the core of the aphid circadian clock were studied in two different RT-qPCR experiments.

Experiment 1: testing factors affecting clock gene expression in the pea aphid

The first experiment was designed to test whether the expression of core clock genes was affected by different factors. First, to test for circadian rhythmicity aphids were sampled every six hours for a total of 36 h, including ZT3, ZT9, ZT15, ZT21, ZT27 and ZT33. Second, in order to reveal a possible involvement of these genes in the seasonal response, aphids sampled in two alternative photoperiods were analysed (Figure IV.7). One group of aphids was reared under LD (Long Day, 16L:8D) conditions in which aphids continuously reproduce parthenogenetically. After reaching adulthood, aphids grown in LD (Figure IV.7) were sampled at the 6 time points mentioned above. A separate group of aphids were sampled as before, except that it consisted of the second generation of aphids reared in SD (Short Day, 12L:12D) (Figure IV.7). In order to investigate whether the expression of these genes could have a role in determining the life-cycle displayed by aphids, their expression was analysed in two different aphid strains: the holocyclic YR2 strain, and the anholocyclic GR strain (see sections I.1.3 and III.1).

Visual inspection of expression profiles (see Figure IV.7) allowed to identify a similar pattern of expression of genes *per* and *tim* that clearly differed between LD and SD aphids of the YR2 strain. However, although both

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genes also exhibited similar profiles in the GR strain, no differences were observed between aphids reared under LD and SD photoperiods for gene *per* and only minor differences for gene *tim* (see Figure IV.7). Indeed, the resemblance in expression profiles of genes *per* and *tim* of aphids reproducing by parthenogenesis (i.e. YR2 aphids reared in LD and aphids of GR strain reared under both photoperiods) was closer than that of aphids in which the seasonal response was active (i.e. YR2 aphids reared in SD). It is worth to mention a statistically significant peak of expression of both *per* and *tim* observed at ZT15 in YR2 aphids reared in LD. In YR2 aphids reared in SD, a statistically significant *per*-specific peak of expression at ZT21 and a *tim*-specific peak of expression at ZT9 were identified that were absent in aphids of the other photoperiods and strains. None of the aphids of both strains reared in any of the two photoperiods showed significant differences in the expression of genes *Clk* or *cyc* between ZTs. *Pdp1* expression was analysed using three different sets of primers that allowed quantification of the two alternative transcripts (see section IV.1.1) and a region common to both of them. Despite that statistically significant differences in the expression of *Pdp1* were observed between ZTs in YR2 aphids reared in LD, these were not as high as those described for *per* and

Figure IV.7. Previous page. Expression profiles of the circadian clock core genes obtained for aphids of the holocyclic strain YR2 (left) and aphids of the anholocyclic strain GR (right). The expression results from aphids reared under LD (Long Day, 16L:8D) are represented by black circles and those of SD (Short Day, 12L:12D) by black triangles. The mean relative expression of three replicates \pm SEM are plotted at 6 h intervals over 1.5 days. Significant differences in expression at different time points are indicated in bold and italic letters for LD and SD photoperiods, respectively. The dark phase of the photoperiods is indicated as grey background ranging from ZT12 to ZT24 in SD and ZT16 to ZT24 in LD. The red curves represent the circadian rhythm estimated by the COSINOR software for those genes showing a significant circadian rhythm (see IV.2).

Figure IV.8. Comparison of levels of expression of the circadian clock core genes between aphid strains and rearing photoperiods. Bars represent the mean relative expression calculated for all ZT within a strain and photoperiod \pm SEM. Letters on top of each bar represent the subgroup significance (p -value < 0.05) of the ANOVA test comparing the variable photoperiod for each gene.

tim. A peak of expression of *vri* was observed at ZT9 in YR2 aphids reared both in LD and SD that was absent in GR. Furthermore, a statistically significant opposite regulation of *vri* expression at ZT21, in which expression increased in LD while decreased in SD, was specific to YR2 aphids (see Figure IV.7). In general, expression of core clock genes was

Table IV.2. Parameter details defining the rhythmic expression of the genes that revealed a significant rhythmicity after a COSINOR analysis in Experiment 1 (see text for details).

Gene	Strain	Photoperiod	P-value	Robustness (%)	MESOR	Amplitude	Acrophase (° / ZT)
<i>period</i>	YR2	LD	0.047433	73.3	1.4512	0.5586	204 / 13.6
<i>timeless</i>	YR2	LD	0.006019	93	2.18	0.9303	198 / 13.2

higher at any ZT in SD photoperiod in the strain YR2, except for *vri* and the *Pdp1* extended variant (*Pdp1-A*). On the other hand, only *Pdp1* and *vri* expression profiles showed higher expression in SD for the GR strain.

Circadian rhythmicity in the expression of clock core genes was tested with the COSINOR method (Refinetti et al., 2007; Cornelissen, 2014). The results of COSINOR tests (see “Summary_cosinor_core” in ANNEXES) are summarised in IV.2. Significant circadian rhythms in expression of *per* and *tim* were found in YR2 aphids reared in LD. Moreover, in both cases the peak of expression (acrophase) occurred at the end of the photophase (ca. ZT13). It is worth to note the case of *per* and *tim* expression profile for aphids of the GR strain reared in LD and SD, that being not significantly rhythmic, still conserved the same pattern as YR2 aphids reared in LD.

When mean expression levels were compared between aphids of both strains reared under different photoperiods (Figure IV.8), the four genes involved in the negative feedback loop of the circadian clock (*per*, *tim*, *Clk* and *cyc*; see Figure I.10) showed significant higher expression in aphids of the holocyclic YR2 strain reared under SD than in aphids reared under LD. Contrarily, expression of these genes remained constant between both photoperiods studied in anholocyclic GR aphids. Of the two genes included in the second, positive feedback loop of the aphid circadian clock (see

Figure I.10), *Pdp1* showed higher expression in SD aphids in both strains, while *vri* only expressed differently in the GR strain (see Figure IV.8).

Experiment 2: self-sustainability of the aphid circadian clock

The results of the experiment 1 prompted us to perform an additional RT-qPCR experiment in order to confirm the self-sustainability of the rhythmicity detected for genes *per* and *tim* (see section I.2.1), as well as to check the reproducibility of the previous results (see **Experiment 1** above). In this second experiment, two groups of YR2 aphids were reared under LD (Long Day, 16L:8D) photoperiod. After the final moult, the first group was kept under LD conditions. The second group of aphids was transferred to DD (constant darkness, 0L:24D) conditions immediately after the final moult. In both groups, aphids were sampled every 6 h over three complete cycles (Figure IV.9). The repetitive sampling of four time points (ZT3, ZT9, ZT15 and ZT21) over three successive cycles facilitated the visual identification of rhythmic patterns. The comparison of expression between ZTs revealed significant differences in all genes and photoperiods (see “Exp2_ANOVA_ZTs” in ANNEXES). As can be seen in Figure IV.9, both *per* and *tim* showed a peak of expression at the end of photophase (ZT15) followed by a sharp decrease to minimum expression at the end of the scotophase (ZT21). This pattern was consistent throughout the whole sampling period, but was more evident the second and third days. The expression profiles of *Clk* and *cyc* did not show a clear rhythm, nevertheless the expression reached maximum levels at ZT15 and gradually decreased at ZT21 and ZT3, finally reaching a plateau during the mid photophase (see Figure IV.9). Notably, the expression profile of *Pdp1* was very similar to that of *cyc* and almost exactly matched that of *Clk*. A particular expression

Figure IV.9. Expression profiles of the circadian clock core genes along three days (Experiment 2). Mean relative expression values of three replicates \pm SEM are plotted at 6 h intervals over three days. The dark phase of the photoperiods are represented as grey background. The dark phase of LD (16L:8D) ranges from ZT16 to ZT24 plus replicates at day 2 (+24 h) and day 3 (+48 h). The DD photoperiod (0L:24D) was represented as a grey background and the LD photoperiod previously experienced by aphids was added to facilitate comparison. Significant differences in expression at different time points were not included for the sake of clarity, but can be consulted in “Exp2_ANOVA_ZTs” in ANNEXES. The red curves represent the circadian rhythm estimated by the COSINOR software for those genes with a significant ($p < 0,05$) circadian rhythm (see IV.3).

pattern was seen in *vri*, which was the only gene showing a peak at ZT21 while its expression remained low during the day.

Concerning the expression profiles of *per* and *tim* in DD (see Figure IV.9), it was evident that the rhythm became very dampened with heavily diminished amplitude. Nonetheless, the expression pattern was still similar to that seen in LD, showing a peak of expression at the end of the photophase and a trough at the end of scotophase during the first cycle in DD, that was lost in the subsequent second and third cycles.

Gene expression in this second experiment was also tested for circadian rhythmicity through COSINOR tests, whose results are summarised in IV.3. The analysis showed a robust rhythm of *per* and *tim* expression in YR2 aphids reared in LD (see Figure IV.9 and IV.3). The expression of the rest of the clock genes, *Clk*, *cyc*, *Pdp1* and *vri*, did not show a significant rhythm. On the other hand, the analysis of *per* and *tim* expression in DD did not show a significant rhythm in either of these genes. Nevertheless, the expression pattern of *per* and *tim* during the first day of DD were similar to those seen in LD (see Figure IV.9). Application of the COSINOR test to ZTs of the first day in DD allowed to identify a significant rhythm for *tim* with a peak of expression similar to that of LD, but with an amplitude an order of magnitude lower (see IV.3). Comparison of general expression levels of *per*

Table IV.3. Summary of results of COSINOR analysis from Experiment 2 (see text for details). Gene expression profiles of strains and photoperiods with significant 24 h period include the parameters of the rhythm.

Gene	Strain	Photo Period	period (h)	P-value	Robustness (%)	MESOR	Amplitude	Acrophase (° / ZT)
<i>period</i>	YR2	LD	24.6	0.007912	53.7	1.57	0.9231	175 / 16.67
	YR2	DD	34.0	0.276605	0			
	YR2	DD (5ZTs)	15.0	0.093156	76.8			
<i>timeless</i>	YR2	LD	24.5	0.016805	45.4	1.54	0.916	188 / 12.53
	YR2	DD	15.0	0.518110	0			
	YR2	DD (5ZTs)	21.7	0.002068	99.3	0.14	0.0501	204 / 13.60

and *tim* between LD and DD photoperiods showed that it was an order of magnitude lower in DD respect to LD (see Figure IV.9).

1.3. Localisation of transcripts of the aphid clock core genes

In situ localisation of the transcripts encoded by the circadian clock genes *per* and *tim* in the central nervous system (CNS), including the brain, the suboesophageal ganglion (SOG) and the thoracic ganglionic mass (TGM) of *Acyrtosiphon pisum*, was studied using DIG-labelled RNA probes that were detected with alkaline phosphatase (AP) conjugated anti-DIG antibodies. Two different substrates of AP were used. In a first approach, transcripts were detected with NBT/BCIP that produce a blue/purple precipitate. In a second approach, the HNPP/Fast Red TR substrates which produce a red chromogenic, but also fluorescent precipitate, were used (see section III.3.4).

Localisation of *period* transcripts

The antisense probe against the aphid *per* homologue successfully located its transcripts in CNSs obtained from adult aphids (Figure IV.10). The specificity of the probe was confirmed by the lack of signal in the hybridisations carried out without probe (see Figure IV.10 A) or using the *per* sense probe (see Figure IV.10 B), apart from the typical tracheal background staining. *Per* transcripts were only detected in the aphid brain (see Figure IV.10 C). Particularly, *per* expression was routinely located in three cell clusters that were named dorsal neurons (DN), lateral neurons (LN) and lamina neurons (LaN) respectively (see Figure IV.10 C), following

the nomenclature used in other insects originally adopted from *Drosophila melanogaster* (Helfrich-Förster, 2002). The DNs expressing *per* were located in the most anterior, dorsal region of each brain hemisphere, also known as *pars lateralis* (see Figure IV.10 C and D, see also Figure I.4), within the deeper layers of the protocerebral soma cortex, which are closer to the underlying neuropil. *Per* transcript detection in whole mount preparations did not allow to clearly distinguish the number of cells in the DN cluster, although it seemed to consist of six to ten neurons with small soma (see Figure IV.10 D and “per1_60x” image stack in ANNEXES). The LN cluster was located in the boundary between the optic lobe and the *protocerebrum* (see Figure IV.10 C and E), within or near the dorsal anterior region described as lobula (see Kollmann et al. (2011) and Figure I.4). Generally, the LN group consisted of four neurons found anteriorly in the cortex surrounding the lobula. A detailed inspection of these neurons revealed that the LN cluster could be subdivided in two groups designated vLN (ventral lateral neurons) and dLN (dorsal lateral neurons). The vLN consisted of three cells located in the lower layers of the soma cortex, right near the underlying

Figure IV.10. Next page. *In situ* localisation of *per* transcripts in brains of adult (A-E) and L3 (F) individuals of *A. pisum*. A, B and F show *in situ* hybridisations revealed with NBT/BCIP substrate. C-E show *in situ* hybridisations revealed with Fast Red/HNPP substrate. The fluorescent Fast Red precipitate is shown in red and the nucleus stained with DAPI are shown in blue. **A)** Control hybridisation with no probe. **B)** Control hybridisation with *per* sense probe. **C)** Z-stack confocal image overview of the localisation of *per* transcripts in the aphid brain showing the three cell clusters expressing *per*. **D)** Z-stack confocal image of the most dorsal slices showing a detail of the DN localisation. **E)** Z-stack confocal image of the medial slices showing a detail of dLN (left) and the vLN (middle) and merge (right). **F)** *per* transcript *in situ* localisation of L3 aphids showing the main *per* expressing cell clusters. DN (dorsal neurons), LN (lateral neurons), LaN (lamina neurons), dLN (dorsal LN), vLN (ventral LN). Scale bars = 50 µm.

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protocerebrum neuropil (see Figure IV.10 E and “per1_60x” image stack in ANNEXES). The single dLN was found in intermediate layers of the soma cortex, in a region located dorsally and distally respect to the vLN (see Figure IV.10 E and “per1_60x” image stack in ANNEXES). The third group of neurons expressing *per* was found in the lamina of the optic lobe (see section I.1.2), the most outer region of the optic lobe, thereby named LaN. A maximum of four cells expressing *per* were found in the posterior region of the lamina (see Figure IV.10 C, see also “per1” image stack in ANNEXES). Finally, in some preparations, other neurons expressing *per* were occasionally found scattered in the dorsal region posterior to the DN cluster (see Figure IV.10 C and D). However, the staining and appearance of these scattered neurons were less consistent than the previously described clusters.

As a first approach to study possible changes in the distribution of *per* expression along the aphid development, localisation of *per* transcripts was also carried out in CNSs of L3 aphids (i.e. third larval stage individuals) of the YR2 and GR strains reared under LD conditions (16L:8D). In L3 aphids, the *per* expressing neurons displayed an arrangement similar to that of the adults described above (see Figure IV.10 F). Irrespective of the strain, a group of neurons in the *pars lateralis* that corresponded to the DN cluster described above was observed. Another group of *per* expressing neurons was found in the region between the *protocerebrum* and the optic lobe that corresponded to the LN (see Figure IV.10 F). The exact number of cells in the DN group could not be clearly identified with the chromogenic blue/purple staining imaged with light microscopy (see section III.3.4). Moreover, as can be seen in consecutive image sections (see Figure IV.10 F), the relative position of the single dLN and few (two or three) vLN was

conserved between L3 and adult aphids. Although in some cases a faint signal could be identified in the posterior lamina of the optic lobe, the signal could not be undoubtedly associated to a cluster of neurons expressing *per* and thus, differently from adult aphids, *per* seemed not to be expressed in the LaN in the third larval stage.

Once the expression of *per* in the aphid brain had been localised, we investigated whether there were changes in the patterns of expression associated to the type of life cycle developed, the experienced photoperiod or the moment along the day/night cycle. In an independent experiment, the localisation of *per* transcripts was compared between adults of the YR2 (holocyclic) and GR (anholocyclic) strains. To investigate whether the photoperiod affected the pattern of *per* expression, aphids reared under LD (16L:8D) and SD (12L:12:D) photoperiodic conditions were analysed. In addition, aphids sampled at two different moments of the day (ZT6 and ZT18) were also compared. The results shown in Figure IV.11 include representative preparations of *per* localisation in aphid CNSs obtained for the different treatments. In reference to the groups of *per* expressing neurons described above (i.e. DN, LN and LaN), none of the preparations revealed new clusters of *per* expressing cells. Focusing on aphids reared under LD conditions (see Figure IV.11), it could be noted that at ZT6 aphids from both YR2 and GR strains showed *per* expression in DNs but none or very low expression in LNs. However, at ZT18 expression of *per* in DNs and LNs was very low in YR2, while in GR there was no detectable expression. With respect to CNSs obtained from aphids reared under SD (see Figure IV.11), *per* expression at ZT6 was located in both DNs and LNs in both strains. In this case, at ZT18 there was no detectable *per* expression for any of the strains (see Figure IV.11). In summary, only the YR2 strain

Figure IV.11. *In situ* localisation of *per* transcripts in brains from adult *A. pisum* detected with DIG-labelled probes and revealed with NBT/BCIP substrate. Images of brains from aphids of the YR2 and GR strains are shown on the left and right columns, respectively. The four upper images correspond to aphids reared under LD (Long Day, 16L:8D) and the four lower images correspond to G1 aphids reared under SD (Short Day, 12L:12D) conditions. For each strain and photoperiod aphids fixed at ZT6 showed *per* expression at ZT18 under LD conditions. With respect to the *per* expressing neurons previously described as LaN (see above), they were

showed *per* expression at ZT18 under LD conditions. With respect to the *per* expressing neurons previously described as LaN (see above), they were only detected at ZT18 in YR2 aphids reared under LD conditions (not shown in Figure IV.11).

Localisation of *timeless* transcripts

In addition to the localisation of *per*, localisation of *tim* transcripts in the CNS of *Acyrtosiphon pisum* was also investigated using the corresponding antisense probe. The main results of *tim* transcript localisation can be found summarised in Figure IV.12 (see also “tim4” and “tim4_60x” image stacks in ANNEXES). The specificity of the staining was confirmed by the absence of signal in brains hybridised with the sense probe (see Figure IV.12 A), apart from the unspecific staining routinely seen in the *trachea*, as also seen for the *per* sense probe (see above). Detectable levels of *tim* expression were found exclusively in the brain (see Figure IV.12), coinciding with some of the regions previously described for *per in situ* hybridisation (see Figure IV.10). Therefore, the nomenclature used to describe the neurons expressing *tim* followed that used for *per* (see previous section). Two groups of neurons were found to express *tim* transcripts (see Figure IV.12 B) that were designated dorsal neurons (DNs) and lateral neurons (LNs). The DNs expressing *tim* were found in the antero-dorsal region of the *protocerebrum* known as *pars lateralis* (see Figure IV.12 B and C). This group consisted of two distinguishable types of cells: a subgroup consisting of two clearly defined neurons with large soma, expressing high levels of *tim*, named large DN (l-DN), and another subgroup of six to eight cells with small soma and lower *tim* expression adjacent to the l-DN that were named small DN (s-DN) (see Figure IV.12 C). The LN cluster of *tim* expressing

Figure IV.12. *In situ* localisation of *tim* transcripts in brains of adult *A. pisum* aphids. **A)** Control hybridisation with *tim* sense probe. **B)** Z-stack confocal image showing an overview of the localisation of *tim* transcripts in the aphid brain including the DN and the LN. **C)** Z-stack confocal image of the dorsal region showing the two subgroups of DN: the l-DN and the s-DN. **D)** Detail of the image stack shown in B indicating the distribution of dLN in red (left) and the vLN in yellow (middle). A merge (right) is included for comparative purposes. DN (dorsal neurons), LN (lateral neurons), dLN (dorsal LN), vLN (ventral LN). DAPI nuclear stain is shown in blue in images B neurons was located in the region between the *protocerebrum* and the

neurons was located in the region between the *protocerebrum* and the optic lobe (see Figure IV.12 B and D). In this case, *tim* staining also revealed two subgroups of LN in a pattern similar to that described for *per* expression (see above). The first subgroup consisted of a single *tim* LN located dorsally and slightly lateral respect to the rest of the LN cluster that was named dorsal lateral neuron (dLN) (see Figure IV.12 D and E). The rest of the LN expressing *tim*, usually three to four neurons, were found ventro-medially with respect to the dLN and were named ventral lateral neurons (vLN) (see Figure IV.12 D). Contrarily to *per* localisation, no detectable expression of *tim* was found in the LaN nor was *tim* expression localised in scattered neurons in the dorsal regions of the *protocerebrum*.

As described above for *per* transcripts, *tim* expression was also investigated in aphids developing different life cycles, under different photoperiodic conditions and at two different moments of the day/night cycle (Figure IV.13). The results confirmed that *tim* is expressed in both the DN and the LN clusters in the two aphid strains analysed and in both photoperiods (see Figure IV.13). However, contrarily to that observed for *per* (see above), no evident differences in *tim* expression were found under the different conditions or strains analysed. Moreover, *tim* was expressed at ZT18 in YR2 and GR strains under both photoperiodic conditions.

Figure IV.13. *In situ* localisation of *tim* transcripts in brains of adult *A. pisum* aphids detected with DIG-labelled probes and revealed with NBT/BCIP substrate. Images of brains from aphids of the YR2 and GR strains are shown on the left and right columns, respectively. The four upper images correspond to aphids reared under LD (Long Day, 16L:8D) and the four lower images correspond to G1 aphids reared under SD (Short Day, 12L:12D) conditions. For each strain and photoperiod aphids fixed at ZT6 and ZT18 were analysed. Black and white arrowheads indicate DN and LN, respectively.

Combined localisation of *period* and *timeless* transcripts

The similarity in the arrangement of *per* and *tim* expressing neurons (see previous sections) motivated a deeper analysis of their distribution to check the possibility that both genes are being expressed in the same brain neuron clusters. Ideally, the use of differently labelled *per* and *tim* probes would have allowed to test the colocalisation of both gene transcripts. However, as we had available DIG-labelled probes for both genes, we used them in combination to simultaneously detect both transcripts in the CNSs of the pea aphid (Figure IV.14). By comparing the positive clusters obtained using both probes in combination with those obtained using the respective single probes, it can be inferred whether both genes are expressed in the same or different brain cells. CNSs obtained from the same group of aphids were used to separately localise the expression of *per* gene (see Figure IV.14 A) and the expression of *tim* gene (see Figure IV.14 B), which revealed the corresponding DN and LN clusters already described for each of the genes. The combined probe hybridisation did not reveal new clusters of cells apart from those already described (see Figure IV.14 C and D). The comparison of the number of cells between the single probe and the combined probe hybridisations showed no more than eight s-DN and two l-DN (see Figure IV.14 C and D, see also “pertim” and “pertim_60x” image stacks in ANNEXES). The number of s-DN expressing *per* or *tim* individually were the same than the number of neurons in the combined probe approach. Therefore, it could be assumed that *per* and *tim* were being coexpressed in the s-DN. Since no detectable expression of *per* in the l-DN was observed, it is suggested that only *tim* would be expressed in the l-DN. In reference to the LN cluster, the same number of neurons could be

Figure IV.14. Combined *in situ* localisation of *tim* and *per* transcripts in brains of adult *A. pisum* aphids. **A)** Light microscope image of *per* expressing neurons. **B)** Light microscope image showing *tim* expressing neurons. **C)** Light microscope image of the combined *in situ* localisation of *per* and *tim*. **D)** a series of Z-stack confocal images showing in detail the DN (left), the dLN (middle) and vLN (right). Below each image, the corresponding merge with nuclear DAPI staining is shown. DN (dorsal neurons), LN (lateral neurons), dLN (dorsal LN), vLN (ventral LN). Scale bars identified in individual and simultaneous hybridisations, indicating that *per*

identified in individual and simultaneous hybridisations, indicating that *per* and *tim* were coexpressed in the LNs (Figure IV.14 D).

Compatibility of quantitative expression and localisation of *per* and *tim* transcripts

Given some apparent discrepancies between the quantification of *per* and *tim* expression through RT-qPCR (see Figure IV.7 and Figure IV.9) and the localisation of their transcripts (see Figure IV.11 and Figure IV.13), additional localisation experiments were performed in order to test the compatibility with previous RT-qPCR results on the quantification of *per* and *tim* expression (see section IV.1.2). This was done by using brains from aphids collected from the RT-qPCR Experiment 2 at ZT15 and ZT21, the two time points that respectively represented the maximum and minimum expression of *per* and *tim* (see Figure IV.15 D). As can be seen in Figure IV.15, localisation of *per* transcripts was evident (see Figure IV.15 A) at ZT15 in DN and LN clusters. Both neuron clusters were also expressing detectable levels of *tim* at ZT15 (see Figure IV.15 B). On the contrary, there were no detectable levels of *per* or *tim* transcripts at ZT21 in any of the neuron groups (see Figure IV.15 C). Therefore, the quantification of *per* and *tim* expression by means of RT-qPCR agreed with localisation data of *per* and *tim* transcripts.

Figure IV.15. Light microscope images showing localisation of *per* and *tim* transcripts in *A. pisum* brains at two moments of the day/night cycle. **A)** Localisation of *per* transcripts in aphid brains collected at ZT15 that corresponds to the peak of *per* expression. Left, detail of DN. Right detail of LN. **B)** Localisation of *tim* transcripts in aphid brains collected at ZT15 that corresponds to the peak of *tim* expression. Left, detail of DN. Right detail of LN. **C)** Image indicating the absence of localisation of *per* and *tim* transcripts in aphid brains collected at ZT21 that corresponds to the trough of *per* and *tim* expression. **D)** Graphical representation of RT-qPCR results of *per* and *tim* genes at different ZTs for YR2 aphids reared in LD conditions. DN (dorsal neurons), LN (lateral neurons). Scale bars = 50 μ m.

2. Analysis of the putative output elements of the aphid circadian clock

As described in Introduction, the circadian clock is an autonomous pacemaker that generates an endogenous oscillation that is synchronised with the external environment mainly by light. The circadian clock provides internal cues in order to coordinate the rhythmic information from the central pacemaker to regulate the metabolism of the organs or tissues. In mammals, the main internal cue of circadian rhythms is the biogenic amine known as melatonin, while in insects the situation seems to be more diverse. In fact several output candidates of the insect circadian clock have been described, including the control of circadian activity by PDF in *Drosophila* (Helfrich-Förster, 2009), the regulation of ecdysteroidogenesis by PTH in *Rhodnius prolixus* (Steel and Vafopoulou, 2006) and the control of PTH release by melatonin signalling from clock cells in *Antheraea pernyi* (Mohamed et al., 2014). In this section, the results of the study of some candidate elements to act as output of the circadian clock in the pea aphid will be described in the context of photoperiodism.

2.1. Pigment dispersing factor

Despite the high degree of conservation at the amino acid level the neuropeptide known as pigment dispersing factor or hormone (PDF/PDH), previous attempts failed to identify a *pigment dispersing factor* (*pdf*) aphid gene through blast searches or through genomic and proteomic analysis (Cortés et al., 2008; Le Trionnaire et al., 2009, 2012; Huybrechts et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2014). However, given that PDF is highly conserved among

Panarthropoda (Mayer et al., 2015), its detection and localisation with antibodies raised against PDF from other arthropod species has been achieved several times (Chuman et al., 2002; Závodská et al., 2009; Vafopoulou et al., 2010; Strauss et al., 2011; Mayer et al., 2015). Two antibodies provided by Dr. Rosato (University of Leicester) that had already been tested on *Drosophila* brains with positive results were used. The detection of PDF/PDH in aphids was attempted with a monoclonal antibody against *Drosophila* PDF and a polyclonal antibody against crustacean Pigment Dispersing Hormone (PDH) (Figure IV.16). Neither of them produced a positive signal in any of the treatments and strains analysed (see Figure IV.16 B), although the integrity of both antibodies was confirmed by the presence of PDF/PDH immunoreactivity in *Drosophila* control brains hybridised along with the aphid brains (see Figure IV.16 A).

Figure IV.16. Detection of PDF/PDH with antibodies. **A)** Z-stack confocal image showing the localisation of PDF immunoreactivity in the *Drosophila* brain showing the LN neurons sending axons distally to the optic lobe and medially to the posterior optic tract and the dorsal protocerebrum. **B)** Z-stack confocal image showing the absence of PDF/PDH immunoreactivity in the brain of *A. pisum*. LN, lateral neurons; OL, optic lobe PC, *protocerebrum*. Bars = 50 μ m.

After an intense search through the pea aphid genome, we identified a region within the annotated transcript prediction XM_008184191 in scaffold GL349863 that might have encoded the aphid PDF (see *Pdf* gene model in ANNEXES). The amino acid sequence that resembled insect mature PDF was, however, encoded in the reverse strand.

2.2. Melatonin

The biogenic amine melatonin (MEL) has been shown to play a role in both circadian and seasonal rhythms in mammals (Dardente et al., 2014; Wood and Loudon, 2014). As described in the introduction, melatonin has been quantified in several insects generally revealing a peak during the night (Vivien-Roels and Pévet, 1993) and has been shown to be involved in some insect circadian rhythms. On the other hand, its hypothetical participation in insect seasonal responses is not well understood, although melatonin has been shown to be involved in PTH signalling and, to some extent, alter the seasonal response of aphids. In the following section the localisation and quantification of melatonin in the aphid central nervous system will be described. In addition, a possible role of insect *AANAT* genes in melatonin synthesis in *A. pisum* will be investigated.

Melatonin localisation

In situ localisation of melatonin in the central nervous system (CNS) of aphids using specific anti-MEL antibodies was successfully achieved (Figure IV.17). Control preparations were carried out by following exactly the same procedure of normal preparations except for the absence of the rabbit anti-MEL antibody (see section III.3.2). The specificity of the MEL signal was confirmed by the absence of signal in these control preparations (see

Figure IV.17 A). In order to investigate the possible changes in MEL distribution along aphid development, CNSs of first instar aphid larva to 9 days old adults were used for MEL localisation. In most preparations, a total of 22 MEL-immunoreactive neurons (MEL-in) were detected within the ganglia, located in the dorsal soma cortex of both SOG and TGM (see Figure IV.17 B to D). Of those, the SOG contained eight MEL-in distributed in pairs, this is one pair per hemineuromere or two pairs per segment (see Figure IV.17 B). In the TGM there were a total of 14 MEL-in arranged in six pairs (see Figure IV.17 B), in a distribution similar to that seen in the SOG. Each of the thoracic neuromeres included two pairs of MEL-in, each pair located in each side of the three thoracic segments. Additionally, there were two single MEL-in at the posterior part of the TGM that would correspond to the fused abdominal ganglia (see Figure IV.17 B). The comparison of MEL immunoreactivity in aphid CNSs from the first (L1) to the third larval instar (L3) revealed that MEL was found mainly in the cytoplasm of the neuron soma, but not in the nucleus (see Figure IV.17 C). In fact, the nucleus of MEL-in could be discerned by the absence of signal, giving the cell a characteristic doughnut-like shape. Even though in some cases MEL was already present in the axonic cones of neurons from the three first larval instars, a more evident mobilisation of MEL from the cell bodies to the axons was usually seen from L3 onwards (see Figure IV.17 C). From L3 on, MEL was mobilised into the proximal segment of the axons, that cross with the axons from the contralateral MEL-in at the ventro-medial commissures (see Figure IV.17 C and D). From each pair of MEL-in, two axons run together towards the ventro-medial commissure (see Figure IV.17 D, full arrowheads) from where they cross with the axons of the pair of MEL-in of the opposite hemineuromere. From this point, the axons continued

dorsally following the boundary between the soma cortex and the underlying contralateral neuropil (see Figure IV.17 D left, empty arrowheads). At this point the MEL signal lost definition, which made it difficult to trace the axonic ends. The axons of the anterior neuromere of the SOG branched at the ventro-medial commissure, with one of the axons extending towards the anterior connective tissue finally innervating the *protocerebrum* (see Figure IV.17 C and E). In adult aphids, these axons extended into the *protocerebrum* resulting in varicose, arborised innervations in the protocerebral neuropil (see Figure IV.17 E). In cases where these innervations had a strong MEL signal, each of the axons further branched in two secondary processes: one reached the ventral region innervating the *tritocerebrum*, while the other continued ventrally in the *protocerebrum* turning upwards in the frontal region finally innervating the *pars intercerebralis* (see Figure IV.17 E, see also “brain_melatonin” and “brain_melatonin2” image stacks in ANNEXES). Besides the extensions towards the anterior part, other processes from the MEL-in in the anterior neuromere of the SOG continued to the contralateral neuropil producing extensive arborisations (see Figure IV.17 D). On the other hand, the MEL-in of the second segment of the SOG only extended the axons towards the contralateral neuropil, also producing arborisations (see Figure IV.17 D).

With respect to the TGM axons from the MEL-in corresponding to the thoracic ganglia (T1, T2 and T3), the axonic pattern was similar to that described for the SOG MEL-in. From each pair of neurons, two axons extended to the ventro-medial commissure (see Figure IV.17 D full arrowheads), where they cross with the MEL axons from the contralateral hemineuromere in the same way they did in the SOG. From that point, one of the processes continued to the posterior distal part of the contralateral

hemiganglion where the axon adopted an arc-shaped form while turned dorsally (see Figure IV.17 D empty arrowheads). The final segment of the axon further extended forming an arborised region in the dorsal neuropil (see Figure IV.17 D right). The axons originated from MEL-in of T2 and T3 followed the same path described for MEL-in of T1 (see Figure IV.17 D).

The two single MEL-in corresponding to the abdominal ganglia (see Figure IV.17 B) projected axons to the posterior ventro-medial region (see Figure IV.17 C and D). From there, the axons sharply turned dorsally and then ran in parallel to the posterior part of the ganglia, probably extending into the posterior nerve (see Figure IV.17 D right). In adult aphids, MEL further spread into the axons of the abdominal neurons and their ends could be traced into the contralateral neuropil. In the adult stage of development, the neurites of all MEL-in in the SOG shared a striking feature, namely the appearance of varicosities followed by arborisations along the processes (see Figure IV.17 C and D right), including the processes reaching the *protocerebrum* (see Figure IV.17 F).

Figure IV.17. Previous page. Z-stack confocal images showing the localisation of MEL immunoreactive neurons in the pea aphid CNS. **A)** Complete aphid CNS control hybridisation without primary anti-MEL antibody. Note the absence of MEL signal. **B)** Overview of MEL positive detection and distribution in the CNS. **C)** Comparison of MEL in CNSs of aphids at different developmental stages. **D)** Z-stack including the most ventral image slices (left) and the complete Z-stack (right) of the aphid nervous ganglia. Two ventro-medial commissures are indicated by full arrowheads and two arc-shaped axons are indicated by empty arrowheads. **E)** Detail of the protocerebral MEL arborised axons (left) and a merge with a light microscopy image of the same brain showing MEL protocerebral axons in green. BR, brain; SOG, suboesophageal ganglion; TGM, thoracic ganglionic mass; S1 and S2 refer to the first and second SOG neuromeres; T1-T3 refer to the first, second and third TGM neuromeres, respectively; L1 and L3 refer to first and third larval stage aphids; A1 and A9 refer to one and nine days old adult aphids. Bars = 50 µm.

Antibody staining showed MEL signal from L1 to 9 days old adults (A9). As previously said, although there was some variability in the localisation of MEL in neurons, the general observed pattern was that MEL remained confined in the neuron soma during the first three larval stages (see Figure IV.17 C). From the third larval stage onwards, MEL moved into the axons. At the beginning, MEL filled the axonic cones (see Figure IV.17 B). During third and fourth larval stages, MEL gradually moved further into the axons. The mobilisation of MEL was coordinated in the three parts of the central nervous system (brain, SOG and TGM). This means that neurites of the three parts are filled with mobilised MEL at the same time and eventually MEL reached the neuropilar regions located beneath the soma cortex (compare stages in Figure IV.17 C). The previously described distribution and mobilisation of MEL in developmental time was compared in aphids from the holocyclic (YR2) and the anholocyclic (GR) strain. Each of the strains included aphids reared under LD (Long Day, 16L:8D) and SD (G1 of aphids reared under Short Day, 12L:12D) conditions (see section III.1). Despite a certain degree of variability in MEL distribution and in intensities in different strains and photoperiods, no major differences were observed in the number or distribution of MEL-in nor in the timing of MEL mobilisation between strains and photoperiods.

Melatonin quantification

Melatonin was both detected and quantified in whole adult aphids following an HPLC-MS/MS method previously developed for aphid samples (Escrivá et al., 2016). In order to reveal a possible involvement of melatonin in the aphid seasonal response, the quantification was carried out in aphids of the holocyclic and anholocyclic strains (YR2 and GR, respectively) reared

under LD (16L:8D) and SD (12L:12D) photoperiods (see section III.1). Aiming to investigate a putative circadian rhythm in melatonin titres, two time points of the day/night cycle (ZT6 and ZT18) were included for each of the strains and photoperiods analysed. All quantified samples of adult aphids from both strains (YR2 and GR) and both photoperiods (LD and SD) were above LOD¹ (1 pg/mg aphid) and LOQ² (5 pg/mg aphid). Levels of MEL were determined from the areas obtained by HPLC-MS/MS using a calibration curve with melatonin dilutions of known concentration (see "HPLC_MEL" file in ANNEXES).

The results from MEL quantification are shown in IV.4. These results were used to compare melatonin mean levels between strains, photoperiods and

Table IV.4. Summary of melatonin quantification by HPLC-MS/MS.

Strain	Photoperiod	ZT	Area	Aphid Weight (mg)	[MEL] (ng/ g aphid)
YR2	LD	6	1.06E+04	182.0	1.0510
			5.79E+03	199.4	0.5217
			1.02E+04	161.3	1.1391
		18	9.94E+03	189.1	0.9451
			1.16E+04	192.5	1.0787
			5.10E+03	194.4	0.4717
	SD	6	2.77E+03	153.8	0.3238
			2.02E+04	159.8	2.2703
			1.34E+04	155.1	1.5555
		18	1.88E+04	169.9	1.9914
			1.79E+04	189.5	1.7010
			3.16E+04	188.7	3.0096
GR	LD	6	2.76E+03	168.3	0.2951
			1.07E+04	188.6	1.0180
			8.75E+03	168.8	0.9317
		18	1.09E+04	139.6	1.3985
			9.71E+03	136.7	1.2775
			1.07E+04	133.8	1.4350
	SD	6	6.51E+03	146.9	0.7966
			1.16E+04	151.9	1.3681
			8.59E+03	149.2	1.0353
		18	7.15E+03	153.6	0.8372
			5.35E+03	156.0	0.6162
			3.26E+03	133.3	0.4390

Figure IV.18. Analysis of MEL quantification in aphids. Bars represent the mean MEL content \pm SEM. **A)** Comparison of MEL content at ZT6 and ZT18 in aphids of the holocyclic strain YR2 (left) and the anholocyclic strain GR (right) reared under two different photoperiods. **B)** Comparison of global MEL content in aphids of the YR2 and GR strains reared under LD and SD photoperiods. ANOVA p-values are indicated by * < 0.050, ** < 0.001.

moments of the day/night cycle (Figure IV.18). Most relevant, aphids of the holocyclic strain YR2 reared under SD conditions showed significant higher MEL content than aphids of the same strain reared under LD photoperiod (see Figure IV.18 B). This increase of melatonin content in SD conditions

respect to LD in the YR2 strain was consistent for each of the ZTs (see Figure IV.18 A). On the other hand, in the anholocyclic strain GR, melatonin levels remained constant in both photoperiods (see Figure IV.18 B). Moreover, melatonin levels in GR aphids reared under both photoperiods were similar to those observed in the YR2 strain reared in LD (see Figure IV.18 B). Finally, no significant differences were found in MEL levels between the two sampled ZTs in any strain or photoperiod analysed (see Figure IV.18 A).

2.3. Studies on *AANAT* genes

In this section we investigate the presence of insect-type *AANAT* (i-*AANAT*) genes in *A. pisum* and examine their possible role in photoperiodism.

Identification of *AANAT* genes in *A. pisum*

A BLASTP search on the *A. pisum* RefSeq database using as query the *Drosophila melanogaster* dopamine-N-acetyltransferase 1 (DAT1) protein sequence¹ yielded five predicted aphid sequences with E-values lower than 1.0×10^{-4} (IV.5). As expected, searches performed using the *Rattus norvegicus* *AANAT* amino acid sequence failed to identify any sequence having significant similarity in the *A. pisum* database. To confirm the orthology of the aphid predicted genes identified, we carried out a phylogenetic analysis that included the five aphid amino acid sequences and i-*AANAT* sequences representative of different insect orders including representatives of the three *AANAT* clusters described by Han et al. (2012) as well as sequences representative of vertebrate *AANATs* (v-*AANAT*) as outgroups. Phylogenetic analysis (Figure IV.19) revealed that four of the

¹ A representative of insect-like *AANAT* (see section I.2.2).

five aphid sequences found after the BLAST searches grouped close together in a single clade within a monophyletic cluster containing other typical i-AANATs (Han et al., 2012), thus confirming that they were in fact i-AANAT aphid orthologues. Correspondingly, these aphid genes were named as *AANAT1* to *AANAT4* (see IV.5). Other sequences that grouped in this clade included the *D. melanogaster* DAT1 sequence, the *Periplaneta americana* NAT1 sequence, a *B. mori* sequence whose variable expression levels were reported to match those of melatonin in that species (Itoh et al., 1995a) and an *Antheraea pernyi* i-AANAT whose expression is regulated by the circadian clock (Mohamed et al., 2014). Genes coding aphid *AANAT1* and *AANAT2* were physically very close together in scaffold GL349852 (see IV.5 and gene models in ANNEXES). The other two genes were in separate scaffolds. The fifth aphid sequence (XP_001949957) identified in BLAST searches grouped in a monophyletic clade very distant from the typical i-AANAT sequences that, however, was not described by Han et al. (2012). Moreover, contrary to the four aphid AANAT sequences described above, a search for conserved domains or motifs failed to find the N-acetyltransferase domain or the acetyl coenzyme A (acetyl-CoA) binding

Table IV.5. Summary of results of BLASTP searches using the DAT sequence from *D. melanogaster* against the RefSeq database available in Aphidbase¹ including the results of CD-search tool at National Center for Biotechnology Information.

RefSeq Peptides	ACYPI code	% identity With DAT1	E-value	Location	N° of Exons	Length of Protein	Assigned Name	CD-search ²
XP_001949940	ACYPI002543	35	3.00E-39	GL349852 (554,922-558,230)	4	254	<i>AANAT1</i>	NAT_SF/CoAbp
XP_001950140	ACYPI000655	34	3.00E-33	GL349852 (529,080-550,730)	4	224	<i>AANAT2</i>	NAT_SF/CoAbp
XP_001950135	ACYPI000856	33	4.00E-29	GL350487 (82,096-95,222)	4	224	<i>AANAT3</i>	NAT_SF/CoAbp
XP_001949503	ACYPI060713	26	3.00E-11	GL349956 (23,388-33,738)	3	222	<i>AANAT4</i>	NAT_SF/CoAbp
XP_001949957	ACYPI000302	28	5.00E-05	GL350216 (139,233-148,099)	3	181	Not assigned	None

1 <http://bipaa.genouest.org/is/aphidbase/>

2 NAT_SF, N-acetyltransferase superfamily; CoAbp, Coenzyme A binding pocket.

2. Analysis of the putative output elements of the aphid circadian clock

Figure IV.19. Neighbour-joining tree built using Poisson-corrected distances on different insect and vertebrate N-acetyltransferases including the pea aphid sequences identified in this report (in bold), four of them indicated as *A. pisum* arylalkylamine N-acetyltransferase (AANAT) after sequence characterisation. Accession numbers of sequences are indicated next to the species names. i-AANAT indicates the insect clade containing all insect AANAT sequences as opposed to the v-AANAT that corresponds to vertebrate AANAT sequences used as the outgroup. Cluster 1, cluster 2 and cluster 3 correspond to three clusters defined by Han et al. (2012) (described in parentheses). Bootstrap support if higher than 50 is indicated above branches. The tree was constructed using MEGA7 (Kumar et al., 2016). *A. gambiae*, *Anopheles gambiae*; *A. pernyi*, *Antheraea pernyi*; *A. pernyi*; *A. mellifera*, *Apis mellifera*; *B. mori*, *Bombyx mori*; *C. quinquefasciatus*, *Culex quinquefasciatus*; *D. melanogaster*, *Drosophila melanogaster*; *H. sapiens*, *Homo sapiens*; *P. americana*, *Periplaneta americana*; *P. humanus*, *Pediculus humanus*; *R. norvegicus*, *Rattus norvegicus*; *T. castaneum*, *Tribolium castaneum*; *X. laevis*, *Xenopus laevis*.

pocket typical of acetyltransferases in this aphid sequence (see IV.5). The fifth aphid AANAT was therefore excluded from further analysis. Of the

four i-AANAT sequences identified in the genome of *A. pisum*, AANAT3 and AANAT4 were most similar (77.2% identity and 90.6% similarity between them) whereas AANAT2 was the most divergent in all comparisons. Compared with the *Drosophila* DAT1 sequence, aphid AANAT1 was most similar, showing 35% identity (56.7% similarity) whereas AANAT4 was more different (26% identity; 50.4% similarity). Aphid i-AANATs were more similar to the cockroach i-AANAT sequence (37.5 and 33.9% identical to AANAT1 and AANAT4, respectively), which was reflected by a closer position in the phylogenetic tree (see Figure IV.19). Aphid i-AANAT sequences were rather divergent with respect to vertebrate type AANAT (v-AANAT) sequences (about 17% identity and 35% similarity when compared with the rat sequence in Figure IV.19).

Characterisation of aphid AANAT genes

As the four aphid AANAT sequences identified corresponded to gene predictions derived from the *A. pisum* genome, we decided to experimentally validate the models and gain some idea of their variability by trying to amplify the coding region along with partial 5'- and 3'- untranslated regions on cDNA synthesised from aphid total RNA from the two aphid strains (see section III.2.2). Amplified cDNAs from AANAT1–4 were respectively 1291, 1275, 949 and 669 bp long and encoded open reading frames (ORFs) of 254, 224, 224 and 222 amino acids, respectively (Figure IV.20; see also AANAT gene models in ANNEXES). Sequences were deposited in GenBank with accession numbers KC626025 to KC626044.

Figure IV.20. Alignment of the four predicted *Acyrtosiphon pisum* arylalkylamine N-acetyltransferase (AANAT) protein sequences from the YR2 strain along with sequences of *Drosophila melanogaster* and *Periplaneta americana*. The NAT domain is indicated by a black bar above the alignment. The conserved residues involved in acetyl coenzyme A binding are indicated by red circles above the alignment (Cheng et al., 2012). GNAT family conserved motifs C, D, A and B (Dyda et al., 2000) are indicated by grey boxes on the alignment. Typical GNAT secondary structure prediction is represented below the alignment. Alpha helices and beta strands are numbered according to Dyda et al. (2000). Extra helix α_2 (see text for details) is also indicated. Conserved residues described for GNATs are marked with asterisks. The three polymorphic amino acids detected in the two aphid strains (see text for details) are enclosed by boxes and the positions indicated by arrowheads on the alignment for easier visualisation.

Apart from minor differences, experimentally obtained sequences basically coincided with the predictions. No polymorphisms within the CDS were found for *AANAT1* nor *AANAT2*. For *AANAT1*, two alternative splicing variants were experimentally obtained that differed in the presence of exon3, whose absence would produce a shorter protein (Figure IV.21 A). Strains YR2 and GR showed the same heterozygous position for the *AANAT3* sequence, having both Asn56 and histidine at that position. For *AANAT4* a heterozygous condition was found in strain GR, having isoleucine and lysine at position 45, where YR2 has isoleucine. In YR2, Thr177 was found in heterozygous condition with alanine (see Figure IV.20). Additionally, *AANAT4* in both strains showed a splicing variant 392 bp long that lacked the second exon and thus resulted in a truncated protein that only coincided with the prediction up to Tyr64 (see Figure IV.21). As already mentioned, the search for conserved domains revealed that all four aphid sequences, similar to *Drosophila* DAT1 and *P. americana* NAT1, contained an N-acetyltransferase domain, typical of the GNAT¹ superfamily (PF00583) (see Figure IV.20). We identified the four NAT conserved regions designated as motifs C, D, A and B (Dyda et al., 2000) in the four aphid *AANAT* sequences (see Figure IV.20). Most relevantly, aphid motif A included the presence of the highly conserved six-residue fragment R/Q-X-X-G-X-G/A, considered an acetyl-CoA binding site (Cort et al., 2008), located inside the acetyl-CoA binding pocket (Cheng et al., 2012). However, in the aphid sequences, the sixth amino acid was a cysteine rather than the canonical glycine or alanine residues (see Figure IV.20). Using aphid sequences, a typical GNAT secondary structure could be predicted consisting of six β strands (β) and six helices (α) in the topology β 1- α 1- α 2-

1 GCN5-related N-acetyltransferases.

$\alpha 2'$ - $\beta 2$ - $\beta 3$ - αA - $\beta 4$ - $\alpha 3$ - $\beta 5$ - $\alpha 4$ - $\beta 6$, followed by a less conserved C-terminal region. Two singular helices were found: αA and $\alpha 2'$.

Regulatory elements

Since i-AANATs may be part of the circadian clock output via regulation of melatonin synthesis, the 5' regions of the four aphid *AANAT* genes were inspected for E-box and V/P-box elements, which are known to mediate in circadian regulation of transcription (Cyrán et al., 2003; Hardin, 2004; Yu et al., 2006; Özkaya and Rosato, 2012). Despite the presence of these elements in all *AANAT* genes, a certain degree of conservation in number and distribution was only observed in *AANAT1* and *AANAT3* (see Figure IV.21 B). The 5' region of *AANAT1* genes of *A. pisum* and *M. persicae* contained one and two E-boxes in the same region, respectively. However, the presence of an assembly gap in *MypAANAT1* suggests that this result should be taken cautiously. In reference to the *AANAT3* gene, two E-boxes and two or three V/P-boxes were present in a similar arrangement in both species.

Quantification of aphid *AANAT* expression

RT-qPCR was performed to analyse the expression profiles of the four aphid i-AANAT genes (Figure IV.22) in the same samples used in the Experiment 1 described in section IV.1.2. In summary, the quantification included samples of aphids collected every 6 h for 1.5 days (i.e. six moments of the day/night cycle) from the YR2 and GR strains reared under LD (16L:8D) conditions, as well as G1 aphids reared under SD (12L:12D) conditions (see section III.1). The expression profiles of *AANAT1* in YR2 aphids showed high levels of expression at the first ZTs that rapidly decreased over time (see Figure IV.22). This pattern was more pronounced

Figure IV.21. Schematic representation of the structure of the four *AANAT* genes of *A. pisum*. **A)** Splicing variants deduced from alignments of our experimentally obtained transcript sequences with the aphid genome sequence. Putative initial methionines are indicated by Met and stop codons by STOP. Putative coding DNA sequences (CDS) are shown in grey. Exon numbers are indicated below the first splicing variant. **B)** Schematic diagram of the regions upstream exon 1 of each gene showing relevant putative regulatory elements in *A. pisum* and *M. persicae*. E-boxes are represented by yellow bars and V/P-boxes by magenta bars. Assembly gaps are indicated by GAP in white boxes. Exons are indicated in white and grey boxes.

in YR2 aphids reared in SD than those reared in LD. Aphids of the GR strain reared in SD displayed a similar profile except that expression increased from ZT3 to ZT9. On the other hand, the expression levels of GR aphids reared in LD displayed steady levels of expression. With respect to *AANAT2* expression, the comparison between ZTs showed significant differences only in YR2 aphids reared under LD conditions, in which there was a peak at ZT9 and a trough at ZT27 (see Figure IV.22). Analysis of *AANAT3* gene expression revealed significant differences between ZTs only in YR2 aphids grown in SD photoperiod (see Figure IV.22). In this case, the expression profile showed a peak of expression at ZT21 and a trough at ZT3 and ZT27 (i.e. equivalent to ZT3 of the second day/night cycle). The expression profile of *AANAT4* was the only one showing higher expression in GR than in the YR2 strain (see Figure IV.22). However, only in aphids of the YR2 strain reared in SD conditions there were significant differences between ZTs, with a maximum at ZT15 followed by a decrease at ZT21 and reaching the minimum at ZT27 (see Figure IV.22).

Since aphid *i-AANATs* are candidates to be part of a circadian clock output, the presence of circadian rhythmicity was tested using COSINOR software. However, none of the expression profiles that previously showed significant differences of expression between ZTs revealed significant rhythmicity with COSINOR (see "cosinor_aanat" in ANNEXES).

The expression of the four aphid *i-AANAT* genes was also compared between aphids of the YR2 and GR strains reared under two different photoperiods (Figure IV.23). The comparison of expression levels of the different aphid *i-AANATs* showed that *AANAT1* was most expressed, followed by *AANAT2* and *AANAT3*. *AANAT4* showed the lowest levels of

Figure IV.22. Expression profiles of the i-AANAT aphid genes obtained for the holocyclic strain YR2 (left) and the anholocyclic strain GR (right). The expression results from aphids reared under LD (Long Day, 16L:8D) are represented by black circles and those of SD (Short Day, 12L:12D) by black triangles. The mean relative expression of three replicates \pm SEM are plotted at 6 h intervals over 1.5 days. Significant differences in expression at different time points are indicated in bold and italic letters for LD and SD photoperiods, respectively. The dark phase of the photoperiods is indicated as grey background ranging from ZT12 to ZT24 in SD and ZT16 to ZT24 in LD.

expression among all AANATs. A general pattern of higher expression in SD respect to LD in YR2 aphids was seen for AANAT1, AANAT2 and AANAT3, but not for AANAT4. On the other hand, for the GR strain only AANAT1, AANAT2

Figure IV.23. Comparison of levels of expression of the *i-AANAT* genes between aphid strains and photoperiods. Bars represent the mean relative expression calculated for all ZT within a strain and photoperiod \pm SEM. Letters on top of each bar represent the subgroup significance (p -value < 0.05) of the ANOVA test comparing the variable photoperiod for each gene.

and *AANAT4* showed significant higher expression in SD respect to LD. In the GR strain, *AANAT2* expression in any of the photoperiods did not reach the expression levels of the YR2 strain (see Figure IV.23). It is also important to note that *AANAT3* expression increased in SD respect to LD in the YR2 strain, while it remained at similar levels in the GR strain.

Localisation of *AANAT* transcripts and melatonin

In order to investigate if any of the four aphid *i-AANAT* genes could be responsible for melatonin synthesis, our indirect approach was to localise their transcripts by *in situ* hybridisations and to compare with melatonin localisation (see section III.3.5). Positive results were only obtained for the *AANAT2* and *AANAT3* genes (Figure IV.24). The specificity of the probes was confirmed by the absence of staining in preparations in which the respective sense probes were used (not shown).

As seen in the *in situ* hybridisation of *per* and *tim* probes (see section IV.1.3), CNS hybridised with sense and antisense probes showed *tracheal* non specific staining (see Figure IV.24).

Similar to melatonin localisation, expression of *AANAT2* was restricted to the ganglia (see Figure IV.24 and image stack “*AANAT2_MELganglia*” in ANNEXES), in which several cells distributed in a similar pattern to that described for melatonin neurons was observed (see Figure IV.24 B and section IV.2.2). However, the position and number of neurons expressing *AANAT2* was different from those that showed melatonin immunoreactivity. The SOG contained four strongly stained neurons expressing *AANAT2* located at the anterior region, close to the circumoesophageal connective between SOG and the brain (see Figure IV.24 A). Additionally, five dorsal clusters each containing approximately four neurons were found in the antero-medial region of neuromeres S1, S2, T1, T2, and T3 (see Figure IV.24 A). It thus seemed that each pair of melatonin neurons was associated to two *AANAT2* neurons, except the abdominal group that was associated to two neurons (see Figure IV.24 C). In summary, 26 *AANAT2* expressing neurons were identified in the aphid

Figure IV.24. Localisation of *i-AANAT* transcripts in the aphid central nervous system. Z-stack confocal images showing a dorsal view of the aphid central nervous system. **A)** Localisation of *AANAT2* transcripts in the nervous ganglia in cyan. Arrowheads indicate the strongly stained neurons expressing *AANAT2* located ventrally with respect to the rest of neurons. **B)** Same ganglia as A showing in red the melatonin immunoreactive neurons (MEL-in). **C)** A and B merged. Note the different positions of *AANAT2* expressing neurons and MEL-in. **D)** Localisation of *AANAT3* transcripts in the nervous ganglia in green. **E)** Same central nervous system as D showing in red the MEL-in. **F)** D and E merged. Note the different position of *AANAT3* expressing neurons and MEL-in. Abd, abdominal neuromere; OL, optic lobe; PC, *protocerebrum*; SOG, suboesophageal ganglion; S1 and S2, first and second SOG neuromeres respectively; TGM, thoracic ganglionic mass; T1-T3, pro-, meso- and metathoracic neuromeres respectively. Bars = 50 µm.

CNS: the SOG contained four anterior and eight dorsal neurons, while the TGM contained a total of 16 neurons expressing *AANAT2*.

Differently to *AANAT2*, expression of *AANAT3* was observed in a larger number of neurons (see Figure IV.24 D), distributed in all three parts of the CNS, including the *protocerebrum* and optic lobes, the SOG and the TGM. Despite the great number of *AANAT3* expressing neurons, none of them colocalised with melatonin neurons (see Figure IV.24 E and F). Generally, the *AANAT3* neurons were found in a deeper position of the soma cortex, closer to the underlying neuropil (see image stacks “*AANAT3_MELbrain*” and “*AANAT3_MELganglia*” in ANNEXES).

In situ hybridisations were also carried out with probes against *AANAT1* and *AANAT4*. Unfortunately, no specific staining was observed for these two genes.

2.4. Prothoracicotropic Hormone

As explained in the introduction, the prothoracicotropic hormone (PTTH) is an insect neuropeptide synthesised in brain cells and released to the haemolymph from the *corpus cardiacum* or the *corpora allata*. Its main function is to activate ecdysteroidogenesis in prothoracic glands that regulate the moulting process (Smith and Rybczynski, 2012). Recent evidence show that PTTH is an output of the circadian clock in the hemipteran *Rhodnius prolixus*, in which clock neurons control the rhythmic PTTH synthesis and release from the brain that synchronise an autonomous clock in the prothoracic glands in conjunction with insulin-like peptides (Vafopoulou and Steel, 2014).

Although several neuropeptides have been identified since the publication of the pea aphid genome (The International Aphid Genomics Consortium, 2010), PTTH was absent from the list of the identified neurohormones. Thus, identification, characterisation and localisation of PTTH in aphids is reported in the present work for the first time.

Identification, validation and characterisation of the *Ptth* aphid gene

Blastp searches using *Drosophila* (NP_001285550.1) and *Bombyx mori* (NP_001037349.1) PTTH protein sequences were used as queries against the protein prediction database of the Aphidbase. The search retrieved a single predicted protein in *A. pisum* with accession number XP_003243880.1 at NCBI and ACYPI37989 code at Aphidbase that was located in scaffold GL349845 (IV.6). A *Myzus persicae* similar sequence could be identified in clone 0 (MYZPE13164_0_v1.0_000038450) that was located in scaffold_1475 (see *Ptth* gene model in ANNEXES). The obtained aphid sequences aligned poorly with the query sequences. Conservation at the amino acid level of insect PTTH is generally low, except for the mature peptide region (Smith and Rybczynski, 2012). However a distinctive set of features are usually conserved among insects that have been summarised

Table IV.6. Details of the results of BLASTP searches against the Refseq and protein prediction database available in Aphidbase¹.

RefSeq Peptides	ACYPI code	% identity		E-value		Location	N° of Exons	Length of Protein	Assigned Name
		bmPTTH ²	dmPTTH ³	bmPTTH ²	dmPTTH ³				
XP_003243880	ACYPI37989	26	25	2.40E-02	4.00E-04	GL349845 (880,550-907960)	3	238	<i>PTTH</i>

1 <http://bipaa.genouest.org/is/aphidbase>

2 *Bombyx mori* PTTH

3 *Drosophila melanogaster* PTTH

in Figure IV.25. The most characteristic was the presence of conserved cysteine residues (C, Cys) within the mature peptide region that are involved in the formation of intra- and inter-molecular disulphide bonds. However, the aphid *PTTH*-like sequence contained a total of six out of seven conserved Cys, thus indicating that in aphids one of the Cys could have been lost (see Figure IV.25). On the other hand, the hydrophobic signal peptide and the hydrophobic regions within the mature peptide were conserved in insects including aphids. In addition, the position of the highly conserved residues proline (P, Pro), tyrosine (Y, Tyr) and tryptophan (W, Trp) were also conserved in aphids, while the glycine (G, Gly) was not found in aphids (see Figure IV.25). It was noteworthy the presence of an aphid-specific glutamine-rich region upstream the putative aphid mature peptide (see Figure IV.25).

In order to validate the putative *Ptth* aphid gene prediction available at the Aphidbase, a PCR using aphid specific primers based on the predicted 5' and 3' untranslated regions (UTRs) (see IX.1) was performed on cDNA from YR2 and GR aphid strains. We could obtain amplicons consisting of 1049 and 992 bp, respectively for YR2 and GR (see IX.2), whose sequence included an open reading frame (ORF) of 654 nt encoding 218 amino acids flanked by putative UTRs. The comparison of the experimentally amplified sequence with the genomic sequence confirmed that the gene contains a three exon structure that agreed with the prediction in the database (Figure IV.26 A). The complete coding DNA sequence (CDS) and partial UTRs were obtained from YR2 (holocyclic) and GR (anholocyclic) strains. The analysis of the sequences revealed six polymorphisms, four of which were SNPs, and the other two involved repetitions of three and seven nucleotide motifs respectively (see "ptth_polymorphisms" file in ANNEXES). None of

Figure IV.26. Previous page. Diagram showing the structure of the aphid *Ptth* gene. **A)** Transcript model of aphid gene *Ptth*. Initial methionine is indicated by Met and stop codon by STOP. Putative coding DNA sequence (CDS) is shown in grey. **B)** Diagram representing the PTTH aphid protein. Conserved domains are shown in white boxes, conserved hydrophobic signal peptide is shown in blue, conserved cysteines are represented by vertical red bars, conserved proline, tyrosine and tryptophan are respectively indicated by P, Y and W letters. **C)** Schematic diagram of the genomic regions flanking exon 1 of aphid *Ptth* gene showing relevant putative regulatory elements in *A. pisum* and *M. persicae*. E-boxes are represented by yellow bars and V/P-boxes by magenta bars. Exons are indicated in black boxes.

the polymorphisms was located within the mature peptide region (see *Ptth* gene model in ANNEXES). The most relevant domains already described in Figure IV.25 are also shown in Figure IV.26 B.

Since *Ptth* expression has been shown to be under control of the circadian clock in *Rhodnius prolixus* (Steel and Vafopoulou, 2006; Vafopoulou and Steel, 2014) and *Antheraea pernyi* (Mohamed et al., 2014), we performed a search for circadian regulatory elements in the 5' region of the aphid *Ptth* gene that could be participating in the circadian regulation (Figure IV.26 C). Several E-boxes and V/P-boxes were found in regions adjacent to exon 1 in both aphid species. Even though the number and distribution of these elements were not exactly the same in *A. pisum* and *M. persicae*, a certain degree of conservation was evident (see Figure IV.26 C).

Localisation of *Ptth* transcripts

Hybridisation with antisense probes against *Ptth* mRNA allowed us to localise four neurons in the dorsomedial region of the *protocerebrum* (Figure IV.27). The specificity of the probe was confirmed by the absence of staining in hybridisations in which a sense probe was used as control (see Figure IV.27 A). Expression of *Ptth* was absent in the ganglia. The four neurons expressing *Ptth* were grouped in two pairs of strongly stained cells that showed a spherical morphology with particularly large nucleus (see Figure IV.27 B to G, see also “Ptth_L3” image stack in ANNEXES). As with other RNA probes (e.g. see Figure IV.10), unspecific staining of tracheae was observed in both sense and antisense probes (see Figure IV.27 A and D). The *Ptth* transcript localisation in CNSs from third larval stage (L3) aphids reared under LD conditions was compared between the holocyclic (YR2) and the anholocyclic (GR) strains (see Figure IV.27 B and C), revealing

Figure IV.27 *In situ* localisation of *Ptth* transcripts in brains of *A. pisum* aphids. **A)** Light microscope image of *Ptth* sense control hybridisation showing no specific staining. **B)** Light microscope image showing *Ptth* expressing neurons in brains of YR2 aphids of the third larval stage reared in LD photoperiod. **C)** Same as B, GR aphid strain. **D)** Light microscope image showing *Ptth* expressing neurons in brains of YR2 aphids of the third larval stage reared in LD photoperiod at ZT6. **E)** Same as D, ZT18. **F)** confocal image Z-stack of showing *Ptth* transcript localisation in brains of YR2 L3 aphids reared in LD conditions. **G)** Same as F, adult aphids. OL, optic lobes; PC, *protocerebrum*. Scale bars = 50 µm, in A Scale bar = 100 µm.

no evident differences in distribution or in staining intensity. Furthermore, a possible circadian variation in expression was studied in brains of YR2 L3 aphids reared under LD photoperiod by comparing *Ptth* staining at ZT6 (see Figure IV.27 D) and ZT18 (see Figure IV.27 E). However, no evident differences between ZTs were observed. Moreover, the localisation of *Ptth* transcripts was also compared between L3 (see Figure IV.27 F) and adult YR2 (see Figure IV.27 G) aphids reared in LD conditions, which revealed a weaker staining in adults though there were no changes in the number of cells.

Given the similarity in morphology and localisation of the *Ptth* expressing neurons to that of the l-DN expressing *per* and *tim* (see Figure IV.12), a combined probe experiment was carried out for *Ptth*, similar to that described at the end of section IV.1.3. In the case that *per*, *tim* and *Ptth* were expressed in the same neurons, only two pairs of cells would be observed in the *protocerebrum*. On the other hand, if *per*, *tim* and *Ptth* were expressed in different cells, a total of eight neurons would be seen in the dorsal anterior *protocerebrum*. The simultaneous localisation of *per*, *tim* and *Ptth* genes allowed to clearly distinguish a total of four large neurons in each of the protocerebral *pars lateralis* (Figure IV.28 A, see also “pertimpth” image stack in ANNEXES). A close inspection of the DN cluster revealed that the four large neurons were grouped in two pairs, thus one of the pairs would correspond to the l-DN expressing *Tim* (described in Figure IV.12) and the remaining pair would correspond to the previously described *Ptth* expressing neurons (see Figure IV.27 B and C). Therefore, it could be assumed that *Ptth* and *Tim* were expressed in a different but adjacent set of neurons. The spherical morphology, with particularly also spherical, large nuclei of the most dorsal posterior pair of large neurons

(see Figure IV.28 A, B and F) made it possible to identify these cells as the *Ptth* expressing neurons. Consequently, the remaining group of neurons that were located anteriorly with respect to the *Ptth* expressing neurons were identified as the l-DN cluster expressing *tim* (see Figure IV.28 A, C and F).

As previously seen in section IV.1.3, the DN cluster included two groups of cells: two neurons with stronger staining that corresponded to the l-DN expressing *tim*, and an undetermined group of neurons with weaker staining that corresponded to the s-DN expressing both *per* and *tim* (see Figure IV.28 A, C and F). Additionally, it was possible to confirm the organisation of the LN cluster that coexpresses *per* and *tim* (see Figure IV.28 F), which consisted of the dLN and the vLNs (see Figure IV.28 D and E respectively).

Figure IV.28. Next page. Combined *in situ* localisation of *Ptth*, *per* and *tim* transcripts in brains of adult *A. pisum* aphids. All images correspond to confocal microscopy. **A)** complete Z-stack showing all neurons stained simultaneously with *Ptth*, *per* and *tim* probes in red and the nucleus stained with DAPI in blue. **B)** Z-substack including the most dorsal slices of A showing the *Ptth* expressing neurons in yellow. **C)** Z-substack including the slices ventral respect to B showing the DN cluster in magenta, including the s-DN expressing *per* and *tim* and the l-DN expressing *tim*. **D)** Z-substack including the slices ventral respect to C showing the dLN cluster in green. **E)** Z-substack including the slices ventral respect to D showing the vLN cluster in red. **F)** same as A maintaining the dorsoventral axis colour code of B-E. L-DN and s-DN, large and small dorsal neurons respectively; dLN and vDN, dorsal and ventral lateral neurons respectively. Scale bars = 50 μm .

2. Analysis of the putative output elements of the aphid circadian clock

V. Discussion

The main objective of the present doctoral thesis was to study the possible role of some of the elements that define the putative aphid circadian clock in the seasonal response in these insects. In the first section I will discuss the characterisation, quantification and localisation of the core genes of the circadian clock firstly in the context of circadian rhythmicity, followed by the discussion of the results in the context of photoperiodism. In the second section, I will discuss our results on how putative output elements of the circadian clock may support their involvement in the seasonal response in aphids.

1. Circadian clock genes

In order to determine a possible involvement of the circadian clock machinery in the aphid seasonal response, it is necessary to first understand the regulation and diversity of its elements. Among insects, the circadian clock of *Drosophila melanogaster* has been the most widely studied of all. The basic functional structure is explained by a transcription/translation feedback loop model (TTL) consisting of two feedback loops—one negative and a second one positive—whose elements are highly conserved in animals (Rosato and Kyriacou, 2001; Looby and Loudon, 2005). Basically, the oscillation is produced by the interaction of transcription factors and photosensitive proteins. The whole system is finely adjusted by the participation of several phosphatases and kinases that control the phosphorylation state of the transcription factors, also including the participation of ubiquitin ligases relevant for protein degradation. The negative loop involves the participation of PER, TIM, CLK and CYC. The two bHLH-PAS transcription factors CLK and CYC, form CLK:CYC heterodimers which bind to E-box elements (consensus sequence

CACGTG) in the promoter region of *per* and *tim* genes activating its transcription. The transcript levels of *per* and *tim* reach their maximum at early night, but the respective proteins accumulate with a 6 h shift. At night, the PAS transcription factors PER and TIM accumulate and eventually, the heterodimer PER:TIM translocates to the nucleus and inhibits the CLK:CYC transcription activation of their own genes. At dawn, the light causes a conformational change in d-CRY that triggers its binding to TIM. Activated TIM is now receptive for JET binding, which targets TIM for proteasomal degradation by ubiquitination. Degradation of TIM leaves PER free and can be phosphorylated by DBT. Then, phosphorylated PER is ubiquitinated by SLIMB and thus, targeted for degradation in the proteasome. The second loop consists of two bZIP (Basic Leucine Zipper) transcription factors: the repressor VRI, and the activator PDP1, the transcription of which is also activated by CLK:CYC binding to E-box elements in both genes. VRI accumulates first during the night and binds to V/P box elements (consensus sequence TTATGTAA) blocking transcription of *Clk*. Later, PDP1ε outcompetes VRI for the V/P boxes and activates *Clk* transcription late in the night.

For years, the *Drosophila* circadian clock was thought to be the general model for insects. However, the characterisation of other insect circadian clocks depicted a more diverse scenario. In fact, the *Drosophila* type of circadian clock is not common among insects, being only shared by other drosophilids (Yuan et al., 2007). Except for drosophilids, the rest of insects encode a mammalian type *Cry* (*Cry-m*, also known as *Cry2* in insects), which in mammals is the main repressor in the negative feedback loop (Hardin, 2005; Dibner et al., 2010). Functional tests in *Drosophila* S2 cells revealed that insect CRY-m is not involved in light-induced TIM degradation, as the

CRY-d, but it is rather a potent transcriptional repressor of CLK:CYC in the negative feedback loop (Yuan et al., 2007). Additionally, there is a strong domain conservation between *Cry-m* of mammals and insects (Hirayama et al., 2003; Rubin et al., 2006). The diversity among insect circadian clocks also includes the absence of a *tim* orthologue gene in hymenopterans, in which *timeout* (also known as *Tim2*, the true orthologue of mammalian *timeless*) is probably the substitute of *tim* as the partner of PER and CRY-m (Rubin et al., 2006). Moreover, *Cry-d* is absent in Coleoptera and Hymenoptera (Yuan et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2013b). The presence of cryptochromes in Hemiptera depends on the suborder: heteropterans such as *Riptortus pedestris* (Ikeno et al., 2008) or *Pyrrhocoris apterus* (Bajgar et al., 2013) have only CRY-m, while the rest of hemipterans including aphids (Sternorrhyncha) have both CRY-d and CRY-m. Given that *Jet* participation in the circadian clock is related to *Cry-d* and *Tim*, those taxa that have lost both or one of them have also lost *Jet* (Cortés et al., 2010). Thus, three main types of insect circadian clock based on the presence or absence of different *Cry* orthologues were postulated by Yuan et al. (2007): 1) the drosophila type, in which *Cry-m* is not present being PER:TIM the main repressor of CLK:CYC mediated activity, and the clock is entrained by a *Cry-d/Tim/Jet* system; 2) the butterfly type in which both *Cry-d* and *Cry-m* are present as well as *tim*; and 3) the beetle type in which *Cry-d* and *Jet* are absent and the hymenopteran-type, in which *tim* is additionally absent.

The identification of the putative aphid circadian clock genes was facilitated by the sequencing, annotation and publication of the *Acyrtosiphon pisum* genome (The International Aphid Genomics Consortium, 2010), along with the genomic resources available at www.aphidbase.com (Legeai et al., 2010). In a previous work carried out in

our laboratory, the orthologous genes of the *D. melanogaster* circadian clock were identified in *A. pisum* (Cortés, 2010; Cortés et al., 2010). The preliminary characterisation of these genes led to the proposal of an aphid circadian clock model (see Figure 1.16), closer to the butterfly type described by Yuan et al. (2007) but having some peculiarities. Contrarily to drosophilids, that only have *Cry-d*, the aphid genome encodes both types of cryptochromes, *cry-d* and *Cry-m*, the latter having recently experienced a duplication. A blastp search with any of the two copies of the pea aphid *Cry2* (ACYPI006584 and ACYPI087167) in the *Myzus persicae* genome retrieved a single *Cry-m* sequence. This indicates that the duplication of *Cry-m* is probably specific of *A. pisum* or that one of the *Cry-m* copies has been lost in *M. persicae*. Another characteristic of the aphid circadian clock is the absence of the ubiquitin ligase *Jetlag* (*Jet*) in a system in which both *cry-d* and *tim* are present. This is striking given that *Jet* regulates *tim* degradation by the proteasome after a CRY-d conformational change triggered by the light at dawn. *Jet* has only been found missing in Coleoptera that have lost *cry-d*, and in Hymenoptera that have lost both *cry-d* and *tim*. Another aphid specific trait is the high rate of evolution found in the genes of the negative feedback loop: *Clk*, *cyc*, *per*, *tim*, and *cry2*, especially the latter three (Cortés, 2010; Cortés et al., 2010).

The characterisation of a complete CDS for the aphid *timeless* gene showed that it encoded a protein with a timeless domain (pfam04821). Moreover, the characterisation of *vri* transcripts in YR2 and GR strains produced an ORF that differed from previous characterisations (Cortés, 2010) and with predictions in Aphidbase. Interestingly, we have shown that most circadian genes exhibit extensive alternative splicing, although we were unable to find any correlation between specific transcript variants and any of the two

aphid strains reared under any of the two studied photoperiods (i.e. LD and SD). However, some of the transcript variants may generate truncated proteins that lack some of the conserved domains essential for its functionality within the circadian clock (e.g. see *Clk* and *cyc* splicing variants in Figure IV.3 and Figure IV.4, respectively). For instance, it was interesting the comparison of *tim-A* and *tim-B* variants (see Figure IV.2 A and B), in which the inclusion/exclusion of the NLS-containing exon 11 did not break the ORF. This could be associated to a possible regulation of the translocation to the nucleus of the transcription factor TIM, as it has been shown in *Drosophila* (Saez and Young, 1996). Specific quantification and knocking down of transcript splicing variants of the core circadian clock genes in aphid heads would shed light on their importance for the maintenance of clock oscillation. We do not discard the possibility that the splicing machinery in aphids has a high failure rate. Thus, the possible role, if any, of this extensive alternative splicing found in circadian clock genes remains to be further investigated.

The rhythmicity of the circadian clock genes was preliminary studied in *A. pisum* (Cortés, 2010). Our present results confirm a robust rhythmicity at the mRNA level of genes *per* and *tim* with a maximum at dusk (see Figure IV.7 and Figure IV.9). Moreover, assuming that the aphid CRY-m could probably participate as a repressor of the CLK:CYC heterodimer together with PER and TIM, aphid *cry-m* expression pattern would be expected to be similar to that of *per* and *tim*, which showed a peak of expression at dusk. These features have already been observed in other arthropods. For instance, the so called evening transcripts –*per* and *tim*– in *D. melanogaster* (Qiu and Hardin, 1996; Rosato and Kyriacou, 2001); genes *per*, *tim* and *cry-m* in the mosquitoes *Aedes aegypti* and *Culex quinquefasciatus* (Gentile et al.,

2009); *per* and *cry-m* in the honeybee *Apis mellifera* (Rubin et al., 2006); *per*, *tim* and *cry-m* in the cockroach *Rhyparobia maderae* (Werckenthin et al., 2012); *per* and *tim* in the blow fly *Protophormia terranovae* (Muguruma et al., 2010); *per* in the crickets *Gryllus bimaculatus* (Moriyama et al., 2008, 2009) and *Modicogryllus siamensis* (Sakamoto et al., 2009); *per* and *cry-m* in the wasp *Nasonia vitripennis* (Bertossa et al., 2014; Mukai and Goto, 2016); *per* and *cry-m* in the fire ant *Solenopsis invicta* (Ingram et al., 2012); *tim* in the firebrat *Thermobia domestica* (Kamae and Tomioka, 2012); or *per* and *tim* in the crustacean *Nephrops norvegicum* (Sbragaglia et al., 2015), among others.

On the other hand, even though the present data do not show a clear rhythm of *cyc*, *Pdp1* or *vri*, previous results obtained on pea aphid heads exhibited a circadian rhythm with a peak at dawn of *cyc* and *vri* transcripts, that is, in antiphase with *per* and *tim* (Cortés, 2010). However, the absence of a circadian rhythm at the mRNA level is not unprecedented. In fact, a lack of a robust mRNA rhythm was observed for some of the circadian clock genes of *Riptortus pedestris* (Ikeno et al., 2008). Nevertheless, a circadian rhythm at the protein level as seen in *Rhodnius prolixus* (Vafopoulou et al., 2010) or even in postranslational modifications (Yu et al., 2006) cannot be ruled out. A remarkable trait of the aphid circadian clock derived from our present work is the lower expression and the rapid dampening of *per* and *tim* under DD (continuous darkness, 0L:24D), in which the rhythm is notably lost already on the second subjective day (see Figure IV.9). The low expression in DD can be tentatively explained by the absence of TIM degradation induced by light. In continuous darkness, the destabilisation of the putative complex PER:TIM:CRY-m would be averted and consequently, PER:TIM:CRY-m would continuously repress CLK:CYC activation of *per* and

tim transcription. Hence the characteristic self-sustainability of circadian clock genes (Helfrich-Förster, 2005; Allada and Chung, 2010) is, at least, questionable in the pea aphid. It is important to recall here the works of Vaz Nunes and Hardie (1987, 2001), in which a dampened circadian oscillator model for the seasonal response of aphids is suggested as an alternative to the classical view of an hourglass-like system (see section 1.2.2). Under the instantly dampening circadian oscillator model, if the aphid *per* and *tim* are considered part of the circadian oscillator, their expression would undergo a quick dampening in DD conditions. Therefore, the aphid expression profiles of *per* and *tim* shown in Figure IV.9 support the dampened circadian oscillator model. The heavily dampened oscillator model has also been proposed to replace the hourglass model in the mite *Tetranychus urticae* (Saunders, 2010). In this regard, the analysis of the expression profiles of circadian clock genes in Chelicerata would shed some light on the issue.

Contrarily to previous results in which aphid *cyc* was found to peak close to dawn in antiphase to *per* and *tim* (Cortés et al., 2010), our data do not clearly support a transcript rhythm of *cyc* (see Figure IV.7 and Figure IV.9). Nonetheless, it is also possible that the expression of aphid *cyc* oscillates with very low amplitude, making it difficult to detect any circadian expression from the background changes in expression. The peak of expression of *cyc* in antiphase with *per*, *tim* and *cry-m* has been reported in other insect species (Rubin et al., 2006; Gentile et al., 2009; Ingram et al., 2012), or its functional equivalent in *Drosophila*, *Clk* (Allada et al., 1998; Özkaya and Rosato, 2012). Contrarily, in *R. pedestris* no significant diel oscillations were found in the expression of the circadian clock genes (Ikeno et al., 2008).

The second loop that constitutes the circadian clock, is based on genes *vri* and *Pdp1*, whose encoded proteins VRI and PDP1 accumulate in that order to repress and activate *Clk* expression in *Drosophila melanogaster*, respectively (Özkaya and Rosato, 2012). In the pea aphid, no significant circadian rhythm was found for *vri*, even though a consistent maximum of expression was detected at late night (ZT21), which agreed with the previous quantification of *vri* expression in *A. pisum* (Cortés, 2010). Regarding *Pdp1* expression, again no significant rhythmicity was observed in our present results, although a maximum of expression was found at late day or early night (ZT15). In this case, the expression of *Pdp1* did not agree with the previous quantification of *Pdp1* expression, which showed a synchronous expression with *vri* peaking at the end of the night (Cortés, 2010). The different profiles of expression of *vri* and *Pdp1* displayed in the pea aphid contrast with the synchronous increase of *vri* and *Pdp1* transcripts seen in *Drosophila* (Cyran et al., 2003), mosquitoes (Gentile et al., 2009), and with the expression of *vri* in advance of *Pdp1* seen in the fire ant *Solenopsis invicta* (Ingram et al., 2012). In *A. pisum*, *Pdp1* transcripts accumulate earlier than *vri* transcripts, a pattern that does not correlate with that seen for the proteins in *D. melanogaster* in which VRI accumulates first, followed later by an increase in PDP1ε levels (Cyran et al., 2003; Özkaya and Rosato, 2012). Nevertheless, even though the studies on the second loop genes in non drosophilids insects are scarce, the comparison of conserved domains in aphid CLK and CYC point to a circadian clock centred on *cyc* instead of *Clk* (Reppert, 2006; Rubin et al., 2006; Gentile et al., 2009), thus showing a circadian mechanism closer to mammals than to *Drosophila* (Looby and Loudon, 2005). However, given that in circadian clocks of non-drosophilids VRI and PDP1 would affect expression of *cyc*

instead of *Clk*, it would be expected a parallelism between maximum of expression of *Pdp1* and that of *cyc*, assuming there is no delay between *Pdp1* transcription and PDP1 synthesis, as it does occur in *Drosophila* (Cyran et al., 2003). If one observes the dynamics of expression of *vri* and *cyc* in the pea aphid, it can be seen that the peak of expression of *vri* is coincident with a trough or at least a decrease in *cyc* expression (see Figure IV.9). Therefore, our results would support a repressive role of VRI on *cyc* expression, although the order of accumulation seems different than that seen in *D. melanogaster*, (i.e. *Pdp1* and *vri* transcripts accumulate at unison, but only translation of *Pdp1* transcripts is delayed (Cyran et al., 2003). Regarding the putative role of *Pdp1* as an activator of *Clk* and *cyc* expression, it is significant the similarity of *Pdp1*, *Clk* and *cyc* expression profiles (see Figure IV.7 and Figure IV.9), specially those of *Pdp1* and *Clk*, that display almost coincident patterns. Additionally, it is also interesting the conservation of V/P-boxes observed in gene *cyc* in both *A. pisum* and *M. persicae* (see Figure IV.4 C), where Pdp1 could probably exert its transcriptional activation. Assuming *Pdp1* as the activator of *Clk* and *cyc* expression, it would imply that there would be no delay in translation of *Pdp1*.

The location and distribution of regulatory elements in the upstream regions of circadian clock genes agrees with some of the putative roles as part of the oscillatory mechanism. This is shown by the presence of conserved E-box elements in *per* and *Pdp1* (see Figure IV.1 C and Figure IV.5 C, respectively) that would agree with its transcription activation by CLK:CYC, as seen for other insects (Yu et al., 2006; Kobelková et al., 2010; Mohamed et al., 2014; Reppert et al., 2016). Gene *vri* also contained E-boxes and V/P-boxes, even though its distribution did not seem to be

conserved between *A. pisum* and *M. persicae*. Additionally, as previously mentioned, the presence and conservation of V/P-boxes in the 5' region of gene *cyc* between the two aphid species (see Figure IV.4 C), but not in gene *Clk* (see Figure IV.3 C) would support the view of a *cyc*-centred circadian clock, rather than a *Clk*-centred clock as in *Drosophila*.

The localisation of *per* and *tim* transcripts allowed to define three groups of neurons per brain hemisphere (see Figure IV.10 and Figure IV.12) that were named DN (dorsal neurons), LN (lateral neurons) and LaN (lamina neurons). However, quantification of expression of *per* and *tim* showed that in aphids of the YR2 strain reared under LD conditions there was a peak of expression at ZT15 followed by a trough at ZT21, which did not completely agree with the transcript localisation at different ZTs of *per* (see Figure IV.11) and *tim* (see Figure IV.13). Given that the quantification profiles do not include a sample at ZT18, we cannot be sure of the moment at which *per* and *tim* expression begins to be downregulated. Thus the drop in transcript levels could occur later between ZT18 and ZT21. Nevertheless, the localisation of *per* and *tim* transcripts in the aphid brain at ZT15 and their absence at ZT21 (see Figure IV.15) agreed with the quantification of these transcripts that showed a peak of expression at ZT15 and a trough at ZT21.

Our results on the localisation of clock gene transcripts allow to define the places where the central circadian clock may be located in aphids. The localisation of *per* and *tim* transcripts in the antero-dorsal *protocerebrum* and the regions between the *protocerebrum* and the lobula was similar to that found in other insects. A recent review by Numata et al. (2015) showed that the latter regions are usually associated with control of circadian

rhythms in flies (Helfrich-Förster et al., 1998; Yoshii et al., 2012), cockroaches (Reischig, 2003; Wen and Lee, 2008), the hemipterans *Rhodnius prolixus* (Vafopoulou et al., 2010; Vafopoulou and Steel, 2012) and *Riptortus pedestris* (Ikeno et al., 2014), and crickets (Okamoto et al., 2001). Even though there are very few studies on circadian rhythms in aphids, it seems that most of their activity would take place during the photophase. *Oviparae* of *Aphis spiraeicola* showed a circadian rhythm in sexual pheromone release with a peak during photophase (Jeon et al., 2003). The potato aphid *Macrosiphum euphorbiae* also displayed circadian rhythms in host finding (Narayandas and Alyokhin, 2006). In a recent work, aphid circadian rhythms were analysed independently of the host plant (Joschinski et al., 2016). In order to confirm a role of genes *per* and *tim* in the diurnal rhythmicity of aphids, it would be necessary to analyse the effect in the described rhythms of knocking down their expression. In addition, the effects on circadian rhythms of the bilateral surgical ablation of the LN cluster would also indicate the role of this neuron cluster in the control of circadian rhythms, if any.

The study of photoperiodism in insects has been characterised by the controversy on whether the circadian clock plays a central role in the regulation of the seasonal response or if, contrarily, it is controlled by an hourglass-like system in which no circadian oscillator is involved (see Photoperiodic clock in section I.2.2) (Saunders, 2010). However, evidence of participation of circadian clock genes in photoperiodic responses have been accumulating in recent years in different insect species (Pavelka et al., 2003; Sakamoto et al., 2009; Ikeno et al., 2010, 2011b, 2011c, 2013; Mohamed et al., 2014; Pegoraro et al., 2014; Meuti et al., 2015). Nevertheless, some authors claim that those results should be taken

cautiously, as the possibility of a pleiotropic effect (i.e. a role of a particular circadian clock gene independent of the circadian clock itself) could lead to misleading conclusions (Bradshaw and Holzapfel, 2007, 2010a, Emerson et al., 2009a, 2009b). In this respect, recent experiments in *Drosophila* analysed the effect of certain mutants of circadian clock genes in the seasonal response (Chill Coma Recovery time, CCRT) showing that the circadian clock genes as a module are involved in photoperiodic time measurement, rather than being a pleiotropic effect of a single gene (Pegoraro et al., 2014).

Aiming at elucidating a putative participation of circadian clock elements in the seasonal response of the pea aphid, their expression was compared between groups of aphids reared under two alternative photoperiods simulating summer and winter conditions (LD and SD photoperiods, respectively). In addition, we compared the expression of clock genes in two aphid strains, one exhibiting a robust photoperiodic response and a second strain that lacks this ability. Therefore, any element showing different patterns of expression between photoperiods and/or strains could be considered as a candidate to further studying its involvement in the photoperiodic response in aphids.

Regarding the expression patterns of circadian clock genes in the pea aphid, several differences were observed between aphids reared under LD and SD photoperiods in the holocyclic strain, while no such differences were observed in the anholocyclic strain. Focusing on the expression profiles of genes that constitute the negative feedback loop of the circadian clock (see *per*, *tim*, *Clk* and *cyc* expression in Figure IV.8), an evident change in transcription levels was observed between YR2 aphids

reared under LD and SD photoperiods that was not seen in the GR strain. This indicates that, whichever the role these genes play in the molecular mechanism of the seasonal response, their expression is differentially regulated by the photoperiodic conditions in the YR2 holocyclic strain but not in the anholocyclic GR strain. Since we did not identify new neuron clusters in YR2 aphids reared under SD conditions respect to those reared in LD, the increase in expression of these genes is probably a consequence of an activation of their expression in the same neuron groups (DN, LN, LaN). Nevertheless, our samples included other tissues beside the aphid brain that could be contributing to these increase of expression. In this regard, differences of expression levels could be confirmed by comparing the relative fluorescence with appropriate localisation of transcripts by means of fluorescent *in situ* experiments. Additionally, the fact that genes *per*, *tim*, *Clk* and *cyc* display this differential regulation depending on the photoperiod support their coordinated involvement in the negative feedback loop of the circadian clock. In this respect, assuming the putative role of CRY-m as a CLK:CYC inhibitor within the negative feedback loop (Zhu et al., 2008) associated with PER and TIM, it would be expected that its expression would also be higher in SD only for the holocyclic YR2 strain. In previous analysis of expression of circadian clock genes in heads of the pea aphid, *per* and *cry-m* showed higher expression under SD conditions (Cortés, 2010). Thus, the present findings that *per* is overexpressed under SD conditions agree with those previously found¹. However, the increase of expression in SD respect to LD in *Clk* and *cyc* in the holocyclic strain were not observed in previous quantification experiments (Cortés et al., 2010).

¹ The expression analysis of gene *tim* only included LD conditions due to problems with amplification (Cortés, 2010).

In regard of the genes involved in the positive feedback loop of the circadian clock, *vri* expression was upregulated in LD respect to SD in the GR strain, while mean transcript levels remained constant in YR2 aphids (see Figure IV.8). Especially relevant was the comparison of *vri* expression patterns along the day, which in the anholocyclic strain GR did not show evident fluctuation of expression, contrarily to the oscillating expression observed in YR2 aphids reared in LD and SD photoperiods (see Figure IV.7). Moreover, a closer inspection of *vri* expression in YR2 aphids showed a more or less concomitant profile between both photoperiods except for ZT21, in which the expression was upregulated in LD while was downregulated in SD (see Figure IV.7). The peak of expression of *vri* at ZT21 under LD conditions was further confirmed as can be seen in Figure IV.9, while the decrease in SD would need further confirmation with new independent quantitative experiments. Thus, as explained above for the genes of the negative feedback loop of the circadian clock, the differential expression between photoperiods of gene *vri* in different strains suggests a role in the seasonal response. The only gene that did not show changes in expression associated with a strain and/or photoperiodic conditions was *Pdp1* (see Figure IV.8). However, its participation in the seasonal response should not be completely discarded since postranslational regulation could still be important. Regarding the expression profile of *vri* (see Figure IV.8), both current and previous results (Cortés et al., 2010) coincide in the similar expression levels between LD and SD photoperiods in the holocyclic strain YR2. The increase of *Pdp1* expression in SD respect to LD is also found in both our results (see Figure IV.8) and previous analysis (Cortés et al., 2010).

If the genes of the circadian clock are involved in the regulation of the aphid seasonal response, changes in expression of some of these genes

would be expected in the holocyclic strain. Likewise, we would also expect that in the anholocyclic strain, which could be considered somewhat “blind” to photoperiodic changes, the expression of these genes would remain the same between photoperiods. Our results show that changes in expression between LD and SD photoperiods that are observed in YR2 but not in GR aphids, point towards a participation of at least some of the circadian genes in the seasonal response in *A. pisum*. In other insects, several studies have shown an effect of diapause inducing photoperiod (usually SD) in the regulation of circadian genes. The influence of the switch to winter photoperiod includes phase shifts in circadian clock genes (Iwai et al., 2006; Stehlík et al., 2008; Kobelková et al., 2010; Werckenthin et al., 2012), and an increase of circadian clock genes expression under SD respect to LD (Hodkova et al., 2003; Syrová et al., 2003; Doležel et al., 2005; Sakamoto et al., 2009; Bajgar et al., 2013). Some authors also compared mutant strains that do not enter diapause under winter photoperiod –equivalent to the anholocyclic strain GR– and found that the increase in expression of circadian clock genes under SD did not occur in the non diapausing mutant (Syrová et al., 2003), as seen in the pea aphid GR strain (see Figure IV.8). However, in other insects such as *Riptortus pedestris* (Ikeno et al., 2008), *Protophormia terranova* (Muguruma et al., 2010), *Nasonia vitripennis* (Mukai and Goto, 2016), *Bombyx mori* (Iwai et al., 2006) and *Culex pipiens* (Meuti et al., 2015), the change in photoperiodic conditions did not affect the overall transcript levels of circadian clock genes but rather their phase. The case of *Rhyarobia maderae* is special since slightly lower levels of expression of circadian clock genes were reported under SD respect to LD (Werckenthin et al., 2012), even though no photoperiodic response is known to occur in this tropical insect (Shiga, 2013).

Our results suggest that clock genes might play some role in the photoperiodic switch in the mode of reproduction in the aphid *A. pisum*. Nevertheless, in order to confirm the involvement of the circadian clock in the aphid seasonal response, a method to knock down the expression of circadian clock genes such as RNAi would certainly be useful. In this regard, RNAi has already been applied to aphids (Mutti et al., 2006; Jaubert-Possamai et al., 2007; Pitino et al., 2011). Assuming that circadian genes participate in the seasonal response of the pea aphid and that their function is conserved in insects, our prediction is that knocking down the expression of genes *per*, *tim* or *cry-m* in aphids reared in winter-like SD conditions would avert the seasonal response. On the other hand, the knocking down of *Clk* or *cyc* expression would induce the sexual phase in aphids reared under summer-like LD photoperiod. These predictions have been done after comparing the effect of knocking down the expression of circadian genes in other insect species, e.g. in *Chymomyza costata* (Pavelka et al., 2003), *Riptortus pedestris* (Ikeno et al., 2010, 2011a, 2011c, 2013; Omura et al., 2016), *Nasonia vitripennis* (Mukai and Goto, 2016) and *Culex pipiens* (Meuti et al., 2015). In all these species, knocking down of the negative elements of the circadian clock (i.e. *per*, *tim* or *cry-m*) avert diapause in SD conditions, while knocking down the positive elements in *R. pedestris* induced diapause in LD conditions. The case of *Antheraea pernyi* is particularly interesting. In this species the seasonal response (i.e. the termination of pupal diapause and emergence) is triggered by long days instead of short days. Thus, knocking down the expression of *per* in moths reared under short day conditions triggered pupal emergence (Mohamed et al., 2014). Therefore, there is a common pattern observed in insects in which the knocking down of *per* expression avoids seasonal response in

insects programmed to develop it, irrespective of being a LD or SD triggered seasonal response.

In this regard, it would be interesting to analyse the expression of the circadian clock genes in two closely related aphids species, *Pemphigus populitransversus* and *P. obesinymphae* of the Eriosomatinae subfamily (Moran, 1992). In *P. populitransversus* the sexual phase of the life cycle occurs in autumn-winter, while in *P. obesinymphae* there has been a shift in the life cycle and the sexual phase occurs in spring (Abbot and Withgott, 2004). The analysis would also benefit from the inclusion of anholocyclic strains of each of the species, if available (Blackman and Eastop, 2000). If the mechanism regulating the seasonal response in these species is conserved with the pea aphid, it would be expected that the expression of the circadian clock genes would increase under conditions inducing sexual phase, that would be SD in *P. populitransversus* and LD in *P. obesinymphae*. Moreover, it would also be interesting to test the effects in the seasonal response of knocking down different circadian clock genes. However, it is possible that the adaptation from a putative ancestral winter-linked sexual phase to a summer-linked sexual phase may be associated to downstream elements in the pathway of induction of sexuality. In this case, the expression of circadian clock genes would maintain the same regulation seen in both *Pemphigus* species.

As already described in the introduction, the study of insect photoperiodism has been characterised by a controversy on whether the circadian clock plays a crucial role in seasonal responses (see section 1.2.2). Košťál (2011) proposed that the photoperiodic system would theoretically consist of the following functional units: 1) a photoperiodic photoreceptor,

2) a photoperiodic clock or calendar that would discriminate between long and short photoperiods 3) a photoperiodic counter that would accumulate photoperiodic information and 4) output pathways. The localisation of some of these elements in aphids was previously addressed in a series of studies mainly performed on the aphid *Megoura viciae*, but also in the aphids *Acyrtosiphon pisum* and *Aphis sp.* These investigations showed that the photoperiodic receptors were located in the dorsomedial anterior region of the brain (see Figure I.13), while the hypothetical photoperiodic clock was suggested to reside in the *pars lateralis* of the *protocerebrum* (see Figure I.4) (Lees, 1964, 1981; Hardie and Lees, 1981; Hardie and Vaz Nunes, 2001). Furthermore, elements of the output pathway were also localised such as the NSC group I in the *pars intercerebralis* (see Figure I.5 A and Figure I.13 B) that under LD conditions would synthesise a yet unknown factor that the authors named virginoparin. This virginoparin would promote asexual reproduction in aphids under LD conditions and inhibition of its synthesis under SD conditions would induce the sexual response (Steel and Lees, 1977; Steel, 1978).

Our *in situ* hybridisation (ISH) experiments against *per* and *tim* transcripts revealed two regions of the aphid brain that expressed these two circadian genes: the DN (Dorsal Neuron) cluster located in the cortex of the *pars lateralis* –anterodorsal– of the *protocerebrum*, and the LN (Lateral Neuron) cluster located in the in the anterior cortex of the optic lobula (see Figure IV.10, Figure IV.12 and Figure IV.14). It should be noted that, interestingly, the DN cluster is located in the above described region previously found to be essential for the photoperiodic response (Steel and Lees, 1977; Steel, 1978). Indeed, microcauterisation experiments revealed that ablation of a group of NSC group I (Neurosecretory Cells) in the *pars intercerebralis*

prevented asexual reproduction in aphids reared under LD conditions that normally promote parthenogenesis. Moreover, the authors also found that destruction of the *pars lateralis*, a protocerebral region where we located neurons expressing *per* and *tim*, produced a depletion of neurosecretory material (i.e. the so called virginoparin) in the NSC group I also averting the asexual phase in aphids reared under LD conditions. Hence, the effect that the ablation of certain neurons in the *pars lateralis* exerted on the mode of reproduction could be consequence of the elimination of the DNs expressing *per* and *tim*, supporting an involvement of these genes in the aphid photoperiodic response. Furthermore, the location and distribution of the LN expressing *per* and *tim* found in a region known as the optic lobula (Kollmann et al., 2011) is similar to that of the so called NSC group V (see **Central nervous system** in section I.1.2). The ablation experiments performed by Steel (1978) involving the NSC group V had no effect on the seasonal response. Nevertheless, examination of the lesions described in that study (Steel and Lees, 1977) does not unambiguously tell if the lesions were large enough to encompass the LN cluster, although in a few cases the cauterisation of the optic lobes produced a delay in the photoperiodic response. Furthermore, in one of the 30 operated aphids the lesion reached the region close to the *protocerebrum*, presumably involving the lobula, where the LNs are located (Steel and Lees, 1977). Therefore, both the delay and the abolition of the photoperiodic response in aphids in which the optic lobe were cauterised suggest a participation of the LNs in the photoperiodic network that should be further investigated. In this respect, it would be interesting to explore the possibility of a double staining using para-aldehyde fuchsin along with *per* and *tim* ISH to determine if at least some of the NSC group V could correspond to the LN.

In case of co-staining, the LN cluster would correspond to the same cells of NSC group V, and could then be discarded as a region essential for photoperiodism. Ruling out the LNs as essential for the seasonal response would disagree with what has been described in other *Hemiptera* such as *Riptortus pedestris* (Ikeno et al., 2014) and also in drosophilids (Goto et al., 2009), in which clock neurons equivalent to the aphid LN are known to participate in the photoperiodic response.

The distribution of *per* and *tim* expressing neurons in the pea aphid is similar to that described in other insects in which these genes have been found in regions between the optic lobe and the *protocerebrum*, as well as in neurons in the anterodorsal *protocerebrum* that would respectively correspond to the LN and DN clusters here described for *A. pisum*. For instance, in *Drosophila melanogaster*, the circadian system consists of the morning and evening oscillators that reside in different sets of lateral neurons that express circadian clock genes (Yoshii et al., 2012). In *Protophormia terranova*, surgical ablation of the *pars lateralis* or *pars intercerebralis*, where PER immunoreactive neurons are located, affected the incidence of diapause (Shiga and Numata, 2000). In this insect, a second group of PER immunoreactive neurons, known as lateral neurons, was found to be involved in both circadian rhythms and seasonal response. Destruction of a subset of the lateral neurons known as the small ventral lateral neurons (s-LN_v) affected the circadian activity rhythms, while destruction of the large set (l-DN_v) affected the seasonal response (Shiga and Numata, 2009). In the hemipteran *Rhodnius prolixus*, a group of neurons homologous to the LN that express PER and PDF, a known circadian clock output, are known to regulate circadian secretion of PTTH (Vafopoulou et al., 2010, 2012). In *Plautia stali*, neurons located in *pars*

lateralis and *pars intercerebralis* of the *protocerebrum* are known to inhibit JH secretion from the *corpus allatum* (Matsumoto et al., 2013), although no localisation of circadian clock genes in these regions has been published so far. In *Riptortus pedestris*, removal of a group of neurons in the optic lobe medulla that expressed PDF, averted diapause under winter-like SD photoperiod (Ikeno et al., 2014). However, RNAi against *Pdf* did not affect the seasonal response of *R. pedestris*. It was then concluded that, even though PDF was not essential for diapause, the neurons containing PDF were essential. Therefore, it seems that regions in insect brains known to express circadian clock genes, i.e. the *pars lateralis* in the dorsal *protocerebrum* and regions between the *protocerebrum* and the optic lobes, are usually involved in regulation of circadian rhythms and photoperiodism (Numata et al., 2015).

As it has been achieved in other insects such as *Drosophila* (Helfrich-Förster et al., 2007) and cockroaches (Wen and Lee, 2008), it would be interesting to explore the detection of the proteins PER and TIM –and other circadian clock proteins– in the pea aphid for various reasons. First, it might allow to identify the axonic processes of DN and LN and thus, better appreciate the neuronal interactions between these clusters and other brain regions. This would eventually confirm the hypothesis of Steel and Lees (1977) who proposed that the short collaterals of NSC group I that end up above central body probably receive synaptic input from the photoperiodic neurons in the *pars lateralis*. Second, *per* and *tim* expression was rather low in the s-DN and in the LNs. Antibody detection of PER and TIM would confirm the number of cells in these neuron clusters and would possibly allow to better identify the scattered dorsal neurons that were barely detected by *in situ* hybridisation with *per* probes (see Figure IV.10). Third,

the protein detection with antibody fluorescent secondary antibodies would allow quantification by measuring the fluorescence of PER and TIM in the context of both circadian and seasonal rhythms. Finally, subcellular localisation of the transcription factors PER and TIM has been found to be an important step in circadian clock regulation (Meyer et al., 2006). Detection of these proteins with antibodies would allow to explore if this circadian feature is conserved in aphids.

2. Circadian clock output elements

Several possible outputs of the photoperiodic clock have been proposed. Among them, the involvement of hormones and neuropeptides in the regulation of the seasonal response –mainly diapause– has been widely studied in insects. In the next paragraphs, the possible involvement of PDF, melatonin and AANAT, and PTTH in the seasonal response of *A. pisum* will be discussed in the light of our results.

Pigment dispersing factor

The pigment dispersing hormone/factor (PDH/PDF) is a conserved neuropeptide that is found in the majority of Panarthropoda (Mayer et al., 2015). PDF is commonly expressed in a group of neurons in the medulla part of the optic lobe, from where these neurons send ramifications to the distal optic lobe and to the *protocerebrum* (e.g. in *Drosophila* see Figure IV.16 A). These PDF neurons are usually seen as the clock neurons, in which the central circadian pacemaker resides. In several insects, PDF has been demonstrated to be an output of the circadian clock governing circadian rhythmic activities (Hamanaka et al., 2005; Helfrich-Förster, 2009; Lee et al., 2009; Shafer and Yao, 2014). Interestingly, in *Riptortus pedestris* ablation of PDF expressing neurons alter the seasonal response, although RNAi against *pdf* expression had no effect on the response. This indicates that in *R. pedestris* the PDF neurons are essential for the seasonal response, although PDF is not required for it (Ikeno et al., 2014). Even though PDF has been identified in some Hemiptera such as *Meimuna opallifera* (Sato et al., 2002), *Riptortus pedestris* (Ikeno et al., 2014) and *Rhodnius prolixus* (Vafopoulou et al., 2007), we failed to identify an aphid PDF by Blastp and Tblastn searches

on the *A. pisum* genome. Moreover, the same searches also failed to identify PDF in the genome of *Myzus persicae*. Furthermore, attempts to detect PDF in *A. pisum* brains using two PDF antibodies failed (see Figure IV.16 B); one of these antibodies was raised against insect PDF and the second was raised against a crustacean β -PDH, both widely used to detect PDF in insects (Helfrich-Förster, 2009; Shafer and Yao, 2014). Additionally, PDF was not found in previous aphid peptidomic and transcriptomic analysis (Le Trionnaire et al., 2009, 2012; Huybrechts et al., 2010). Thus, it would seem that PDF is genuinely absent in aphids. However, the possibility that aphids contain a highly divergent PDF cannot be discarded. In Lepidoptera, corazonin is a marker of clock neurons, however, aphid corazonin was also absent in the transcriptomic and peptidomic analysis (Le Trionnaire et al., 2009, 2012; Huybrechts et al., 2010). Since PDF is the main circadian output in insects, this raises another question: assuming there is no PDF in aphids, what factor plays the circadian rhythm output conveyor of the circadian clock?

Melatonin and AANATs in the pea aphid

In mammals, melatonin is known to play a signalling role as an output of circadian clock as well as output of the photoperiodic calendar. The synthesis of melatonin by the pineal gland is controlled by N-acetyltransferases (AANAT) whose expression is under control of the central circadian clock that resides in the suprachiasmatic nucleus of the hypothalamus (Lincoln, 2006; Ikegami and Yoshimura, 2012). Melatonin is also known to be the principal output conveyor of circadian rhythms in mammals, as well as a photoperiodic token (Dardente et al., 2010; Wood and Loudon, 2014). The melatonin biosynthesis pathway is well conserved

Figure V.1. Melatonin biosynthetic pathway as generally described in mammals. Modified from Hardeland (2010).

in vertebrates, involving hydroxylation and decarboxylation of tryptophan giving serotonin, which is converted into N-acetyl serotonin by an arylalkylamine N-acetyltransferase (AANAT). N-acetyl serotonin is then carboxylated by an hydroxyindole-O-methyltransferase (HIOMT) giving melatonin (Figure V.1). In general, the rate limiting enzyme in melatonin biosynthesis is the penultimate enzyme AANAT, which controls the rhythmic circadian levels of this indoleamine (Klein, 2007). However, the role of melatonin in circadian and seasonal rhythms in insects has been less investigated. Nevertheless, few studies in insects (IV.6) showed concomitant levels of melatonin and NAT (N-acetyl transferase) enzymatic activity in different tissues, mainly brain and haemolymph. Additionally, the quantification of melatonin in some insect species generally revealed higher levels during the scotophase. Although the melatonin biosynthetic

Table V.1. Summary of melatonin detection and quantification in insects. Moment of peaks of melatonin content and NAT (N-acetyl transferase) enzymatic activity are indicated by D (day), N (night) or None (no differences).

Species	Order	Tissue/Organ ¹	MLT peak	NAT activity Peak	Photoperiod	Method ²	Author	Year
<i>Locusta migratoria</i>	Orthoptera	CE	-	-	15L:9D	RIA, GC-MS	Vivien-Roels	1984
<i>Periplaneta americana</i>	Blattodea	BR, OL	N	-		RIA	Binkley	1987
<i>Musca autumnalis</i>	Diptera	BR	-	-		RIA	Wetteberg	1988
<i>Drosophila sp</i>	Diptera	H	-	-	12L:12D	2D-TLC, MS, RIA	Finocciaro	1990
<i>Ischnura verticalis</i>	Odonata	H, WO	N	-	13.5L:10.5D	RIA	Tilden	1994
<i>Enallagma civile</i>		H, WO	None	-	12L:12D			
<i>Bombyx morii</i>	Lepidoptera	H, HL	N	N	12L:12D	HPLC-fluorometric, RIA	Itoh	1995
<i>Gryllus bimaculatus</i>	Orthoptera	CE, BR, P	N	-	12L:12D	HPLC-fluorometric	Itoh	1995
		C, OP, Ant, HDL, Ov	D	-				
		L, MP, DT	None	-				
<i>Trichoplusia ni</i>	Lepidoptera	PC, OL, SOG, TGM, HL	N	-	14L:10D	HPLC-ECD	Linn	1995
		PC, SOG	N	-	6L:18D, 12L:12D, 18L:8D			
		PC, OL, SOG, TGM	N	-	14L:10D, DD			
		PC, OL, SOG, TGM	None	-	LL			
<i>Drosophila melanogaster</i>	Diptera	WO	D	None	12L:12D	RIA	Hintermann	1996
<i>Acyrtosiphon pisum</i>	Hemiptera	WO	None	-	16L:8D, 12L:12D	RIA	Gao	1997
<i>Gryllus bimaculatus</i>	Orthoptera	Eg	N	N	12L:12D vs DD	HPLC fluorometric, RIA	Itoh	1998
<i>Rhodnius prolixus</i>	Hemiptera	HL	N	-	12L:12D	RIA	Gorbet	2003
<i>Ischnura graellsii</i>	Odonata	BR	N	N	15L:9D	HPLC-ECD	Vieira	2005
<i>Oedipoda caerulescens</i>	Orthoptera	BR	N	N	12L:12D			
<i>Periplaneta americana</i>	Blattodea	BR, RT, HL	N	N	12L:12D, DD	RIA	Bembenek	2005
<i>Apis sp</i>	Hymenoptera	H	D, N	-	12L:12D	RIA	Yang	2007
<i>Dianemobius nigrofasciatus</i>	Orthoptera	H	-	N	16L:8D	only NAT activity	Izawa	2009
<i>Antheraea pernyi</i>	Lepidoptera	BR, SOC	N	Early N	16L:8D >12L:12D	RIA	Mohamed	2014
<i>Acyrtosiphon pisum</i>	Hemiptera	WO	-	-	16L:8D	ESI-HPLC-MS/MS	Escrivá	2016
<i>Acyrtosiphon pisum</i>	Hemiptera	WO	None	-	16L:8D < 12L:12D	ESI-HPLC-MS/MS	Barberá	-

1 Ant, antenna; BR, brain; C, cercus; CE, compound eyes; DT, digestive tube; Eg, eggs; HL, haemolymph; H, head; HDL, hind leg; L, legs; Mp, Malpighian tubes; OL, optic lobe; Ov, ovaries; OP, ovipositor; P, palps; PC, *protocerebrum*; RT, retina; SOC, suboesophageal complex; SOG, suboesophageal ganglion; TGM, thoracic ganglionic mass; WO, whole organism.

2 ECD, electrochemical detection; ESI, electrospray ionization; GC-MS, gas chromatography mass spectrometry; HPLC, high performance liquid chromatography; RIA, radio immunoassay; 2D-TLC, 2D thin layer chromatography.

pathway is well conserved in vertebrates, it has been less investigated in invertebrates. In fact, insects lack true vertebrate-like AANAT (v-AANAT), but instead have insect specific AANAT called insect-type AANAT (i-AANAT), being both types classified as Gcn5-related N-acetyltransferases (GNAT¹). Indeed, phylogenetic analysis showed that v-AANAT and i-AANAT group in different clusters (Barberà et al., 2013; Falcón et al., 2014; Hiragaki et al., 2015).

If we consider a recent study in the lepidopteran *Antheraea pernyi* (Mohamed et al., 2014), the present work is the second report of *in situ* localisation of melatonin in the central nervous system of insects and, to our knowledge, the first to localise melatonin in the ganglia. The aforementioned report described two pairs of melatonin neurons found in the dorsal *protocerebrum* of *Antheraea pernyi* (Mohamed et al., 2014). In the aphid *A. pisum*, however, the melatonin neurons have been located in the ganglia, including the SOG and the TGM, but not in the *protocerebrum* (see Figure IV.17). Even though there are no previous reports on *in situ* localisation of melatonin in the ganglia, quantification of melatonin in the SOG and TGM of the lepidopteran *Trichoplusia ni* were previously reported (Linn et al., 1995). In addition, despite the absence of melatonin neurons in the aphid brain, some of the ganglionic melatonin neurons showed axonic processes that extended into the *protocerebrum* (see Figure IV.17 C). Moreover, the end of these axons could be traced to the posterior contralateral neuropils in the SOG and TGM forming arborisations and varicosities. These structures were similar to the primary protocerebral arborisations identified with PDF antibodies in *Rhodnius prolixus* by

¹ Members of this protein family catalyze the transfer of acetyl from acetyl-CoA to different substrates.

Vafopoulou et al. (2010), that were described as neuronal connections through dendrites of local neurons. In the pea aphid, these structures could provide input to other melatonin neurons in order to elicit a coordinated response. Moreover, axons running towards the *protocerebrum* showed similar arborised structures, producing two main processes that ventrally run into the *protocerebrum* reaching medial and dorsolateral regions. These protocerebral melatonin arborisations reached regions near the anterior *protocerebrum* and therefore, could hypothetically provide connections between the DN expressing *per* and *tim* in the *protocerebrum* and the melatonin neurons in the ganglia. Furthermore, the protocerebral melatonin axons could also have contact to the NSC group I found in the *pars lateralis* (see **Photoperiodic effectors** in section I.2.2). The hypothetical synaptic connections between DN, melatonin neurons and virginoparin neurons (i.e. NSC group I) opens the possibility that the photoperiodic information may be relayed in that order to finally regulate virginoparin production in the NSC group I. In this respect, detection of PER and TIM proteins with fluorescent antibodies would allow to visualise the DN axons and help to better identify any possible neuronal connections with melatonin neurons.

The comparison of melatonin localisation between aphid strains reared under different photoperiods did not reveal evident differences in signal strength or distribution of melatonin. Nonetheless, a common developmental pattern was found in all strains and photoperiods analysed. Melatonin was initially restricted within the soma, close to the nucleus, from L1 to L3 (first and third larval instar, respectively). From L3 onwards, melatonin was mobilised into the axons and finally, in older aphids, it was mainly present in the axons, being virtually absent in the soma (see Figure

IV.17 C). The distribution of melatonin neurons in the ganglia (see section IV.2.2) was very similar to that described for NSC stained with paraldehyde fuchsin (PAF) in the aphid *Megoura viciae* (Steel, 1977). The common patterns of cell distribution suggests that the melatonin neurons and the NSC could actually be the same cells. However, while melatonin was already detected in L1 aphids, the PAF staining was undetectable until the L3 (Steel, 1977). In addition, PAF staining is specific to disulphide bonds, thus excluding melatonin from detection with PAF (Panov, 1980). Moreover, the PAF stained neurons in the ganglia described by Steel (1977) were located ventrally, while MEL-in revealed in the present work were found in the dorsal region of the ganglia. In any case, a combined approach including melatonin detection with antibodies and PAF staining would answer whether the NSC in the SOG and the TGM described by Steel (1977) correspond to the melatonin neurons revealed in the present work. It was interesting that the timing of melatonin mobilisation in L3 was coincident with the appearance of PAF stained neurosecretory material in the NSC. This suggests the possibility that the activation of synthesis of peptides containing disulphide bonds in the NSC found in the ganglia may be regulated by melatonin. In this regard, the appearance of PAF staining in L3 aphids could depend on the mobilisation of melatonin and consequent signalling in the NSC cells via melatonin axonic processes described in the ganglia (see Figure IV.17 D). This hypothesis could be tested by treating aphids with luzindole –a MEL receptor antagonist– followed by observation of the effect on the PAF staining on ganglionic NSC.

The methodology previously used for melatonin quantification in insects (see IV.6) usually involved the use of radioactivity, even in recent publications (Bembenek et al., 2005; Yang et al., 2007; Mohamed et al.,

2014). In collaboration with Dr. G. Font, Dr. G. Meca and the PhD student L. Escrivá from the “Departament de Medicina Preventiva i Salut Pública, Ciències de l’Alimentació, Toxicologia i Medicina Legal” of “Universitat de València”, we developed a quick and economical extraction procedure as well as a sensitive and specific detection and quantification ESI HPLC-MS/MS method that avoids manipulation of radioactive isotopes (Escrivá et al., 2016). Quantification of melatonin in aphids by HPLC MS/MS led to two main conclusions. First, no significant differences of melatonin levels between ZT6 and ZT18 were found (see Figure IV.18 A). This view contrasts with the night peak of melatonin commonly observed in other insects (see IV.6). Nevertheless, similar levels of melatonin between day and night were also reported in the brain of the damselfly *Enallagma civile* (Tilden et al., 1994). Moreover, our results agree with previous melatonin quantification in whole aphids reared under LD and SD conditions showing no significant differences between mid-photophase and mid-scotophase melatonin content (Gao and Hardie, 1997). However, the fact that our melatonin quantification was performed in whole aphids that may include melatonin produced in other tissues, including embryos, could be masking a putative circadian rhythm of melatonin in the central nervous system. Also, the inclusion of only two time points in our experiment could have hindered the observation of a putative melatonin circadian rhythm. It would be then recommended to carry out additional quantification experiments on aphid heads, as well as increase the moments of sampling along the day to completely discard a potential melatonin rhythm. The second conclusion that could be assumed from the quantification analysis is that in the YR2 holocyclic strain, melatonin content was higher in aphids reared under SD than in LD conditions, while melatonin levels remained the same under

both photoperiods in the GR anholocyclic strain (see Figure IV.18 B). This result disagrees with previous melatonin quantification in aphids, which showed lower content of melatonin in SD respect to LD (Gao and Hardie, 1997). However, the discrepancy between our results and those of Gao and Hardie (1997) can be explained by the different procedures followed to obtain the SD aphids. In our case, we transferred the first generation (G0) to SD in L3, while Gao and Hardie (1997) transferred them as young adults. Some of the melatonin quantification experiments in insects summarised in IV.6 included quantification in LD and SD photoperiods, although none applied statistical analysis to compare melatonin content between photoperiods. One of the studies in Lepidoptera reported no difference in melatonin content between insects reared in 6L:18D, 12L:12D and 18L:6D photoperiods (Linn et al., 1995). However, it was not clearly described how long the analysed pupae were in the new photoperiods. In other studies, melatonin levels even showed a trend to be higher in LD respect to SD, e.g. in the aphid *A. pisum* (Gao and Hardie, 1997) and the moth *Antheraea pernyi* (Mohamed et al., 2014). However, in *Antheraea pernyi* the photoperiodic response refers to the termination of diapause triggered by LD photoperiod, thus the response would still be associated to a high melatonin content, despite the change of photoperiodic conditions. Moreover, the present melatonin analysis is the first that systematically analyses differences between photoperiods in both holocyclic (photoperiodic responsive) and anholocyclic (non photoperiodic responsive) strains. It is also the first in which an increase of melatonin in individuals reared in SD photoperiod is reported, a response similar to what has been described in mammals (Dardente et al., 2010; Yoshimura, 2010; Dardente, 2012; Hazlerigg, 2012). In concordance with our results

reporting higher melatonin content in SD reared holocyclic aphids, Gao and Hardie (1997) demonstrated that continuously melatonin-fed aphids reared under LD conditions mimicked a DD response, producing a partial induction of the seasonal response in which the progeny consisted of males and intermediate parthenogenetic/oviparous females (Lees, 1989). This suggests a role of melatonin in the signalling pathway of the photoperiodic response, although the precise role in the machinery is yet to be studied. In this context, high melatonin levels would act as a token of SD photoperiod, signalling the switch to sexual progeny development. The effect of melatonin in the aphid seasonal response could be tested by treating aphids with luzindole, an antagonist of the yet unidentified melatonin aphid receptors, that hypothetically would avert the induction of sexual morphs under SD conditions. Recently, melatonin and dopamine have been postulated as antagonist partners in the photoperiodic counter of *Antheraea pernyi* (Mohamed et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2015). In *Periplaneta americana*, melatonin has been shown to inhibit vitellogenin synthesis in the fat body, which is usually associated with ovarian development (Kamruzzaman et al., 2016). Additionally, Kamruzzaman et al. (2016) also found that melatonin inhibited the expression of *JHAMT* (*JH acid O-methyltransferase*) and *FAMet* (*farnesoic acid O-methyltransferase*) genes that encode enzymes involved in JH synthesis. This would provide the mechanisms by which the increase of melatonin in SD observed in holocyclic aphids (see Figure IV.18 B) would activate the switch from parthenogenetic to sexual development by downregulating vitellogenin synthesis and JH titre. In this context it is worth to note that JH is known to regulate diapause incidence in several insects (Denlinger et al., 2012; Goodman and Cusson, 2012), among other roles in regulation of

development and control of polyphenisms. The role of JH has also been studied in aphids, in which only JH-III was detected (Corbitt and Hardie, 1985). Among other studies, it was found that topically applied JH to aphids reared under SD produced a partial reversion to parthenogenesis (Hardie, 1981), and that low JH titters as a consequence of the overexpression of JH esterase, that increases the degradation of JH, were correlated to sexual morph development (Tagu et al., 2005; Ishikawa et al., 2012).

Furthermore, the hypothetical role of melatonin neurons in the pea aphid as a relay of photoperiodic information from DNs to the NSC group I (the neurons producing the so called virginoparin) could also be investigated in aphids by observing the effect of luzindole in the PAF staining of NSC group I on aphids reared in different photoperiodic conditions.

In addition to the melatonin content analysis, the candidate genes to encode for enzymes that regulate the melatonin synthesis in aphids were also investigated. In *A. pisum*, four genes, derived from two recent duplication events, have been identified (Barberà et al., 2013). The phylogenetic analysis showed that the four genes grouped close together in a single clade within the monophyletic cluster of i-*AANAT* (Barberà et al., 2013). The analysis of expression of the four aphid i-*AANAT* genes in the context of the circadian rhythms and photoperiodism revealed a lack of clear circadian rhythmicity (see Figure IV.22). Although changes in day and night NAT enzymatic activity have been reported in several insects (see IV.6), day/night changes in *AANAT* expression have only been reported in *Periplaneta americana* (Bembenek et al., 2005) and *Antheraea pernyi*

(Mohamed et al., 2014) apart from our own in *A. pisum* (Barberà et al., 2013).

The analysis of aphid AANAT expression in different photoperiods and strains (see Figure IV.23) showed a significant increase of expression of aphid *AANAT1*, *AANAT2* and *AANAT3* in YR2 aphids reared under SD compared to aphids reared under LD. On the other hand, in the GR strain, this increase was observed for genes *AANAT1*, *AANAT2* and *AANAT4*. Comparison of AANAT expression profiles (see Figure IV.23) allowed to identify concomitant patterns of *AANAT3* with the melatonin content (see Figure IV.18), both showing an increase in SD respect to LD conditions in YR2 aphids but not in GR aphids. In addition, even though there was an increase of *AANAT2* expression in SD in GR strain, its levels were lower than those found in YR2 aphids (see Figure IV.23). Thus, the correlation between the higher expression of *AANAT2* and *AANAT3* and the increase of melatonin levels in SD with respect to LD specific to the YR2 strain suggests a role for *AANAT2* and *AANAT3* in the regulation of melatonin biosynthesis. We explored this putative role of *AANAT2* and *AANAT3* by trying to colocalise their transcripts with melatonin, in a similar approach to that described by Mohamed et al. (2014). Although a similar pattern of expression between the two *AANAT* genes and melatonin was observed, our results did not show a colocalisation of aphid *AANAT2* and *AANAT3* with melatonin (see Figure IV.24), apparently ruling them out as regulators of melatonin biosynthesis. At this point, different hypothesis could explain the relation between melatonin levels and *AANATs*. It was demonstrated that melatonin was present in L1 aphids, but was not until L3 that melatonin was mobilised into the axons (see Figure IV.18 B). If melatonin synthesis is restricted to the first three larval stages and, from then on, only

transported into the axon without further synthesis, the *AANAT* involved in melatonin synthesis would only be expressed during the first three larval stages. This could be easily tested by quantifying and localizing the transcripts of each of the four *AANATs* by *in situ* hybridisation in L1 to L3 aphids. Another hypothetical explanation could be that different steps of melatonin synthesis may be located in different neurons. This would require that the penultimate and rate-limiting step would take place in the neurons expressing *AANAT2* or *AANAT3* and that its product –N-acetylserotonin– would be transported to the melatonin neurons where the last enzymatic step HIOMT (Hydroxindole-O-methyltransferase) would take place. If *AANAT2* and *AANAT3* are definitely discarded as regulators of melatonin biosynthesis, *AANAT1* and *AANAT4* would still remain as candidates. However, the expression profile of *AANAT1* analysed in young adult aphids that have recently moulted exhibited a particular decrease in time, with some degree of variation with strain and photoperiods (see Figure IV.22). This profile would agree with a participation of *AANAT1* in the sclerotisation and tanning process of the final moult, in which it has been shown that NAT activities that convert dopamine into melanin are involved (Zhan et al., 2010; Noh et al., 2016). In this context, it is important to recall the previous studies on aphid cuticle maturation reviewed by (Gallot et al., 2010), in which N-acetyl transferase activities have been shown to participate in cuticle sclerotisation. To further investigate this hypothetical role of *AANAT1* in sclerotisation, quantification of its expression in aphids sampled at different times before and after a moult will be revealing. Nevertheless, the hypothetical role of *AANAT1* in tanning and sclerotisation could be producing an expression profile that may be masking the expression of *AANAT1* associated with a putative role in melatonin

biosynthesis. In order to confirm an involvement of AANAT1 in the synthesis of melatonin, colocalisation of its expression with melatonin would certainly provide an answer to this issue.

Prothoracicotropic Hormone

PTTH has been found to relay circadian information in the hemipteran *Rhodnius prolixus* (Steel and VaFopoulou, 2006) and various lepidopteran species (Smith and Rybczynski, 2012; Mohamed et al., 2014). It is known that the prothoracicotropic hormone (PTTH) is synthesised by neurosecretory cells in the brain, from where it is released to the prothoracic glands (PG), where it regulates ecdysteroidogenesis (Steel and VaFopoulou, 2006; VaFopoulou et al., 2007; Smith and Rybczynski, 2012). Thus, PTTH controls the moulting process through the regulation of ecdysteroid synthesis and release. Recently, the synthesis and release of PTTH in *Antheraea pernyi* was shown to be under control of two pairs of circadian clock neurons that produce a rhythmic expression of *i-AANAT* and consequently, a circadian rhythm of melatonin. It was also shown that melatonin activates specific receptors in adjacent neurons that synthesise PTTH (Mohamed et al., 2014). In a similar way, *in vitro* experiments in *Periplaneta americana* showed that melatonin regulated the production and release of PTTH. In turn, PTTH induced a dose dependent release of ecdysteroids by the PG, which was inhibited by the MEL receptor antagonist luzindole (Richter et al., 2000). PTTH not only participates in the circadian rhythms, it has also been shown to participate in some cases in the regulation of the insect seasonal response. In some insect species, low PTTH and ecdysteroid levels have been related to larval and pupal diapause (Denlinger et al., 2012). However, generally adult diapause –an arrest in

reproduction— is not thought to be regulated by PTTH because of the degeneration of PG associated with adulthood. However, it has been reported that synthesis of ecdysteroids takes place in the gonads of adults (Nelson et al., 2009). Even though low PTTH release and ecdysteroid levels in haemolymph have been correlated with embryo and larval diapause, and in some insects with adult diapause (Denlinger et al., 2012), a direct involvement in the sexual morph development in aphids would need further research due to several reasons. First, aphid PTTH was missed in previous transcriptomic (Cortés et al., 2008; Le Trionnaire et al., 2009, 2012; Gallot et al., 2010; Huybrechts et al., 2010) and peptidomic (Huybrechts et al., 2010; Le Trionnaire et al., 2009) studies. In the present work, the pea aphid gene encoding PTTH has been reported for the first time. Moreover, the aphid *Ptth* gene was identified and characterised in a holocyclic and an anholocyclic strains (see Figure IV.26). In addition, a predicted protein highly similar to the *A. pisum* PTTH sequence was also identified in the *Myzus persicae* genome. Both sequences showed a high degree of conservation, specially in the putative mature peptide (see Figure IV.25). Furthermore, in the pea aphid we have localised the sites of expression of *Ptth* transcripts in the dorsal *protocerebrum* (see Figure IV.27). The PTTH neurons were found in apposition to the DN cluster which, as already discussed, expresses the circadian clock genes *per* and *tim* (see Figure IV.28). The place and distribution of the neurons expressing PTTH was similar to that found in other insects. With respect to the localisation of aphid PTTH, previous experiments in aphids demonstrated that ablation of NSC group II located in the dorsal *protocerebrum* altered the moulting and tanning process concluding that the NSC group II were the aphid PTTH expressing neurons (Steel, 1978). The number and distribution of PTTH

neurons that we have identified (see Figure IV.27 and Figure IV.28) correspond to the so called NSC group II. However, as already proposed for NSC group V, colocalisation of PTTH transcripts with paraldehyde fuchsin staining, would further confirm this hypothesis.

Even though a circadian rhythm in PTTH levels or release has been reported in several insects (Sauman and Reppert, 1996b; McBrayer et al., 2007; Vafopoulou et al., 2007; Mohamed et al., 2014), we did not observe evident differences in staining strength at different moments of the day in *A. pisum* (see Figure IV.27 D and E). In lepidopteran species, low ecdysteroid levels resulting from a decrease in PTTH levels have been related to diapause (Smith and Rybczynski, 2012). Moreover, as already discussed, termination of diapause in Lepidoptera is related to an increase of PTTH expression consequence of regulatory input from the adjacent clock neurons via melatonin signalling (Mohamed et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2015). On the contrary, in *Culex pipiens* slightly higher PTTH expression was found under SD diapause-promoting conditions (Zhang and Denlinger, 2011). In the hemipteran *Rhodnius prolixus*, PTTH has also been demonstrated to participate in the synchronisation of the autonomous clock in prothoracic glands in conjunction with insulin-like peptides (ILP) (Vafopoulou and Steel, 2014). Considering that the aphid PTTH neurons do, in fact, correspond to the NSC group II, a direct involvement of PTTH in the seasonal response of aphids could be discarded *a priori* as it was demonstrated that destruction of NSC group II neurons had no effect on the morph determination in *Megoura viciae* (Steel, 1978). However, a role of PTTH in the output pathway of the aphid circadian clock cannot be discarded and should be addressed in future investigations through the quantification of expression of the *Ptth* gene along the day/night cycle.

Considering our different results altogether, the present thesis provides new advances in the knowledge on the circadian system and some of the elements that may regulate the seasonal response in aphids. A summary of the localisation of different elements analysed is shown in Figure V.2. As previously discussed, microcauterisation and RNAi experiments will be needed to unequivocally associate the DN group of neurons and *per* and *tim* expression within them to the seasonal response in *A. pisum*. The putative modulator role of the LN in the seasonal response, as suggested from ablation experiments performed by Steel and Lees (1977), would also need clarification using the same approaches. Given the absence of effect on the photoperiodic response after ablation of NSC group II (Steel, 1978), that we have shown to be the neurons expressing *Ptth*, a direct role of PTTH as conveyor of photoperiodic information in the aphids is discarded. On the other hand, we have provided evidence to support a role of melatonin in the aphid seasonal response. Although some of the identified *AANAT* genes showed expression patterns concomitant with those of melatonin suggesting an involvement in melatonin synthesis, this hypothesis was not confirmed by our results on the localisation of *AANAT* transcripts. Nevertheless, we could not localise the expression of two of the four *AANATs*, thus leaving them still as candidates, specially *AANAT1*. Further experiments involving luzindole treatment that blocks melatonin receptor and RNAi against the aphid *AANAT* genes would provide the answers to this issue. This thesis provides the basic neuroanatomical knowledge of the aphid circadian system from which future studies on the photoperiodic response hopefully will take advantage.

Figure V.2. Summary of neuroanatomical localisation of the different elements included in the thesis in the *A. pisum* brain. The DN (dorsal neuron cluster) includes two subgroups of neurons: the l-DN (large DN) cluster expressing *tim*, and the s-DN (small DN) cluster coexpressing *per* and *tim*. Additionally, *per* and *tim* are coexpressed in the LN (lateral neuron) group that is subdivided into dLN (dorsal LN) and vLN (ventral LN). *Ptth* was expressed in two pairs of cells adjacent to the DN cluster. Melatonin (MEL) was found in several neurons in the SOG and the TGM, from which axons arose innervating the ganglionic masses and the *protocerebrum*. These melatonin axons reaching the *protocerebrum* may produce synaptic contact with DN and NSC group I. Localisation of *AANAT2* and *AANAT3* transcripts was conspicuous and therefore it was not included for clarity.

VI. Conclusions

1. Gene transcripts from the full set of genes at the core of the pea aphid circadian clock, including genes *period*, *timeless*, *Clock*, *cycle*, *Pdp1* and *vriille* have been completely characterised. Transcript characterisation revealed extensive alternative splicing for clock genes that, nevertheless, could not be related with any of the parameters studied (i.e. aphid strain, aphid body section, moment of the day or photoperiod conditions).
2. The analysis of expression showed a robust rhythm of *per* and *tim* genes, both peaking at dawn, but not for the other circadian clock genes. Moreover, *per* and *tim* expression was rapidly dampened under DD conditions, which supports the model of a dampened circadian oscillator to explain the seasonal response in aphids.
3. The conservation between *A. pisum* and *M. persicae* of putative regulatory elements in 5' regions of genes *per*, *cyc* and *Pdp1* support the role of these genes in the circadian clock. Moreover, the conservation of these elements in *cyc* but not in *Clk* points towards a *cyc*-centred circadian machinery.
4. Localisation of transcripts of *per* and *tim* allowed to identify three groups of neurons that were named DN (dorsal neurons), LN (lateral neurons) and LaN (lamina neurons). The DNs were found in the anterodorsal *protocerebrum* and could be subdivided into l-DN (large DN) expressing *tim* and s-DN (small DN) expressing both *per* and *tim*. The LNs were found in the optic lobe lobula and could be subdivided into LN_d (dorsal LN) and LN_v (ventral LN), all expressing *per* and *tim*. The LaN group was located in the posterior region of the lamina of the optic lobe expressing *per*.

5. Localisation of *per* and *tim* transcripts at different times of the day/night cycle confirmed the peak of expression of these genes at ZT15 and the trough at ZT21.
6. *In situ* analysis in aphids of the holocyclic and anholocyclic strains reared in LD and SD conditions showed specific differences in the localisation of *per* expression in YR2 aphids reared in LD, but not in *tim* transcript localisation.
7. Comparison of expression of circadian clock genes between aphids of the YR2 and GR strains in different photoperiodic conditions revealed that genes constituting the negative feedback loop of the putative aphid circadian clock (*per*, *tim*, *Clk*, *cyc* and probably, *cry-m*) share a differential regulation between photoperiods only in the holocyclic YR2 strain. Additionally, expression of gene *vri*, involved in the positive feedback loop of the circadian clock, also displayed this differential regulation.
8. Accumulated evidence, including the absence of a homologous *Pdf* gene in the aphid genome together with previous failed attempts to identify it in transcriptomic and proteomic analysis and our failure to detect PDF with antibodies, suggest that PDF may be genuinely absent in aphids.
9. Melatonin has been localised for the first time in aphids and Hemimetabola. It is the first time that melatonin has been localised in insect ganglia and shown its mobilisation pattern along aphid development. No major differences in melatonin content have been

found in the day/night cycle, although its role in aphid circadian rhythms should be further investigated.

10. A significant increase in melatonin content has been shown to occur in aphids reared under short day conditions (i.e. determined to produce sexual morphs) when compared with aphids kept under long day, parthenogenetic promoting, photoperiodic conditions. However, no evident differences in melatonin localisation between aphids reared under different photoperiod conditions were observed.
11. Four insect-type *AANAT* genes have been identified in the aphid genome. These genes possess typical GNAT characteristics and their transcripts have been experimentally characterised.
12. Increased expression of genes *AANAT1*, *AANAT2* and *AANAT3* in aphids of the holocyclic strain reared under short day conditions was observed. In the anholocyclic strain genes overexpressed in aphids reared under short day conditions were *AANAT1*, *AANAT2* and *AANAT4*, instead of *AANAT3*.
13. The expression patterns of *AANAT1*, *AANAT2* and specially, *AANAT3*, suggest a role of these genes in the synthesis of melatonin. The localisation of *AANAT2* and *AANAT3* transcripts in the ganglia revealed a distribution similar, but not concomitant with that of melatonin. Thus, their involvement of these *AANAT* genes in the synthesis of melatonin and in aphid photoperiodism deserves further investigations. In particular, the localisation of *AANAT1* could be relevant for the issue.

14. The aphid *Ptth* gene has been successfully identified and characterised. Its transcripts have been experimentally characterised and localised in the aphid brain. Localisation of *Ptth* transcripts allow us to propose the brain cells where it is expressed as the previously described NSC group II. Consequently, an essential direct role of PTTH in the aphid seasonal response is discarded.

VII. Resum en valencià

Introducció

Els pugons o àfids són insectes hemimetàbols que pertanyen a la família Aphididae dins de l'ordre Hemiptera. Aphididae està constituïda per unes 4700 espècies de pugons majoritàriament distribuïdes per l'hemisferi nord. Els pugons són animals fitòfags que s'alimenten de la saba de les plantes hoste gràcies a unes peces bucals modificades en forma d'estilet. Algunes espècies són especialment nocives per als cultius com a conseqüència dels danys directes pel consum de nutrients de la planta així com per la transmissió de fitovirus.

Els pugons són especialment interessants per la seua plasticitat fenotípica, que és la capacitat d'un organisme amb un genotip concret de desenvolupar diversos fenotips com a resposta front a diversos canvis en l'entorn. En el cas dels pugons, els canvis en l'entorn donen lloc a la formació de fenotips discrets alternatius o polifenismes (i. e. morfcs). Aquesta plasticitat fenotípica és la base de la complexitat dels cicles biològics dels pugons, que es poden classificar en dos tipus: les espècies heteroècies (o dioiques) en les que el cicle de vida alterna entre dos tipus de plantes (normalment una llenyosa i una herbàcia), i les espècies monoiques en les que el cicle transcorre íntegrament en un hoste (normalment herbaci). Entre els polifenismes que conflueixen als pugons, cal destacar el dimorfisme de dispersió (pugons alats vs. pugons àpters) i el polifenisme reproductiu (pugons partenogenètics vs. pugons sexuats). Aquest últim és el que serà objecte d'estudi en aquesta tesi doctoral. El polifenisme reproductiu és un exemple d'adaptació a l'estacionalitat, atorgant a aquests insectes la capacitat de colonitzar les regions

temperades. L'espècie que s'ha utilitzat en aquesta tesi, *Acyrtosiphon pisum*, desenvolupa un cicle vital monoic. Durant les estacions favorables (primavera i estiu) els pugons es reproduïxen partenogènèticament, és a dir, femelles vivíparas partenogèniques donen lloc a la següent generació de femelles partenogèniques. En arribar la tardor, la disminució del fotoperíode (i. e. les hores de llum del cicle dia/nit) induïx la formació dels morfs sexuals —mascles i femelles— que després de copular produeixen ous de resistència a les dures condicions de l'hivern en els quals ocorre una diapausa embrionària. A principis de la primavera, els ous desclouen donant lloc a una nova generació de femelles partenogèniques. Donat el paper crucial del fotoperíode, la resposta estacional dels pugons (i d'altres organismes) també es coneix com a fotoperiodisme. En la natura es donen soques holocíclics que segueixen el cicle de vida complet com el descrit dalt, però en les zones on els hiverns són suaus també es donen soques anholocíclics que han perdut la fase sexual i per tant, es reproduïxen per partenogènesi al llarg de tot l'any.

Les bases moleculars que controlen la resposta estacional es coneixen més profundament en mamífers, en els quals la participació del rellotge circadià és clara. El rellotge circadià està constituït per factors de transcripció que conformen bucles de retroalimentació que produeixen un oscil·lador autònom, també conegut com a nucli del rellotge circadià. En insectes, s'ha estudiat principalment en *Drosophila*, en el que el rellotge està constituït per dos bucles principals: el negatiu, conformat per l'heterodímer CLK:CYC que activa la transcripció dels gens *per* i *tim*, les proteïnes dels quals inhibeixen l'activació de la seua pròpia transcripció mitjançada per CLK:CYC; i el positiu, conformat per CLK:CYC que activa l'expressió dels gens *vri* i *Pdp1* (les proteïnes dels quals són repressors i activadors transcripcional,

respectivament). La base de l'oscil·lació es dona gràcies a que en les regions 5' dels gens del rellotge hi han elements reguladors conservats anomenats E-box (seqüència consens CACGTG) als quals s'uneixen els complexos CLK:CYC i PER:TIM, i V/P-box (seqüència consens TTATGTAA) als quals s'uneixen els homodímers VRI:VRI i PDP1:PDP1. Aquest oscil·lador se sincronitza amb el medi extern principalment per la llum mitjançant proteïnes fotoreceptores CRY-d (criptocrom tipus *Drosophila* o CRY1) que constitueixen la via d'entrada del rellotge circadià. L'estudi del rellotge circadià d'altres insectes, no obstant, posà de manifest certa diversitat en el tipus de rellotge circadià, depenent dels gens que el conformen: 1) el tipus *Drosophila* present en drosòfílids en el que *cry-m* (criptocrom tipus mamífer) està absent, 2) el tipus papallona present en la majoria d'insectes, en el qual, a més de *cry-d* n'hi ha un altre criptocrom ortòleg al de mamífers (*cry-m* o *cry2*), i 3) el tipus que es dona en escarabats, en el qual *cry-d* i *Jetlag* estan absents, i himenòpters, en els quals addicionalment està absent *tim*. En treballs previs es van identificar un conjunt de gens que podrien formar part del rellotge circadià en el pugó del pèsol *A. pisum* els quals conformaven un rellotge tipus papallona (presència de *cry-m* i *cry-d*) però amb la particularitat de que *Jetlag* està absent. A més es trobà que els gens que conformen el bucle negatiu (*per*, *tim*, *Clk*, i *cyc*) mostren altes taxes d'evolució, especialment *per*, *tim* i *cry-m* (*cry2*).

En mamífers, l'oscil·lador central del rellotge es troba al cervell, concretament al nucli supraquiasmàtic de l'hipotàlem, el qual controla la resta de rellotges circadians de l'organisme mitjançant diverses hormones i vies neuronals que conformen l'eixida del rellotge circadià. La principal senyal d'eixida del rellotge circadià de mamífers és la melatonina, la qual regula diverses ritmicitats circadianes com els cicles de son/vigília o

temperatura corporal. A més a més, també s'ha demostrat que la melatonina participa en la mesura del fotoperíode, indicant així si l'organisme està experimentant dies llargs típics de l'estiu, o si pel contrari, està en condicions de dies curts comuns en la tardor i l'hivern.

En insectes, no obstant, la participació del rellotge circadià en la resposta estacional ha sigut un tema recurrent de debat. Aquest fet afavorí la proposició de diversos mecanismes per a explicar la resposta estacional en insectes. Entre tots, els més importants són els models de «Coincidència externa» i «Coincidència interna», els quals assumeixen la participació del rellotge circadià en la resposta estacional. En el model de «Coincidència externa» la llum té dos funcions: sincronitza un oscil·lador autònom amb el fotoperíode extern i determina la duració del fotoperíode mitjançant la il·luminació de la fase fotosensible al final de la nit. Així, en fotoperíodes llargs la fase fotosensible es vorà il·luminada, mentre que en fotoperíodes curts aquesta es manté en obscuritat. En el model de «Coincidència interna», la duració del fotoperíode es determina per la relació entre les fases de dos oscil·ladors, un sincronitzat amb l'alba i l'altre amb el crepuscle. La participació del rellotge circadià en el fotoperiodisme s'ha demostrat mitjançant el cultiu d'aquests organismes en fotoperíodes complexos. No obstant, el fet de que aquests experiments en pugons i àcars no donaven resultats típics d'altres insectes, conduí a la formulació d'un tercer model independent del rellotge circadià conegut com a «Rellotge d'arena». En aquest model, la duració del fotoperíode es mesura per l'acumulació d'un factor que se sintetitza en obscuritat. Per tant, en dies curts típics de l'hivern (nits llargues) aquest factor s'acumula per sobre d'un llindar que activa la resposta estacional, mentre que aquest llindar no se sobrepassa durant els dies llargs (nits curtes). Nogensmenys, finalment

es va formular un model circadià amb un oscil·lador esmorteït el qual explica el patró atípic en la inducció de sexuals quan els pugons es crien en fotoperíodes complexos.

Com s'ha mencionat abans, en mamífers la melatonina és un element crucial tant en la regulació dels ritmes circadians com en la resposta estacional o fotoperiodisme. La síntesi de melatonina es produeix a la glàndula pineal, que està sota el control del rellotge circadià central en el nucli supraquiasmàtic de l'hipotàlem. La regulació es dona a nivell del penúltim enzim en la ruta de síntesi de melatonina, l'arilalquilamina N-acetil transferasa (AANAT), que activa la producció de melatonina durant l'obscuritat. En diversos insectes s'ha trobat un ritme en els nivells de melatonina amb un màxim durant la nit que estaria suggerint un paper d'aquesta com a transmissor de la informació circadiana. No obstant, cal tindre en compte que els ritmes circadians en la locomoció en insectes depenen principalment del neuropèptid PDF (Pigment Dispersing Factor), la síntesi del qual es produeix en les neurones del rellotge i està sota control del mateix rellotge circadià. El paper de la melatonina i la seua regulació via AANATs no està tan clara en insectes. En primer lloc, la comparació de les seqüències de les AANATs d'insectes amb les de vertebrats va mostrar que aquests dos grups no són homòlegs. Malgrat això, estudis recents en el lepidòpter *Antheraea pernyi* han demostrat que la melatonina se sintetitza rítmicament en neurones que contenen el rellotge circadià via control d'expressió d'AANAT. La melatonina actua com a missatger en cèl·lules adjacents, en les quals produeix una síntesi rítmica de PTH (en anglès *prothoracicotropic hormone*, hormona protoracicotròpica), que finalment activa una síntesi d'ecdisteroids en la glàndula protoràtica, també rítmica.

En estudis previs realitzats en el nostre laboratori es van identificar i caracteritzar de manera preliminar els gens que conformen el putatiu rellotge circadià del pugó *Acyrtosiphon pisum*. Es trobà que els elements que el conformen estan conservats amb animals. En aquesta tesi a més de caracteritzar en detall els gens del nucli del rellotge circadià de pugons, s'ha estudiat la possible implicació en la resposta estacional dels pugons de diversos elements del rellotge circadià. El treball inclou la comparació de diversos elements en dues soques de l'especie *Acyrtosiphon pisum* —la soca holocíclica YR2 i l'anholocíclica GR— a més del cultiu sota condicions de fotoperíode llarg (en anglès, long day, LD) i fotoperíode curt (en anglès, short day, SD). Amb aquest arranjament, només en pugons de la soca holocíclica YR2 crescuts en condicions de SD es produeix la formació de sexuats, mentre que la soca anholocíclica GR fa el paper de «mutant sense fase sexual». En concret s'ha comparat l'expressió circadiana del gens del nucli del rellotge circadià (*period*, *timeless*, *Clock*, *cycle*, *Pdp1* i *vri1*), incloent la comparació entre les diferents soques i fotoperíodes. A més, s'ha localitzat l'expressió dels gens *period* i *timeless* en el cervell mitjançant sondes d'ARN. Pel que respecta a l'eixida del rellotge circadià, s'ha estudiat la possible implicació de la melatonina i de les AANATs en la resposta estacional de pugons. En aquest apartat s'ha estudiat la localització de la melatonina en el sistema nerviós central del pugó en diversos estadis larvaris i s'ha quantificat mitjançant ESI-HPLC MS/MS en adults. A més, s'ha quantificat l'expressió de quatre gens codificants d'AANAT de tipus insecte identificats al pugó i s'ha explorat la seua implicació en la síntesi de melatonina mitjançant colocalització amb melatonina. Finalment, s'ha identificat, validat i caracteritzat el gen que codifica PTTH en pugons, i a més s'ha obtingut la localització de la seua expressió en el protocervell.

Objectius

Els objectius d'aquesta tesi s'emmarquen dins d'un projecte més ample orientat cap a la investigació del paper del rellotge circadià o alguns dels seus components en el control de la resposta estacional dels pugons. En particular, aquesta tesi està centrada en l'anàlisi de dos conjunts d'elements que conformen la maquinària circadiana: els gens del nucli del rellotge circadià i els elements que putativament puguen constituir l'eixida del rellotge en el pugó model *Acyrtosiphon pisum*. Aquest objectiu general s'ha desenvolupat mitjançant els següents objectius específics:

- 1 Completar la caracterització dels gens *period*, *timeless*, *Clock*, *cycle*, *Pdp1* i *vriille*, que conformen el nucli del rellotge circadià en el pugó del pèsol *A. Pisum*.
- 2 Caracteritzar i quantificar l'expressió dels gens del nucli del rellotge circadià tant en el context dels ritmes circadians com del fotoperiodisme.
- 3 Localitzar l'expressió dels gens *period* i *timeless* en el cervell del pugó i, a més, comparar-la amb regions prèviament descrites com a rellevants per a la resposta estacional.
- 4 Identificar, caracteritzar i determinar la localització dels elements putatius de l'eixida del rellotge, incloent el neuropèptid PDF, l'hormona melatonina junt amb els gens *i-AANAT*, i l'hormona PTTH.
- 5 Quantificar els nivells de melatonina i l'expressió dels gens *AANAT* de pugó tant en el context dels ritmes circadians com del fotoperiodisme.

- 6 Investigar el paper que podrien tindre els gens AANAT en la regulació de la síntesi de melatonina en el pugó.

Metodologia

Els pugons es mantenen en fase partenogenètica en cambres amb fotoperíode 16L:8D a 18°C. En aquest treball s'han utilitzat dues soques: YR2 és la nostra soca holocíclica de referència, la qual desenvolupa la fase sexual sota fotoperíodes curts com 12L:12D; GR és la nostra soca anholocíclica de referència, la qual es manté sempre en fase partenogenètica incloent-hi en fotoperíodes curts. En els experiments en els qual s'han comparat pugons de les dues soques i en fotoperíodes 16L:8D (Long Day, LD) i 12L:12D (Short Day, SD) la inducció s'ha portat a terme de la següent manera. Per a cadascuna de les soques, individus sincronitzats de la primera generació (G0) en estadi larvari 3 (L3) s'han dividit en dos grups. El primer grup es mantingué en LD, mentre que el segon es passà a condicions de SD. La generació següent (G1) es manté en les condicions de fotoperíode dels parentals i es mostregen en arribar a adults. Per tant tindrem per a cada soca dos grups de pugons: LD G1 i SD G1. En la soca holocíclica YR2, els pugons de SD G1 pariran els sexuals (G2), i per tant es coneixen com a *sexuparae*. La efectivitat del procés d'inducció es comprova observant la presència de pugons sexuals en YR2 i l'absència en GR.

Per a la caracterització dels gens s'han utilitzat diverses tècniques generals de biologia molecular tals com extracció de RNA, síntesi de cDNA, PCR, purificació de DNA, clonació en vectors, transformació de *Escherichia coli* i seqüenciació de Sanger. A més, la quantificació de l'expressió s'ha

aconseguit mitjançant RT-qPCR i amb quantificació relativa utilitzant el mètode $\Delta\Delta C_T$. Les diferències d'expressió entre moments del dia, fotoperíodes i soques s'han avaluat mitjançant ANOVA. A més, per a determinar si l'expressió segueix un ritme circadià s'ha aplicat una anàlisi COSINOR.

La localització *in situ* dels transcrits dels gens *period*, *timeless*, *ptth* i les *AANATs* s'ha portat a terme en cervells de pugons amb sondes d'ARN marcades amb digoxigenina (DIG) detectades amb anticòs anti-DIG conjugat amb fosfatasa alcalina. Com a substrat de la fosfatasa alcalina s'han utilitzat dos substrats: NBT/BCIP que produeix un substrat blau i Fast Red / HNPP que dóna un substrat roig i fluorescent.

La localització de melatonina en el sistema nerviós central dels pugons s'ha aconseguit amb un anticòs comercial contra melatonina i amb dos anticossos secundaris de diferents fluoròfors. Addicionalment, s'ha desenvolupat un protocol per a la detecció conjunta de melatonina i transcrits d'*AANATs*.

Les preparacions de localització *in situ* tant de transcrits com de melatonina s'ha portat a terme amb un microscopi òptic i d'epifluorescència. Les imatges de «stack» s'han obtés amb un microscopi laser confocal.

Finalment, es desenvolupà un mètode ESI HPLC-MS/MS per a la quantificació de melatonina específic de pugons en col·laboració amb el Departament de Tecnologia d'Aliments i Toxicologia de la Universitat de València.

Resultats

Respecte als gens del nucli del rellotge circadià, s'ha pogut completar la caracterització del gen *timeless*. A més, s'han descrit diverses variants d'empalmament alternatiu per als transcrits dels gens *period*, *timeless*, *Pdp1*, *vri* i especialment per a *clock* i *cycle*. Encara que no s'ha trobat cap especificitat d'alguna variant a cap soca o fotoperíode, cal assenyalar que en alguns casos produeixen codons de parada al principi de la proteïna, mentre que en altres afecten a segments peptídics que codifiquen senyals de localització nuclear, un factor que podria ser rellevant donat que es tracta de factors de transcripció que exerceixen la seua funció en el nucli. La recerca d'elements reguladors en la regió 5' del gen ha permés identificar elements E-box conservats en *period* i *Pdp1*, i V/P-box en *cycle* i *vri*. El paper dels gens del nucli del rellotge circadià requereix una oscil·lació en la seua expressió. L'anàlisi de l'expressió d'aquests al llarg de 1,5 dies en pugons de la soca YR2 crescuts en LD ha confirmat la ritmicitat en els nivells d'expressió dels gens *period* i *timeless*, amb un pic cap al final del la fotofase. No s'ha trobat un ritme evident en l'expressió de la resta dels gens circadians. A més, en pugons YR2 crescuts en SD s'ha pogut observar un canvi en el patró d'expressió respecte al de LD en els gens *per*, *tim* i *vri* que no s'han donat en la soca GR. La comparació entre soques i fotoperíodes dels nivells mitjans d'expressió dels gens del rellotge mostrà dos canvis interessants. El primer, es dona un augment de l'expressió dels gens que conformen el bucle negatiu del rellotge circadià (*per*, *tim*, *Clk* i *cyc*) en SD respecte a LD en la soca holocíclica YR2, mentre que en la soca anholocíclica GR els nivells d'expressió d'aquests gens es mantenen igual entre fotoperíodes. El segon canvi s'observa en els nivells d'expressió de

vri, el quals es mantenen semblants entre fotoperíodes en la soca YR2, mentre que s'observa un augment en SD respecte a LD en la soca GR. L'anàlisi d'expressió dels gens *per* i *tim* en DD (obscuritat contínua), permeté avaluar la capacitat d'auto-sostenibilitat de l'oscil·lació en l'expressió d'aquests gens. Es pot apreciar que l'amplitud de l'expressió al llarg del cicle dia/nit subjectius es veu ràpidament disminuïda arribant a perdre el ritme a partir del segon cicle dia/nit.

La localització dels transcrits dels gens *per* i *tim* en el cervell del pugó ens ha permés identificar tres grups de neurones que expressen gens circadians. En la part anterodorsal de cada hemisferi del protocervell trobem un grup d'unes 10 neurones anomenat *Dorsal Neurons* (DN, neurones dorsals), el qual es pot subdividir en: *large DN* (l-DN, DN grans) que expressen *tim*; i *small DN* (s-DN, DN menudes) les quals expressen *per* i *tim*. El segon grup, localitzat a la regió proximal del lòbul òptic coneguda com a medul·la, l'hem anomenat *Lateral Neurons* (LN, neurones laterals) i coexpressen ambdós gens *per* i *tim*. Aquest està format per dos subgrups que contenen una *dorsal LN* (LNd, LN dorsal) i 3-4 *ventral LN* (LNv, LN ventrals). Addicionalment, s'ha trobat en la part distal del lòbul òptic coneguda com a làmina un grup de 4 neurones amb expressió de *per*, les quals hem anomenat *Lamina neurons* (LaN, neurones de la làmina). La distribució d'aquests tres grups de neurones s'ha analitzat en pugons de les dues soques (YR2 i GR) crescuts en dos condicions de fotoperíode (LD i SD). A més, en cada cas s'han inclòs dos moments del cicle dia/nit corresponent al dia i a la nit (ZT6 i ZT18¹, respectivament). Pel que fa a la localització del transcrits de *per*, s'ha vist que durant el dia (ZT6) el transcrit es detecta en

¹ZT: *zeitgeber time*, indica el nombre d'hores des del començament de la fotofase, la part il·luminada del cicle dia/nit.

els DN i les LN en tots els casos. No obstant, no es detectaren transcrits de *per* en cap soca ni fotoperíode durant la nit (ZT18), excepte en pugons de YR2 crescuts en LD. Respecte a la localització de l'expressió de *tim*, en aquest cas es pogué detectar en els dos moments del cicle dia/nit sense diferències entre soques ni fotoperíodes. Donat que les anàlisis d'expressió en pugons de la soca YR2 crescuts en LD mostraren un pic d'expressió a ZT15 i un mínim a ZT21, el fet de que els transcrits es localitzaren a ZT18 indicaven una certa contradicció. Amb experiments de localització addicionals de *per* i *tim* incloent un mostreig a ZT15 i a ZT21 es confirmà la detecció de transcrits a ZT15 mentre que no s'observaren nivells detectables a ZT21, per tant concordant amb els resultats de quantificació de l'expressió.

En insectes, PDF és el principal element d'eixida del rellotge circadià i constitueix un factor regulador de diversos ritmes circadians. Es troba àmpliament distribuït, no només en insectes, sinó en artròpodes en general. Malgrat la seua ubiqüitat, no s'han trobat prediccions d'un gen homòleg a *Pdf* en el genoma d'*A. pisum*, ni tampoc s'ha trobat en anàlisis transcriptòmiques o peptidòmiques. La regió codificant del pèptid madur de PDF està altament conservat en Panarthropoda, cosa que ha facilitat la seua detecció i localització mitjançant anticossos en diverses espècies. Nosaltres hem intentat localitzar el putatiu PDF de pugons mitjançant anticossos desenvolupats contra PDH de crustacis i PDF de *Drosophila*, ambdós àmpliament utilitzats per a detectar PDF en diversos insectes. En cap cas hem aconseguit localitzar el PDF homòleg de pugó, per tant donant suport a la hipòtesi de que PDF està absent en pugons. No obstant, donat que són evidències negatives, no podem afirmar categòricament que el genoma de pugons no conté un homòleg de PDF.

En mamífers, els ritmes circadians estan regulats principalment pels nivells de melatonina, els quals normalment mostren un pic durant la nit. Els nivells de melatonina estan sota control del rellotge circadià principal, que resideix al nucli supraquiasmàtic de l'hipotàlem i regula els nivells de melatonina produïts en la glàndula pineal mitjançant la regulació d'expressió de l'enzim AANAT. A més, la melatonina també és un dels factors principals en la regulació de la resposta estacional de mamífers. El paper de la melatonina en ritmes circadians i fotoperiodisme no està tan clar en insectes. En el present treball, hem detectat i localitzat la melatonina per primera volta en un insecte hemimetàbol, i és el primer cas de localització de melatonina en neurones dels ganglis nerviosos en insectes. Les neurones amb immunoreactivitat a l'anticòs contra melatonina (en anglès, *melatonin immunoreactive neurons*, MEL-in) es troben distribuïdes en el gangli subesofàgic (en anglès, *suboesophageal ganglion*, SOG) i la massa ganglionar toràcica (en anglès, *thoracic ganglionic mass*, TGM). Al SOG s'han identificat 8 MEL-in distribuïdes per parelles, concretament cada neuròmer conté dues parelles de MEL-in. Pel que fa a la TGM, s'han trobat un total de 14 MEL-in distribuïdes en dues parelles per cada neuròmer toràcic (T1, T2 i T3) i dues MEL-in en la regió posterior del TGM corresponent als ganglis abdominals. L'anàlisi de la distribució de melatonina en els sistema nerviós central en pugons de les dues soques i crescuts en els dos fotoperíodes sota estudi no revelà cap diferència específica. No obstant, l'estudi de la distribució de melatonina en pugons de diferents estadis larvaris i adults de diferents edats revelà que la melatonina estan concentrada principalment en els soma de les MEL-in des de L1 fins a L3. A partir d'aquest estadi, la melatonina comença a mobilitzar cap als axons, que es creuen en la regió ventral amb els axons de les MEL-in

contralaterals. La melatonina arriba finalment a innervar el neuropil contralateral i, en els adults més vells (uns 9 dies des de l'última muda), es pot apreciar una depleció de melatonina en el soma, quedant només en els axons. Cal destacar 2 processos axònics que sorgeixen del SOG, van cap al protocervell per la part ventral i finalment innerven zones laterals i antero-dorsals.

A més de la localització de melatonina, també es van quantificar els seus nivells en dos moments del cicle dia/nit en pugons de les dues soques estudiades crescuts en diferents fotoperíodes mitjançant la tècnica ESI HPLC-MS/MS¹. En primer lloc, es va observar que no hi havia diferències significatives entre els nivells de melatonina en diferents moments del dia (ZT6 i ZT18) en cap de les soques o fotoperíodes estudiats. En segon lloc, hem trobat un augment dels nivells de melatonina en pugons de la soca holocíclica YR2 crescuts en SD respecte dels crescuts en LD, mentre que aquest augment no es va observar en la soca anholocíclica GR. Per tant, hi ha un augment dels nivells de melatonina associat a la resposta fotoperiòdica.

També s'han estudiat els gens *AANAT* d'*A. pisum*, que podrien codificar el penúltim enzim en la síntesi de melatonina i són candidats a controlar els seus nivells. Primerament, es va fer un cerca al genoma de gens homòlegs a *Dat* (Dopamine N-acetyl transferase) de *Drosophila* i *AANAT* de *Bombyx mori*. S'identificaren fins a 4 homòlegs en *A. pisum* anomenats *AANAT1* fins a *AANAT4*, els quals codifiquen les respectives seqüències aminoacídiques que agrupen en el mateix clade que les *AANATs* d'insectes (insect-like *AANAT* o i-*AANAT*). Tots ells contenen el domini N-acetil transferasa comú a

¹Electrospray ionisation high performance liquid chromatography acoblada a un analitzador masses/masses.

totes les GNAT², incloent els motius C, D, A i B, a més dels residus que conformen el lloc d'unió d'acetil CoA. Donat que l'expressió dels gens AANAT són candidats a estar baix el control del rellotge circadià, es realitzà una cerca d'elements reguladors. Malgrat la presència de diverses E-box i V/P-box en tots els 4 gens d'*A. pisum* i *M. persicae*, només es trobà cert grau de conservació en les regions 5' dels gens *AANAT1* i *AANAT3*. Addicionalment, l'expressió dels 4 gens que codifiquen les AANAT es va analitzar en pugons de les dues soques objecte d'aquest estudi crescuts en condicions de LD i en SD al llarg d'un dia i mig. Es pogué observar que cap de les AANATs s'expressa de manera circadiana segons l'anàlisi amb el mètode COSINOR, encara que algunes d'elles, com l'*AANAT3* tenen un patró que podria semblar-se al circadià. D'altra banda, la comparació dels valors d'expressió mitjans entre fotoperíodes indicà que per a *AANAT1*, *AANAT2* i *AANAT3*, s'hi donà un augment d'expressió en SD respecte a LD en pugons de la soca YR2, mentre que en la soca GR aquest patró s'observà en *AANAT1*, *AANAT2* i *AANAT4*.

Considerant que almenys algun dels gens *AANAT* d'*A. pisum* podria estar controlant la síntesi de melatonina, cabria esperar que la seua expressió es localitzara en les MEL-in esmentades abans. Aquesta qüestió s'abordà amb una localització combinada amb anticossos contra melatonina i sondes contra cadascun dels transcrits dels gens *AANAT*. Només es pogué detectar l'expressió per a *AANAT2* i *AANAT3*, els quals s'expressen en els ganglis nerviosos (SOG i TGM) i en tot el sistema nerviós central, respectivament. No obstant, en cap dels casos es colocalitzà la melatonina amb els transcrits d'*AANAT*.

2GCN5-related N-acetyl transferases.

L'hormona protoracicotropa (PTTH) és un neuropèptid d'insectes que se sintetitza en certes neurones del protocervell i s'allibera a l'hemolimfa des del *corpus cardiacum* o el *corpus allatum*. La seua funció principal és l'activació de la síntesi d'ecdisteroids en les glàndules protoràciques. Recentment, s'ha vist que podria formar part de l'eixida del rellotge circadià en l'hemípter *Rhodnius prolixus* i el lepidòpter *Antheraea pernyi*, per tant vinculant PTTH als ritmes circadians i a la resposta estacional. Malgrat que s'ha buscat el gen homòleg a PTTH en diversos estudis transcriptòmics i proteòmics, aquest neuropèptid important en la regulació de la muda en insectes ha romàs sense identificar durant anys. En el present treball s'ha identificat per primera volta una predicció no anotada del gen que codifica la PTTH en *A. pisum* (ACYPI37989), que dóna un pèptid amb baixa conservació a nivell de seqüència, com ocorre entre les PTTHs d'insectes. La predicció del transcrit es validà mitjançant PCR i seqüenciació dels fragments obtinguts. No obstant, el transcrit codificaria per a un pèptid que sí conserva la presència de residus de cisteïna, generalment involucrats en la formació de ponts disulfur intra- i intermoleculars rellevants en l'estructura terciària del pèptid, a més d'una sèrie de pèptids senyals hidrofòbics i el pèptid madur, en el qual la conservació és major.

Donat que el gen *Ptth* també podria estar baix la regulació del rellotge circadià, es portà a terme una cerca d'elements reguladors en la regió 5' del gen, el qual conté diverses E-box i V/P-box, algunes d'elles particularment conservades en les dues espècies de pugons *A. pisum* i *M. Persicae*.

A fi de confirmar la identitat d'aquest gen com a *Ptth* es portà a terme una localització de l'expressió d'aquest en cervells de pugó. Es trobà que el gen candidat a *Ptth* s'expressa en la regió antero dorsal del protocervell en dos

parells de neurones. Aquesta disposició anatòmica és molt semblant a la descrita en altres insectes per a PTTH, per tant confirmant aquest gen com al codificant de la PTTH de pugons. Tenint en compte que la seua localització i distribució és molt semblant a la de les l-DN (vore dalt) que expressen el gen *tim*, es va realitzar una localització combinada dels transcrits de *Ptth* amb *tim*. Aquesta aproximació confirmà que les neurones que expressen *Ptth* no corresponen a les l-DN, sinó que estan disposades adjacents a aquestes últimes.

Discussió

El principal objectiu del present treball és l'estudi del paper que puguen tindre alguns dels elements del putatiu rellotge circadià de pugons en la resposta estacional d'aquests insectes.

Primerament, s'ha completat la caracterització del gen *tim*, donant com a producte una proteïna amb un domini TIM (pfam04821). A banda, s'han trobat per al gen *vri* dues CDS (en anglès *coding DNA sequence*, seqüència d'ADN codificant) diferents de les prèviament descrites. En general, s'ha trobat una gran varietat de processats alternatius en els transcrits dels gens del rellotge, especialment per a *Clk* i *cyc*. Encara que no s'ha trobat associació entre cap processat alternatiu i una soca o fotoperíode, algunes variants són especialment interessants donat que sense trencar la pauta de lectura, introdueixen/eliminen NLS (en anglès *nuclear localisation signal*, senyal de localització nuclear). Aquests senyals podrien ser rellevants en la funció com a factor transcripcional que aquests gens porten a terme en el nucli de la cèl·lula.

A més, s'ha estudiat la ritmicitat de l'expressió dels gens del putatiu rellotge circadià de pugons. Els resultats presents confirmen la ritmicitat dels gens *per* i *tim*, amb un pic d'expressió al crepuscle i una baixada forta al final de la nit. Aquest patró s'ha trobat en diversos insectes incloent panderoles, abelles, vespes, formigues, diversos drosofilids i ortòpters. D'altra banda, els resultats obtinguts no indiquen una ritmicitat clara dels gens *cyc*, *Pdp1* o *vri* trobades en anàlisis prèvies. No obstant, l'absència d'oscil·lació a nivell de transcrit té precedents en insectes (per exemple el hemípter *Riptortus pedestris*) i, per tant, no podem descartar un ritme a nivell de proteïna. Un dels resultats més interessants ha sigut el ràpid esmorteïment de l'oscil·lació dels gens *per* i *tim* en DD (obscuritat total). Aquesta característica podria estar associada al model de fotoperiodisme basat en un rellotge circadià amb ràpid esmorteïment, descrit per a la resposta estacional de pugons en el qual s'explica l'absència d'una resposta típica als fotoperíodes complexos. La distribució d'elements reguladors en la regió 5' dels gens del rellotge confirma el seu paper en aquest. És important destacar la presència d'elements reguladors en *cyc*, cosa que ens indica un rellotge centrat en *cyc* com la majoria d'insectes, i no com en drosofilids en els quals està centrat en *Clk*.

A banda, s'ha vist que els nivells d'expressió mitjans dels gens que conformen el bucle negatiu del rellotge augmenten la seua expressió en SD respecte de LD en pugons de la soca holocíclica YR2, mentre que en la soca anholocíclica es mantenen en nivells semblants. Aquest augment d'expressió està doncs, associat a la inducció de la resposta sexual. Aquest patró s'ha observat en diversos insectes en els quals un fotoperíode típic d'hivern produeix un augment de l'expressió d'alguns dels gens del rellotge. Per a confirmar el paper d'aquests gens en la resposta estacional

del pugó seria convenient portar a terme experiments de RNAi sobre aquests i analitzar l'efecte en la formació de sexuats.

Pel que fa a la localització dels transcrits de *per* i *tim*, aquests s'han trobat principalment en dues regions del cervells en grups de cèl·lules anomenats DN i LN (vore dalt). Aquesta distribució és semblant a la descrita en altres insectes, en els quals aquestes regions s'han associat a ritmes circadians i, en alguns casos, a ritmes estacionals. És important destacar ací els experiments de microcauterització desenvolupats en el pugó *Megoura viciae*, en els quals amb tinció de para-aldehid fucsina es caracteritzaren les cèl·lules neurosecretores (en anglès, neurosecretory cells o NSC) dels sistema nerviós central i algunes de les seues funcions. La destrucció de «NSC group I» en la regió descrita com a *pars intercerebralis* del protocervell, induí la fase sexual del cicle en pugons destinats a reproducció partenogenètica (virginópares). Per tant, anomenaren «virginoparina» al factor produït en aquestes NSC. A més, la destrucció de la regió adjacent lateral a les «NSC group I» coneguda com a *pars lateralis*, sense afectar a les «NSC group I», produïa els mateixos efectes. Per tant, arribaren a la conclusió de que les neurones de la *pars lateralis* controlaven a les «NSC group I» en la *pars intercerebralis*. En aquest context, és rellevant destacar que el grup de cèl·lules que expressen *per* i *tim* que nosaltres hem descrit com a DN està localitzat precisament en la regió *pars lateralis*, per tant suggerint que les DN i possiblement els gens del rellotge circadià estiguen regulant la producció de virginoparina, és a dir, la resposta estacional.

Respecte als elements que podrien formar part de l'eixida del rellotge circadià, hem centrat l'estudi en el gen que codifica per al neuropèptid *Pdf*,

l'amina biogènica melatonina i els gens *AANAT* que podrien regular la seua síntesi, i l'hormona PTTH.

Pdf és un neuropèptid conservat en Panartròpodes, que en insectes està generalment lligat a la regulació dels ritmes circadians. El seu paper com a eixida del rellotge s'ha estudiat principalment en *Drosophila melanogaster*, encara que s'han fet estudis en altres insectes, i s'utilitza normalment com a marcador d'algunes de les neurones rellotge (que expressen gens del rellotge i s'encarreguen del control dels ritmes circadians). Malgrat la seua ubiqüitat en insectes, els nostres resultats afegeixen més suport a la hipòtesi de que *Pdf* està absent en pugons. Aquest fet planteja una qüestió: si finalment *Pdf* està absent en pugons, quin factor és l'encarregat de la regulació dels ritmes circadians?

En aquest context convé valorar el paper que podria tindre la melatonina en la regulació no només dels ritmes circadians, sinó també del fotoperiodisme. En mamífers està clar que la melatonina intervé en ambdós ritmes biològics. Normalment es troben nivells més alts durant la nit pel que fa als ritmes circadians, i també nivells més alts a l'hivern pel que fa als ritmes estacionals.

En el present treball hem aconseguit localitzar melatonina en cèl·lules del SOG i TGM. Primerament es troba concentrada en els soma de les neurones i al llarg del temps es desplaça cap als axons. Aquesta distribució contrasta amb la trobada en el lepidòpter *Antheraea pernyi*, en el qual la melatonina es troba en el protocervell. A més, hem trobat dos processos que arriben fins al protocervell que podrien formar connexions sinàptiques amb altres neurones, incloent les DN i les LN. No obstant, per a poder observar aquestes connexions, seria convenient obtindre la localització de les

proteïnes PER i TIM amb anticossos específics que facilitarien l'observació dels axons de les DN i LN.

A més de localitzar les neurones productores de melatonina, hem portat a terme la quantificació d'aquesta mitjançant ESI HPLC MS/MS. Els resultats obtinguts mostren que no hi han diferències significatives en el contingut de melatonina entre dos moments del dia (ZT6 i ZT18), per tant suggerint que no hi ha un ritme circadià d'aquest factor. No obstant, cal tindre en compte que el baix nombre de punts de mostreig podria estar emmascarant un ritme circadià de melatonina real. A més, la quantificació es realitzà en pugons sencers i, per tant, inclou també la melatonina produïda per embrions en l'abdomen. Per a poder determinar amb seguretat si la concentració de melatonina varia de manera circadiana seria convenient realitzar noves quantificacions només amb caps de pugons (que continguen el sistema nerviós central) incloent més punts de mostreig al llarg del cicle dia/nit.

La quantificació també ha permés observar un augment de melatonina en condicions de SD respecte a LD en pugons de la soca holocíclica YR2, mentre que en pugons de la soca anholocíclica GR els nivells permaneixen constants en pugons crescuts en els dos fotoperíodes. Aquests resultats comporten una associació de l'augment de melatonina a la formació de sexuals. Aquest fet concorda amb estudis previs en els quals es comprovà que l'aplicació de melatonina via ingesta de dieta artificial produeix una inducció parcial de la resposta estacional de pugons. No obstant, en el mateix estudi no observaren canvis en la concentració de melatonina entre diferents condicions de fotoperíode. Aquesta discrepància podria donar-se per la baixa quantitat de material analitzat o per les diferents estratègies

seguides per a la inducció de la fase sexual. A més, nosaltres recomanem l'aplicació de luzindol, un antagonista del receptor de melatonina, que podria utilitzar-se per a bloquejar els receptors de melatonina de pugons, que encara estan per identificar, i veure l'efecte que tindria en la resposta estacional. És important assenyalar que en estudis recents en *Antheraea pernyi*, melatonina i dopamina s'han postulat com a factors antagònics involucrats en el comptador del sistema estacional.

Respecte a l'estudi dels gens AANAT candidats a regular la síntesi de melatonina, hem portat a terme la identificació de quatre homòlegs al gen *Dat* de *Drosophila* i s'ha caracteritzat la seua seqüència i l'expressió.

Els quatre gens homòlegs agrupen en el clade de i-AANATs, en el qual també agrupen AANATs d'altres insectes que s'ha demostrat que participen en la síntesi de melatonina. Pel que fa al patró d'expressió en pugons de les diferents soques crescuts en els dos fotoperíodes, s'ha trobat una concomitància entre els nivell de melatonina i els gens *AANAT2* i *AANAT3*. No obstant açò, la localització dels transcrits d'aquests gens amb melatonina revela que es produeixen en neurones diferents i, per tant, no estarien encarregats de la seua síntesi. Dels homòlegs restants, *AANAT1* és l'únic que mostra un augment en SD respecte a LD, encara que es dona en les dues soques. Quedaria per tant pendent l'anàlisi de la colocalització de melatonina amb els transcrits d'*AANAT1* per a confirmar que aquesta és la *AANAT* encarregada de la seua síntesi. Així i tot, el fet de que en la soca anholocíclica també es done un augment de l'expressió en SD podria explicar-se per les funcions addicionals que la *AANAT1* podria tindre en l'esclerotització de la cutícula, com podrien estar indicant els patrons

d'expressió observats al llarg del cicle dia/nit, en els quals es veu una baixada d'expressió al llarg del temps.

Per últim, es va identificar el gen de pugons que codifica l'homòleg de PTTH. En *Rhodnius prolixus*, PTTH està implicat en la transducció de la informació circadiana del rellotge central al rellotge de la glàndula protoràcica, sincronitzant així els nivells d'ecdisteroids en tot l'organisme. A més, en el lepidòpter *Antheraea pernyi*, s'ha trobat que el rellotge circadià central que resideix en certes neurones del cervell, produeix un ritme en els nivells de melatonina que indueix en neurones adjacents un ritme en la producció de PTTH. Aquesta cascada senyalització ha estat relacionada amb la transducció del senyal fotoperiòdic que activa la resposta estacional.

Nosaltres hem aconseguit identificar per primera volta el gen *Ptth* homòleg de pugons, que no s'havia pogut identificar en diversos estudis previs de transcriptòmica i peptidòmica. La proteïna que putativament codifica està poc conservada a nivell de seqüència, excepte en la regió del pèptid madur, com és habitual en la majoria d'insectes. Per a estudiar la seua possible implicació en ritmes circadians, recomanem l'anàlisi de la seua expressió al llarg del cicle dia/nit. A més, la seua localització en dues parelles de neurones en la part dorsal del protocervell confirmà que es troben en aposició a les DN prèviament descrites que expressen els gens *per* i *tim*. Per tant, de manera semblant a la descrita en *Antheraea pernyi*, podria estar participant en la transducció dels ritmes circadians. No obstant, caldria recordar ací els treballs de mircocauterització de les cèl·lules neurosecretores identificades amb para aldehyd fucsina. En aquests experiments, es descriuen les «NSC group II», les quals estan constituïdes per dues parelles de neurones en la part dorsal del protocervell. La

destrucció d'aquest grup de neurones produí defectes en la muda dels pugons i per tant, els autors assumiren que eren les cèl·lules productores de PTH. La distribució de l'expressió de *Ptth* que nosaltres hem observat coincideix clarament amb les «NSC group II». Assumint que aquestes «NSC group II» són de fet les neurones productores de *Ptth* que nosaltres hem observat, podem dir que *Ptth* no tindria un paper en la regulació de la resposta estacional, donat que la destrucció d'aquestes no va tindre cap efecte en el mode de reproducció dels pugons.

Així doncs, considerant el conjunt dels nostres resultats, hem aportat nous avanços en el coneixement del putatiu sistema circadià de pugons i alguns dels elements que podrien participar en la resposta estacional. El paper de les DN i LN en la regulació del mode de reproducció dels pugons queda pendent de confirmació amb experiments de microcauterització i, sobretot, experiments de RNAi contra gens del rellotge. També hem vist que la melatonina és un bon candidat a participar en la regulació de la resposta estacional, encara que seria convenient confirmar aquest paper amb el bloqueig de la seua senyalització amb l'antagonista luzindol. Addicionalment, és important acabar l'estudi del paper de les AANATs, especialment la localització dels transcrits d'*AANAT1*, en el control de la síntesi de melatonina. De nou, experiments de RNAi contra els gens *AANAT* donarien una resposta clara al paper en la síntesi de melatonina i en la resposta estacional. Respecte al paper de *Ptth* en el fotoperiodisme de pugons, queda descartat *a priori*, encara que podria tindre un paper modulador. A més quedaria per investigar la funció de *Ptth* en els ritmes circadians. En general, els estudis de localització dels diferents elements proporcionen informació bàsica sobre la neuroanatomia del sistema nerviós

del pugó que podrien aprofitar per a estudis futurs de la resposta estacional de pugons.

Conclusions

1. Els transcrits dels gens que conformen el nucli de rellotge circadià (*period*, *timeless*, *Clock*, *cycle*, *Pdp1* i *vriille*) s'han caracteritzat completament, revelant un alt grau de variants d'empalmament alternatiu. No obstant, no s'ha trobat cap correlació amb cap soca o fotoperíode en particular.
2. L'anàlisi de l'expressió mostrà una ritmicitat circadiana robusta en els gens *per* i *tim*, ambdós amb màxima expressió al final del dia i mínims al final de la nit, confirmant el seu paper en el rellotge circadià. A més, aquesta ritmicitat es veu ràpidament esmorteïda en obscuritat total, donant suport al model de resposta estacional basada en un oscil·lador circadià esmorteït. Addicionalment, els gens *per*, *cyc* i *Pdp1* contenen elements reguladors típics de rellotges circadians centrats en *cyc*.
3. La localització dels transcrits de *per* i *tim* en les regions antero-dorsal (DN) i lateral (LN) del protocervell és semblant a la descrita en altres insectes. A més, les DN es troben en la *pars lateralis*, una regió del protocervell prèviament descrita com a essencial per a la resposta estacional de pugons. Aquest resultat suggereix la participació dels gens del rellotge en la regulació de la resposta estacional.
4. L'acumulació de diverses evidències, incloent l'absència d'un homòleg del gen *Pdf* al genoma d'*A. pisum* conjuntament amb la

manca de detecció dels transcrits en anàlisis transcriptòmiques i de PDF amb diversos anticossos i anàlisis proteòmiques, suggereixen que PDF podria estar genuïnament absent en pugons.

5. La localització *in situ* de melatonina en el sistema nerviós de pugons il·lustrat en aquesta tesi és el segon cas descrit en insectes i el primer en hemimetàbols. A més, és la primera volta que s'ha trobat melatonina en neurones distribuïdes al llarg dels ganglis en insectes en compte del cervell. S'ha mostrat que la melatonina es troba principalment en el soma fins a l'estadi larvari 3 i que després es mobilitza cap als axons. No obstant, no s'han trobat diferències entre soques i fotoperíodes en la distribució o la mobilització de la melatonina.
6. S'ha demostrat que hi ha un augment en els nivells de melatonina en pugons de la soca holocíclica YR2 en condicions de SD en els que s'ha activat la resposta estacional (formació de sexuals) respecte a les condicions de LD. Aquest augment no es produeix en els pugons de la soca anholocíclica en condicions de SD. Aquest fet indica que la melatonina probablement està involucrada en la transmissió de la resposta estacional.
7. Encara que s'han trobat nivells d'expressió d'alguns dels gens d'*AANAT* concomitants amb els de melatonina i malgrat que l'expressió d'*AANAT2* i *AANAT3* s'ha localitzat en els ganglis, el seu paper la regulació de la síntesi de melatonina no queda clar donat que no s'ha trobat colocalització de cap d'elles amb melatonina.

8. S'ha identificat i caracteritzat el gen *Ptth* de pugons. A més, la localització dels seus transcrits en la regió dorsal del protocervell indica que es tracta del grup II de NSC prèviament descrit com al lloc de producció de PTTH. Conseqüentment, s'ha descartat un paper directe de PTTH en la resposta estacional.

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IX. Annexes

The annexes of this thesis are included in the DVD attached containing the following elements:

ANNEXES	Description
Table_primers.ods	IX.1
README.txt	instructions on how to access different files.
SPSS_syntax_SE.txt	syntax used in SPSS for single effects analysis.
pGEMvector.txt	sequence of pGEM T easy vector (Promega).
accession_no.odt	IX.2
1-circadian clock core	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-gene models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-period 2-timeless 3-Clock 4-cycle 5-Pdp1 6-vrille Summary_5UTR.ods..... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> annotated models built with Uniprot UGENE. summary of regulatory elements (E- and V/P-box).
2-RTqPCR	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-experiment1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-YR2 2-GR 2-experiment2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-LD 2-DD Exp2_ANOVA_ZTs.odp 3-cosinor_analysis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-experiment1 2-experiment2 Summary_cosinor_core.ods.. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> raw expression data from RT-qPCR Experiment 1. raw expression data from RT-qPCR Experiment 2. summary of ANOVA tests comparing variable ZT. input data and raw results from COSINOR tests. summary of COSINOR tests comparing variable ZT.
3-microscopy	confocal image stacks shown in section IV.1.3.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-period 2-timeless 3-combined_pertim 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> confocal image stack shown in Figure IV.10. confocal image stack shown in Figure IV.12. confocal image stack shown in Figure IV.14.

continues in next page

■ 2-circadian clock output	
■ 1-PDF	
■ 1-gene model	annotated model built with Uniprot UGENE.
■ 2-microscopy	confocal image stacks shown in Figure IV.16.
■ 2-melatonin	
■ 1-microscopy	confocal image stacks described in section IV.2.2.
■ 2-quantification	
HPLC_MEL.ods	HPLC-MS/MS results. Includes standard curve.
insect_melatonin.ods.....	summary of melatonin detection in insects.
■ 3-AANATs	
■ 1-gene models	annotated models built with Uniprot UGENE.
■ 1-A. pisum	
■ 2-M. persicae	
■ 2-RTqPCR	
■ 1-experiment1	raw expression data from RT-qPCR Experiment 1.
■ 1-YR2	
■ 2-GR	
■ 2-cosinor_analysis	input data and raw results from COSINOR tests.
■ 1-AANAT1	
■ 2-AANAT2	
■ 3-AANAT3	
■ 4-AANAT4	
cosinor_aanat.ods	summary of COSINOR tests comparing variable ZT.
■ 3-microscopy	confocal image stacks shown in Figure IV.24.
■ 4-PTTH	
■ 1-gene model	annotated model built with Uniprot UGENE.
■ 2-microscopy	
■ 1-Ptth	confocal image stacks shown in Figure IV.27.
■ 2-combined_pertimPtth	confocal image stacks shown in Figure IV.28.
Ptth_polymorphisms.ods	polymorphisms found in <i>Ptth</i> mRNA sequences.

Table IX.1. List of primers used for PCR amplification¹, sequencing and RT-qPCR of the genes characterised in the present study².

Gene Name	Primer Name	Primer sequence 5'-3'	Gene Name	Primer Name	Primer sequence 5'-3'
<i>Period</i>			<i>Timeless</i>		
	Per-F1	GGTTGCTATTTAAGAGGTTACAG		Tim-F1	ATTCTGGTTAGTTTAAATATCACC
	Per-F2	TTCCATAGGTACGTGTACG		Tim-F2	TTACTTGGGCTGAATTGGATGATG
	Per-F3	CGTGTACGAATTTGCTTAGAATG		Tim-F3	TACGAAAATACTATATTGTGGATG
	Per-F4	ACTCGAGCTGATTATGACTCTGG		Tim-F4	GTTTCATGAGGGTCTTAAATATC
	Per-F5	ATTGTGTCCATGAATGATGGTCT		Tim-F5	GAATACTTGCATGACTTAATAGT
	Per-F6	CCGTGGTCTGGTCGAGTAGA		Tim-F6	GTGCTTGTATGATGCATCATGTA
	Per-F7	GACCACGACTCCACGCTCTTTATC		Tim-F7	CGAACAAAACGCTGAGTCTCCTGC
	Per-F8	TCATCAGAAGATTCAAGTGG		Tim-F8	CAGTGGCCGGTGGGATACACTCTAC
	Per-F9	GTTCAACCAGATACAATACC		Tim-F9	CACCTCATACCGATGTTTATTGC
	Per-F12	ATCTATCGATACCAATGAACACG		Tim-F10	TTTGTCTACCTGACACAATGTA
	Per-F13	ACCCGTGGAACAATCAAGCCAAAC		Tim-F11	TTTCAACCAATCATTTTGAAAAC
	Per-QF1	ACCACCTGAGCATCAAGACATTGC		Tim-F12	GTGTATCTACGAAGCAACGAATG
	Per-QF2	AAGACGGAACCTTCATCAAGCAGTG		Tim-F14	TTCTGTTTCAAACATAACGAAGTG
	Per-QF3	GCATCAATGCTTCAAAAATGG		Tim-F15	GGACACAATGTAATACAACGGCG
	Per-QF4	GCATCAATGATACTGTTTTAAAGGC		Tim-F16	ATAATATCTAGTGGGAATCTTTAAC
	Per-R1	ATATCAGGAATGTATATAGTTTG		Tim-F17	CCAAAACAGTTCAATGTGCCAAG
	Per-R2	TGCTGTTTGACGAGATCACATCCAT		Tim-F18	TACTTACATCTAATTCACACATTG
	Per-R3	TGGTCAGAACAATTACCAGACAT		Tim-F19	TACTTACATCTAATTCACACATTG
	Per-R4	ACGTCAGGATTAATAGGACCCTG		Tim-QF	TCGAGTTCTATCGCCAAACTGCTG
	Per-R5	AATGTCATCCGATCGTTAGGATG		Tim-R1	TCGATGTACGCAGTAATATTGTC
	Per-R6	ACTGTTCTGTTCACTAACATAGG		Tim-R2	GATGGCCAAATGCAAAATGTCTGAC
	Per-R7	CATTTAGTGATGCTTATGTGAC		Tim-R3	GAATGAAATCAGTTTGAAAGATAC
	Per-R8	AGTATAACATATCACTAAGTTAC		Tim-R4	GCTTTGCTCATCGACATCATCCA
	Per-R9	TGTGGCAAACCTAGGTGACGTTG		Tim-R5	TACATGATGCATCATAACAAGCAC
	Per-R10	ACTTGCACTTTGTTCTGAATC		Tim-R6	GAGTGACGTAGTGTTCGAC
	Per-R11	AGTATAACATATCACTAAGTTAC		Tim-R7	CACTGTCCTTGTGATAATTCAGA
	Per-R12	AGTATAACATATCACTAAGTTAC		Tim-R8	CATAGCGATATACGACTCAGAG
	Per-QR1	TTTGGCCTGGGCTTGGTTGTATTG		Tim-R9	TTCTAATGAAATGTATGGTCTTC
	Per-QR2	TTGACAACCTTGCCTGGCGAGGTTG		Tim-R10	GAAGAGTGTTCCTCAGAACAGTC
	Per-QR3	TGTGTGCTTGGTCTTTTAAATGCC		Tim-R12	ACTGTAATGTTGGTACATCCTGC
				Tim-R13	ATTTTGTGTTAAAGATTCCCACTAG
				Tim-R14	TGGGACATAATCATTACCAACGC
				Tim-QR	TGATTGATTCTGGAGAGGTGTTGC
				Tim-QR2	TTTCAACCAATCATTTTGAAAAC

1 Primers used in RT-qPCR analysis are indicated in bold letters.

2 A detailed localisation of the primers in the gene models can be found in the databases contained in the CD included in the annex.

Table VIII.1. (Continued).

Gene Name	Primer Name	Primer sequence 5'-3'	Gene Name	Primer Name	Primer sequence 5'-3'
<i>Clock</i>			<i>Pdp1</i>		
	Clock-F1	CGACATCGAGCATACATAATAG		PdP1-F1	CGTCGGTAGTCGAAGCACAGTA
	Clock-F2	CGATTATACACCGTGTGCATG		PdP1-F2	AGTCTCGACAAAGCTGTCTCC
	Clock-F3	ATACGTACCGGACTGCACCTCA		PdP1-F3	ATGTACGAAGCAAAGTGTATTG
	Clock-F4	GATGACCAGTATGATGATGAAC		PdP1-F4	GCGTCGTCCAGCAGAGACTTCG
	Clock-F5	GGTTATGAGTATTACCATATTG		PdP1-F5	GCAC TCCGAGATCGTCTTTC
	Clock-F6	GTTATGCAGCATTCTTATTC		PdP1-F6	AGCCGCAGCCAATGTTTGTACC
	Clock-F7	CAGAATATGGTCGATGAGGGAG		PdP1-F7	GAAGCCGCAGCCAATGGTAAAG
	Clock-QF	ATCCACACAGACTTCCGAGC		PdP1-R1	ATGGTGCATACAAAATCCAGC
	Clock-R1	TCATTGAGCGTTGAACAAATG		PdP1-R2	GGTGCGGCTTCAATTCCTCGTC
	Clock-R2	GAACATCATTAGACTGATTAC		PdP1-R3	CATTACATAGCATCTGATGTCCG
	Clock-R3	ATGAGTCTGTACTTGATTGTTT		PdP1-R4	GATTCCATCTGGTCAATCAGG
	Clock-R4	ATGCTGGCTTCCAATCATTGTC			
	Clock-R5	GTTTTGAGTTCATTGGTGGTAAC	<i>Vrille</i>		
	Clock-QR	TGTCCTCCTCCCTCATCGAC		Vrille-F1	AGAATACACGCATGTTCACTGCG
	Clock-QR2	CATAACTTGTTCATTTTCGTTCTGTCG		Vrille-F2	CGTTTTCAGATATCAATACAG
				Vrille-F3	ATGGTAGCGGACACGGCCAACAG
				Vrille-F4	TCTGGCATTAGCCTGGGCGTCCG
				Vrille-F6	ACCAGACTCAAGTCCGAAGTGG
				Vrille-F7	GACTGCGACAGCCCTGTGACCC
				Vrille-F8	GTTATGGCTTCTCTGCTTAC
				Vrille-F9	CCTACAAACGAACAAGTGTGA
				Vrille-F10	CGCCACAACACATGGATAACGCTC
				Vrille-F11	TCGACGACGGGGCAGTTTCACTCG
				Vrille-F12	CACCAACTCCAGCAACAACAGC
				Vrille-F13	GGAATCAGTGGCGAGGCTGTGG
				Vrille-F14	CTCCCTCCTGAACGCCGCCGAC
				Vrille-R1	CCTATGTATGGATTTCGGTGC
				Vrille-R2	AGTTGACCGCAACGGTGGTGG
				Vrille-R3	GGTCGACAGGGCTGTGCGAGTC
				Vrille-R4	ACTCACGCTGCTTGCCTGCGC
				Vrille-R5	CCGACTGTTCCATGTGCTGAC
				Vrille-R6	TTGAGGGTGGCCACTTCGGACGC
				Vrille-R7	TCCGCATCCCACGGTGGACTG
				Vrille-R8	CCACTTCCGCTGCTCAGCTCG
				Vrille-R9	TTGCTGATGCTGGTGTGGTTTAG
				Vrille-R10	GTATAACAACAAAATACCTGTGG
				Vrille-R11	CGTCGTCATAGCCTGCCGCCG
<i>Cycle</i>					
	Cycle-F1	TTGGAGAAGACTTCTCGTCGTCA			
	Cycle-F2	ATACGATTTCTGACAGCCGCTGTCC			
	Cycle-F3	TGGAAAGGATCTAAAATGAAGCC			
	Cycle-F4	GTAATCCAGTGTACTGGTTACT			
	Cycle-F5	AGTTCACCGCTGGCGATGCTCA			
	Cycle-F6	ACGTTGTGCGAGTAGTGGTGGCG			
	Cycle-F7	ACAACATACAAAACAGTACCCGAC			
	Cycle-R1	GCTATTGACTCGACTAATT			
	Cycle-R2	GTACGCGCAGAGGCCATGGTA			
	Cycle-R3	TCAACAGATTCACGCTGTCCCTG			
	Cycle-R4	TCCCAGATACATCCTCACATTC			
	Cycle-R5	CAGCAGTAGAGGAAGCCAGTCCG			
	Cycle-R6	TTCAGCTGCACGAAAACTAATCAA			
	Cycle-R7	CATCCTGAGTACAGACAGTTTATC			
	Cycle-QR1	CCGAGTCATTATTGGTATTGGTTCG			

Table VIII.1. (Continued).

Gene Name	Primer Name	Primer sequence 5'-3'	Gene Name	Primer Name	Primer sequence 5'-3'
<i>AANAT1</i>			<i>AANAT4</i>		
	AANAT1-F1	AGCTATTTACAATATGGAATGAC		AANAT4-F1	ATAACGGTCCTAAGGTAGCGAGT
	AANAT1-F2	CACATTCACGTTGAAAGTAAACGTCG		AANAT4-F2	GGTAGCGAGTCGAGGTCGAGCTC
	AANAT1-F3	CGATGCGTATAGTGGTTGAAGGGC		AANAT4-F3	CAAAGCTGGACGAGAAACTGATG
	AANAT1-F4	CTCTTGTGGATTAGGATATTGG		AANAT4-F4	GCAGTATCAAACATAGATCGTAATG
	AANAT1-F5	GACGTAGAAGAAGACGACGAGG		AANAT4-F5	CTCCGAGCCCTACTTATAAGC
	AANAT1-R1	TGTAACCTGCTAGTAGACCAAAGC		AANAT4-F6	AGTGGTTCGTATCTATAACATTG
	AANAT1-R2	ACATACACTTTGGCACCTCTGTG		AANAT4-F7	TCGTATCTATACATTGTAAACC
	AANAT1-R3	TGGCCTCTATAAGCTTCATTAC		AANAT4-R1	TATATTAGAGAAGTAAACACATGGAT
	AANAT1-R4	GAACTCTGTTTCTTCCAACAACGTG		AANAT4-R2	GAAAATTGTGTGAGGAGGCTGTG
	AANAT1-R5	TGATGAGACGAAAGTTTGACGGC		AANAT4-R3	ACGTACATCATTGATACCCCTAA
<i>AANAT2</i>			<i>Ptth</i>		
	AANAT2-F1	CAACGGTAACAAGCTATTCTTCG		Ptth-F1	TCGGTAACCTCAACGAATCACGC
	AANAT2-F2	AATGGATGTGTACCATTGAGGTC		Ptth-F2	TTTATAGTGGAGGATAGTTCATG
	AANAT2-F3	AATGGATGGACACTGCAGATAG		Ptth-F3	TGGAGGGATAGTTCATGAGACCTC
	AANAT2-F4	GCGTTTAAAGCTGTATCTCCTGATG		Ptth-F4	ATCACGGTTGCCTGCTACTGTTC
	AANAT2-R1	AATTTAGTCGATTCAGGAAGGAC		Ptth-R1	AGTTCAGAAATAAGAAAGAACAC
	AANAT2-R2	TATCTATGTGTGAATTTGCTGTG		Ptth-R2	AATTGCCTTTTGCCTATTATTTTG
	AANAT2-R3	GCTCGACTTTATCCAAAATGCCG		Ptth-R3	AAACGAAACGATAAAAATGTCGTG
				Ptth-R4	GAATGATTCGTCGTTCCGCAAG
				Ptth-R5	GCTCGTCACGCTGCTGTATCAGG
				Ptth-R6	TAATGTCCAAATCGAAATACGCC
<i>AANAT3</i>			Others		
	AANAT3-F1	ACTGTTGAAGAGTTATTGATGAAG		SP6	TATTTAGGTGACACTATAGAA
	AANAT3-F2	TGATGAAGTGACGTTGTGCGTTG		T7	GTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGC
	AANAT3-F3	ATCGACAAGTCTAAAGAGTTGGC		Rpl7QF	GCGCGCCGAGGCTTAT
	AANAT3-F6	AACATGGATGAAATCAAAAACACC		Rpl7QR	CCGGATTTCCTTGCATTTCTTG
	AANAT3-F7	CTATCAACGTAGTACCTATAACTG			
	AANAT3-R1	ATAGCAAAGTACTATCCATGTAC			
	AANAT3-R2	TACAGATTTAGTTTGGCATATAAC			
	AANAT3-R3	TGAGGAAACTGTGTCTTGAACAC			
	AANAT3-R4	GATTACTATTAGATCGGATAGC			

Table IX.2. Summary of gene splicing variants of genes deposited at NCBI database, including accession numbers and size of transcripts and CDS.

Gene Name	Splicing Variant	Strain	Size of Transcript ¹ (nt)	Size of Predicted CDS (nt / amino acids)	Accession Number	Comments
<i>period</i>	B	YR2	3315	3054 / 1018	KY305403	Contains the alternative in-frame exon 4 (168 nt)
<i>timeless</i>	A	YR2	2744	2037 / 679	KY305404	
<i>timeless</i>	B	YR2	2957	2250 / 750	KY305405	Contains the alternative in-frame exon 11 (213 nt)
<i>Clock</i>	A	YR2	2684	1839 / 613	KY305406	Contains the alternative in-frame exon 11 (153 nt)
<i>Clock</i>	B	YR2	2758	1773 / 591	KY305407	Includes intronic region upstream exon 3
<i>Clock</i>	D	YR2	2531	1686 / 562	KY305408	Same as <i>Clock</i> -A but not including exon 11
<i>cycle</i>	A	YR2	2777	1944 / 648	KY305409	
<i>cycle</i>	B	YR2	2870	2037 / 679	KY305410	Same as <i>cycle</i> -A but including the in-frame exon 4 (93 nt)
<i>cycle</i>	C	YR2	2362	1413 / 471	KY305411	Same as <i>cycle</i> -A but not including exons 3 to 8
<i>cycle</i>	F	YR2	2870	2037 / 679	KY305412	Same as <i>cycle</i> -A but including the in-frame exon 3 (93 nt)
<i>Pdp1</i>	A	YR2	932	900 / 300	KY305413	Includes extra 21 nt region encoding the heptapeptide
<i>Pdp1</i>	B	YR2	911	879 / 293	KY305414	Lacks 21 nt region encoding the heptapeptide
<i>vriille</i>	A	YR2	1233	1047 / 349	KY305415	
<i>vriille</i>	B	YR2	1111	951 / 317	KY305416	Lacks 95 nt in the 5' region of exon 5 keeping the same ORF
<i>Ptth</i>	-	YR2	1049	654 / 218	KY305417	
<i>Ptth</i>	-	GR	992	654 / 218	KY305418	

¹ Size corresponds to the amplified PCR fragment.